

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D7.5 Baseline report: Communication and information – Update M26

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is an update of D7.1 “Baseline report: Communication and information” which presented a description and analysis of national COVID-19 communication by different COVINFORM partners in 15 countries: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Israel, Ireland, Italy, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom, Switzerland, and the United States of America.

This deliverable focuses on the evolution and respective changes of COVID-19 communication and information from March 2021 to September 2022, across the aforementioned target countries – following the suggested COVID-19 communication model in D7.4 “Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation”.

This deliverable also presents global analyses based on each country report regarding major relevant changes in communication strategies, plans, and practices, as well as of the review of research and evaluation analysis to national and international communication on Covid-19 crisis and successful communication approaches provided by each country report.

Moreover, it also provides a synthesis based on a global analysis of the main learnings, best practices, and guidelines provided in each country report.

Contents

Executive Summary	4
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Evolution of COVID-19 communication strategies, plans, and practices.....	8
2.1 Austria	9
2.2 Belgium.....	15
2.3 Cyprus.....	20
2.4 England	23
2.5 Germany	30
2.6 Greece	37
2.7 Ireland.....	43
2.8 Israel	48
2.9 Italy.....	53
2.10 Portugal	56
2.11 Romania.....	63
2.12 Spain	68
2.13 Sweden	71
2.14 Switzerland	74
2.15 Wales.....	79
3 Global analysis of the evolution of COVID-19 communication	85
3.1 Communication structures & responsibilities	86
3.2 National and International COVID-19 Communication Evaluation.....	88
3.3 Main Lessons and Recommendations.....	89
3.4 Relevant Indicators.....	91
4 Conclusions.....	96
References.....	97
Austria	98
Belgium.....	99
Cyprus.....	100
England.....	102
Germany.....	105
Greece	107
Ireland	110
Israel.....	112

Italy.....	112
Portugal	113
Romania.....	115
Spain.....	116
Sweden	119
Switzerland.....	120
Wales.....	123

Figures

Figure 1. Adaptation of the COVID-19 communication model suggested in D7.4 of COVINFORM project... 8

Tables

Table 1. Identification of structural changes in COVID-19 communication across all countries. 8

Table 2. Main 10 key principles for effective risk and crisis communication..... 92

1 Introduction

This deliverable update identifies, describes, and reviews the evolution of communication strategies, plans, and practices, as well as the main lessons learnt, from March 2021 to September 2022, across the following 15 target countries: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Israel, Ireland, Italy, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom, Switzerland, and the United States of America.

As this deliverable is focussing on the evolution of the pandemic from the early phase up to almost two years after, this report presents a global cross-analysis on major changes across the countries concerning COVID-19 communication and information rather than just an exhaustive individual presentation of all country reports. This analysis was conducted according to the information included in each country's report, which elaborated on the following aspects:

- The review and description of communication strategies, plans, and practices of governments and public health authorities throughout this time on a national level, including strategies to influence behaviour change, and a detailed analysis of factors influencing communication practices;
- The review of research and professional analysis to national communication on the Covid-19 pandemic;
- Main lessons learnt, best practices, and successful communication approaches in each country, as well as relevant indicators that can be used to evaluate communication efficiency.

The two templates that guided the work conducted by each partner in D7.1 (Excel template used to register communication events and sources, as well as a Word document with user guidelines; and a Word template including a set of questions to be answered considering the three aspects aforementioned) were updated given the pandemic period addressed then.

In this deliverable, Section 2 provides a description of the evolution of COVID-19 communication between March 2021 and September 2022 in each of the 15 countries aforementioned, focusing on common major changes - through the lens of the suggested COVID-19 communication model in D7.4 "Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation".

Section 3 provides an overall analysis of the changes identified and described in section 2, as well as a global analysis of the review of research and professional analysis to national communication on Covid-19 crisis (communication?) and successful communication approaches provided by each country report. It also provides a subsection with a synthesis based on a global analysis of the main learnings, best practices, and guidelines. Section 4 is a synthesis of the global conclusions provided in each country report.

2 Evolution of COVID-19 communication strategies, plans, and practices

This section presents the evolution of strategies and plans between March 2021 and September 2022 by identifying and describing the changes regarding major relevant topics per country, following the suggested COVID-19 communication model developed in D7.4 “Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation” (see Figure 1 below).

Figure 1. Adaptation of the COVID-19 communication model suggested in D7.4 of COVINFORM project.

Each country section presented below addresses the common major changes analysed from each country report regarding the review and description of communication strategies and practices of governments, public health authorities, and organisations (see Table 1 below).

Table 1. Identification of structural changes in COVID-19 communication across all countries.

Major Relevant Topics	Model Fit
Means of communication	Means of communication & communication channels
Main contents	
Communication style	
Communicators	Communication structures & responsibilities
Vulnerability considerations	
Methods used	People communicating & receiving information
Misinformation targeting	Strategies
	Impacts
It is also important to note governmental movements and other world occurrences that may impact communication perception such as the war of Russia against Ukraine and the outbreak of Monkeypox.	

Each country section is organised by the following subtitles, according to the correspondence between topics suggested in Table 1:

- Communication structures & responsibilities
- Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style
- People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations
- Strategies: Methods used
- Misinformation targeting: Impacts.

2.1 Austria

2.1.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

Through our first desk research conducted in the months of January and February 2021, we could not find or access any information on a formal government communication strategy for the COVID-19 pandemic and its crisis management. Now, almost three years into the pandemic, there is still no formal communication strategy or plan publicly available.

The political communication during the COVID-19 pandemic in the time period under investigation is characterised by about-turns and does not follow straight lines (Dierken 2021). However, in a document published by the ministry of health in April 2022, “Die COVID-19 Pandemie – Bestandsaufnahme und Handlungsrahmen” (the COVID-19 Pandemic – Stocktaking and Framework for Action)” (BMSGPK 2022), a chapter on communication outlines basic principles and rules of risk and crisis communication. The chapter is directed at those persons within the authorities responsible for communication and (retrospectively) describes the planning, implementation, and analysis of communication measures between March 2020 and the beginning of 2022.

With Rauch, the COVID-19 management strategy changed: the government set out to adopt policies that prepared Austria to live with COVID-19. This was also reflected when the National Council voted against the COVID-19 mandatory vaccination which then got suspended in July 2022, only five months after it got installed in the first place (under the same government).

In addition, the report points out “key documents”, which include the following:

- Leitfaden Krisenkommunikation (crisis communication guide) by the German Ministry of Interior;
- Influenza-Pandemieplan Schweiz (influence pandemic plan Switzerland), 2018, by the Swiss federal health office;
- COVID-19-Bewältigung: Strategische Grundlagen von Bund und Kantonen, 2020, by the Swiss federal health office;
- Nationaler Pandemieplan, Teil I – Strukturen und Maßnahmen, 2017, by the Robert Koch Institut;
- Nationaler Pandemieplan, Teil II – Wissenschaftliche Grundlagen, 2016, by the Robert Koch Institut;
- WHO outbreak communication guidelines;
- Sechstes Zukunftsforum zum Thema Krisenkommunikation, 2004 by the WHO.

The constant change of personnel also influenced the press conferences which were no more a sign of governmental presence, continuity, and safety, which they used to symbolise in the first few weeks of the pandemic.

GECKO was created – Gesamtstaatliche Covid-Krisenkoordination (general covid crisis coordination). The aim of this newly formed task force, composed of experts, scientists, and professionals from advocacy groups and other organisations, was to assess the COVID-19 situation on an ongoing basis. GECKO should not only be able to provide advice, but also operationally support the government with the implementation of measures. Still, policy decisions would continue to be made by the federal government.

The Federal Ministry for Social Affairs, Health, Care and Consumer Protection (BMSGPK) supported the federal government's "Austria vaccinates" campaign in 2021 as part of the vaccination-related communication measures, as well as the subsequent campaign #GemeinsamGeimpft (vaccinated together), which followed in March 2022. In addition, BMSGPK maintains a close exchange with official contacts at the provincial and federal levels to ensure a continuous flow of information. A communication jour-fixe is held regularly with the provinces in order to enter into dialogue and provide information material.

The Austrian public health sector is quite complex, and it's a relatively new field in the country. For many years, the public health structure was not clearly defined, and the country was lacking specific public health plans and strategies (Ladurner et al., 2011). However, in the past years the importance of public health significantly increased, and the government acknowledges that public health must be considered on multiple levels, involving actors from different disciplines and sectors (BMSGPK 2021). The main actors in Austria's public health system include different federal ministries, health insurance funds, several specified health agencies as well as universities, research institutes, expert groups, or non-governmental organisations (Bachner et al. 2018).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, several of these public health actors played a significant role in the pandemic response, but only few of them were majorly involved in formal communication strategies. Even though those actors were not specifically following a communication strategy or plan, they were providing pandemic related content, launched campaigns, and communicated relevant information via different channels.

One of the main players in providing health data during the COVID-19 pandemic is the Agentur für Gesundheit und Ernährungssicherheit (Agency for Health and Food Safety, AGES) with many of the government's actions relying on it. It is also responsible for risk communication on behalf of the Federal Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, Long-Term Care and Consumer Protection (BMSGPK) and the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions, and Water Management (BML). Further, AGES runs a publicly available COVID-19 dashboard with various data to the current situation in all of Austria and additionally individually for each of the federal states as well as the main COVID-19 hotline, through which questions about the coronavirus (general information about transmission, symptoms, and prevention) are answered.

2.1.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The regularity as well as the actors and topics of the press conferences changed in the second pandemic year. There were (almost) no daily press conferences in the time period under research.

During the summer months, barely any press conferences took place. In the consecutive weeks and months, the vaccination became a 'hot topic' often covered in press conferences.

Besides the conferences on the pandemic and the latest measures, the government also held some press conferences on the present situation of the labour market, which has been severely affected by the pandemic. Mask-wearing and mandatory vaccination were the main topics discussed.

Websites and dashboards are still predominantly used to provide access to information, in particular about pandemic response measures.

In addition to the BMSGPK, several ministries continue to provide information on the coronavirus on their websites, regarding different sectors of activity (e.g., Federal Ministry for European and International Affairs; Federal Department of Finance, Federal Ministry of Labour and Economics, Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, Federal Ministry of Justice, Federal Ministry for Climate Protection, Environment, Energy, Mobility, Innovation and Technology, Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Regions and Water Management).

Throughout the pandemic, the Austrian federal government, as well as the ministry of health, launched campaigns with different aims, disseminating them via different channels such as TV, radio, and social media. The Austrian Red Cross played an important role in implementing and designing some of the campaigns in collaboration with the government.

With the availability of vaccines, the focus shifted to vaccination campaigns. In the abovementioned report, the ministry of health (BMSGPK, 2022) described its strategy for communication about the COVID-19 vaccines. The focus was put on education, information, and target group-oriented stakeholder communication. According to the BMSGPK, the strategy focused on the following principles: honesty, understandability, transparency, and speed. The goal is to increase confidence in the effectiveness and safety of vaccination and in the reliability of information through education and collaboration. Community leaders and public health representatives acted as 'confidence builders'. The focus was on multilingualism and low-threshold access. All vaccination-related communication activities were centred around the following core messages:

- COVID-19 vaccination works.
- The vaccines are safe and effective.
- The vaccine protects me and everyone close to me.
- The pandemic cannot be "sat out".

The #GemeinsamGeimpft campaign has a dedicated website and a YouTube channel. It is also linked to the newly found Coronavirus hotline run by AGES (see below) and works with short videos and infographics. Its main aim is to motivate people to get another booster shot and also inform people about the effectiveness of booster shots. Currently (September 2022), it also focuses on school students as they are about to return to school. The webpage also provides information about vaccination sites all over Austria.

The social media channels of the BMSGPK represent another important pillar in the communication around corona vaccination, as information can be shared promptly and directly, thus fostering a low-threshold exchange with the community. This ensures target group-oriented communication and promotes social listening. The mood in the community can be perceived and the content adapted accordingly. In addition to the various communication channels of the BMSGPK, diverse information

materials were developed, including folders and posters on various key topics (effectiveness, 3rd vaccination, childbearing, and pregnancy, etc.).

Each state installed its own hotline for questions about the care and support regulations. The following hotlines and information services are dedicated to specific topics, and operated by different governmental actors:

- Information telephone for questions regarding compulsory education, schooling, universities and examinations (Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research);
- Hotline for questions regarding travelling and travel restrictions (Federal Ministry for European and International Affairs);
- Hotline for questions regarding working in art and culture (Federal Ministry of Arts, Culture, Civil Service and Sport);
- Hotline for questions regarding sport (Federal Ministry of Arts, Culture, Civil Service and Sport);
- Hotline for questions regarding travelling and travel restrictions (Federal Ministry for European and International Affairs).

These hotlines were installed to inform citizens and answer specific questions and concerns, i.e., their purpose is to inform and advise the public. In addition to the abovementioned, there are hotlines dedicated to psychological health; care and support; children, teenagers, parents, and families; violence prevention, volunteering and voluntary activity; and work and occupation. These are handled by different actors, including the chamber of commerce, the chamber of labour, the Austrian Red Cross and various civil society organisations. According to the ministry of health (BMSGPK, 2022), the existence of these hotlines was continuously communicated to the population on social media channels and in press statements, especially on various occasions.

In addition to the abovementioned communication activities (BMSGPK 2022), the ministry of health reported distributing information via its accounts on Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube. Individual government members also communicated in their roles as chancellor, minister of health, minister of interior, etc. Recordings of press conferences were uploaded to the YouTube channels of the respective ministries and shared across social media platforms. Furthermore, the website of the BMSGPK is directly linked to results if a user searches the internet for anything COVID-19 related and is located in Austria.

In the report “Die COVID-19 Pandemie – Bestandsaufnahme und Handlungsrahmen” (the COVID-19 Pandemic – Stocktaking and Framework for Action)” (BMSGPK 2022), the ministry of health describes its strategy to communicate via social media, emphasising a dialogue-oriented use of the internet: through social media, authorities can create offers via existing contact opportunities and build positive relationships with the population. Information can be disseminated particularly quickly, easily and efficiently via social networks. Further emphasised is the importance of community management. Particularly at the beginning of the pandemic, enquiries skyrocketed and multiplied on all channels. Further, reliable information was not always available to dispel false reports and rumours. In such cases, the ministry of health’s internal crisis team was responsible: a specific wording was formulated and released internally, ensuring following the one-voice principle and answering questions from the public quickly. Wherever possible, the ministry tried to answer questions directly, with reference to the respective FAQs on their website. According to the report, hate messages, underhanded insults and calls for violence were moderated by deleting or hiding them. The report further identifies a great

need for action in this area in particular: guidelines for public authorities are needed that define how communication with citizens can be implemented in a digitalised world.

There are some examples of organisations belonging to the public sector that illustrate general trends we could identify: The public sector encompasses organisations such as the Arbeitsmarktservice (unemployment agency), Wirtschaftskammer Österreich (Austrian Economic Chamber of Trade), Arbeiterkammer (lobby for workers and employees), Werbung Österreich (the national tourism organisation) or the Österreichischer Integrationsfond (the Austrian Integration Fund). With the beginning of the pandemic all of these started to provide specific information in relation to their field of work and COVID-19. Due to the ongoing pandemic, it is still relevant to offer information (e.g., regulations for those looking for jobs and training for those who are unemployed during the pandemic, support and information to businesses, nationwide subsidies, etc.).

2.1.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

Although according to the BMSGPK, the #GemeinsamGeimpft campaign targets mainly those willing to vaccinate and those who are hesitant – as the goal is to not increase those who do refuse to get vaccinated –, the webpage and videos of the campaign are only available in German.

According to the attitude towards COVID-19 vaccination, the BMSGPK focuses on target-group-specific education of foreign-language communities as well as a direct approach by setting priorities, such as the preparation of information for children, parents, pregnant women, etc.

The BMSGPK collaborates with a variety of stakeholders, including the general crisis coordination GECKO, experts from different areas, the chamber of physicians (Ärztammer, who distribute folders and posters, as well as professional information and conversation guides to doctors), and the abovementioned community leaders (e.g., civil society organisations, among others organisations of disabled people, senior citizens associations, care and nursing facilities, family associations, associations for children and youth work, educators, cultural associations and associations for target groups with a migration background).

With the approval of the COVID-19 vaccination for children and adolescents, target group-specific measures were taken to reach the target group of parents and guardians as well as the children: on the one hand, cooperation with stakeholders from the health sector (doctors, nurses, pharmacists), who act as confidence builders, was promoted. On the other hand, there was cooperation with organisations specifically working with children and young people (youth work, recreation, education) as well as with organisations with a high degree of networking among parents (Chamber of Labour, parent platforms, etc.).

In January 2022, a big campaign named 'Du+Ich=Österreich' (You+Me=Austria) was launched by the Österreichische Gesundheitskasse (insurance provider for employees), the Austrian medical association, the Austrian Red Cross and the Austrian Broadcasting Corporation ORF. The aim of the campaign was to target the social tensions within the Austrian society, which emerged as a result from the pandemic. With the hashtag #lassunsreden (#letustalk) the campaign encourages people to revert to a constructive discussion, to accept differences and acknowledge similarities, and to enforce a feeling of cohesion. The campaign was launched via print media, TV spots, radio spots, on its own website and on different social media channels.

In May 2022, the Österreichische Gesundheitskasse launched another campaign, this time focusing on COVID-19 vaccines. With the hashtag #lassunsimpfen (#letusvaccinate), the campaign aims to achieve

a positive mindset and acceptance towards the vaccination. There is no specific target group, but a major goal is to reach sceptical and unvaccinated persons. With different means on various media channels, a wide range of the population should be targeted. Social media channels, the inclusion of celebrities as well as the production of an own song were conducted to reach out to different population groups. The campaign was broadcasted online, on radio, TV, and social media channels. On its own website, specific information related to the COVID-19 vaccine is provided.

The Österreichische Integrationsfonds (ÖIF) (Austrian Integration fund) is a fund of the Austrian government promoting integration. For people who do not yet speak sufficient German, ÖIF staff are available not only in person, but also by telephone to answer questions and provide information on various subjects such as the pandemic. Personal Corona consultations are offered in the languages Arabic, Dari/Farsi, Ukrainian, and Somali. The multilingual ÖIF info service also offers information on Corona security measures in 17 languages on their homepage. The page is currently under construction and will be updated continuously.

The Austrian Red Cross (one of the biggest non-profit-organisations) not only informs about prevention and how to deal with an infection but has also compiled some tips that make it easier to deal with all the unpleasant feelings caused by the pandemic on its website. It also offers easy to understand information on Corona vaccination and is still the key partner of the Austrian Government in COVID-19-related communication. While most of their information posters are available just in German (with few exceptions in English), the information flyer on the correct use of mouth-nose protection is translated in nine other languages.

Moreover, ORANGE 94.0, as an advertising-free, politically independent, and non-commercial radio station, has set up a broadcast focus on the topic of the Coronavirus. It is the largest community radio in the German-speaking world and conveys a wide range of information to people from a wide variety of backgrounds. They have collected informative broadcasts around the fight against COVID-19 and the current changes in our society. Their own current special broadcasts on the pandemic are available in Farsi, Arabic and Somali, in addition to German and English. Further, one can obtain specific information from the political, legal, and social areas. Here, the fight against the spread of COVID-19 and its social impact are presented from a critical perspective (e.g., animal transport in the Corona crisis, staying politically active under quarantine, Corona and the women who are also mothers).

2.1.4 Strategies: Methods used

With the introduction of the Corona Traffic Light (see D7.1), political decision-makers pursued the goal of transparent political crisis communication. For the minister of health at the time, Anschöber, the Corona Traffic Light was "a great step forward for transparency". It makes it possible to explain regional risk assessments with regard to the infection situation and the utilisation of healthcare capacities as well as the resulting measures in a comprehensible, understandable and transparent manner. However, the implementation of the "Corona traffic light" instrument has somewhat failed.

The BMSGPK builds on the results of the Austrian Corona Panel Project (ACPP) regarding the (lack of) trust in the government and the public broadcaster (Österreichischer Rundfunk, ORF) within the group of the hesitant and those unwilling to get vaccinated. The BMSGPK describes the use of methods such as social proof, community leaders (i.e., well-known persons or civil society organisations and representatives of the health care system), target-group-specific education, and personal approaches. The focus on social proof means activating the 'pro-vaccination' group and encouraging them to motivate the unvaccinated to vaccinate. Since people are guided by the behaviour of others, both the

general population and opinion leaders who enjoy the trust of the relevant target groups should actively inform and educate about the COVID-19 vaccination. Furthermore, representatives of the healthcare system such as doctors, caregivers, and pharmacists are trusted by the abovementioned groups and are thus used as ‘confidence builders’.

Regarding the communication measures, the BMSGPK established a multi-channel communication strategy. The central contact point for questions about the vaccination was the website of the BMSGPK. Attention was paid to the accessibility and multilingualism of the website, aiming to reach as many members of the population as possible.

In autumn 2022, the City of Vienna launched a new campaign to motivate citizens to register for the booster vaccination. The main message of the campaign is to inform about the risks of Long Covid in relation to the benefits of the booster vaccination. It further stresses the minimal amount of time needed to receive the vaccination, compared to the long-lasting impacts of Long Covid. The target group of the campaign are people willing to get vaccinated, rather than people who never received one dose and are unlikely to change their attitude towards the vaccine. The campaign includes three different outlines, will run between August 2022 and November 2022, and is published on TV, radio, social media, and posters in public spaces. Before developing the campaign, the City of Vienna conducted a survey, asking the Viennese population about their attitude towards the vaccination, their concerns as well as motivation to take a booster shot.

Werbung Österreich (ÖW) provides a covid-dashboard on its website. With the dashboard, ÖW has developed a monitoring tool that provides an up-to-date picture of developments in 31 countries and is intended to help identify trend reversals at an early stage in order to be able to react quickly to changes in demand.

2.1.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

In order to counteract misinformation and conspiracy theories, a fact check on the topic of myths was specially designed, taking a look at common false statements about the COVID-19 vaccination and refuting them in a scientifically sound manner.

2.2 Belgium

2.2.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

For Belgium, important developments of the pandemic and responses to it during the timeframe of this update – i.e., March 2021 to September 2022 – include the third to the seventh corona waves and the further roll-out of the vaccination campaign. This vaccination campaign began in January 2021 and was broadened from priority groups and the general adult population to young people (16-18 years old and 12-15 years old) in respectively June and July 2021, and children (5-11 years old) in January 2022. Later in 2022 vaccination campaigns focused on the first so-called “booster shot” (repeat vaccination) and more recently on the second so-called “autumn booster shot”. In May 2022, most official measures to limit the circulation of the virus were cancelled.

Belgium has a complex state structure that progressively changed from a unitary state to a federalized country with, next to the federal level, different territorial regions, and language communities, which each have specific jurisdiction and policy responsibilities. Within this context, it can be challenging to

communicate a unified message across administrative layers in crisis situations (Derison, 2020). In March 2020 it was therefore decided that Belgium would enter a ‘federal phase’, in which coordination and communication regarding the COVID-19 pandemic would occur at a federal level, carried out by the National Crisis Centre (NCCN) (CCVO, 2020). Communication at other administrative levels, such as the communication by the Coordination and Crisis Center of the Flemish government (CCVO), had to correspond with the federally determined messages (ibid.). When the communication regarded issues that fall under the federated entities’ responsibility, such as education and residential care for the elderly, the federated entities were free to specify how the federal measures applied within their local competences.

Between March 2021 and February 2022, the governmental organizations responsible for COVID-19 communication strategies, plans and actions remained relatively stable. After February 2022 two main changes occurred:

In March 2022, the so-called ‘federal phase’ that began in March 2020 came to an end due to “the favourable evolution in the epidemiological circumstances” (Nationaal Crisiscentrum, 2022). Since then, the coordination and communication regarding the COVID-19 pandemic no longer occurs at the federal level through its National Crisis Centre (NCCN) but has primarily become the responsibility of the regional authorities, governors of the various provinces, and local administrations. The national press conferences that were regularly organized by NCCN in cooperation with Sciensano (national public health institute) and FPS Public Health (federal public health ministry) to inform the general public about COVID-19 and the measures in place ceased to take place. The national COVID-19 website www.info-coronavirus.be as well as the general information number that can be called free of charge have remained in place. Sciensano also continues to provide regular epidemiological updates, which are publicly available on its website.

In April 2022, the Corona Commissioner’s Office also stopped its activities, as the corona crisis was considered “under control” (VRT NWS, 2022). The Corona Commissioner’s Office was created in October 2020 and was responsible for achieving better coordination between the federal and the various federated entities in terms of decision-making and communication regarding Belgium’s corona policy.

The Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, usually referred to as the FPS Health, is responsible for developing and implementing public health related policies in Belgium and operates under the primary responsibility of the federal Minister of Public Health. As a public service, part of the task of FPS Health is to inform the public. To be able to do this, during the COVID-19 crisis the FPS Health has been working together closely with the National Crisis Centre (NCCN) and much of the federal crisis communication relating to COVID-19 occurred through collaborative efforts between the two agencies. FPS Health did not develop any major new communication strategies or plans since March 2021.

Sciensano is a federal scientific institution that acts as the national public health institute. Epidemiologists from Sciensano are part of the Risk Assessment Group (RAG) which analyses the risks faced by the population based on epidemiological and scientific data, as part of the ‘medical cluster’ of Belgium’s crisis consultation structure. As such, Sciensano plays an important role in informing federal decisions regarding COVID-19. Sciensano’s main responsibilities during the COVID-19 crisis relate to data collection and epidemiological follow-up of the pandemic.

2.2.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

Since the ‘federal phase’ of the pandemic ended in March 2022, FPS Health continued to update the national COVID-19 website www.info-coronavirus.be with news items after each consultative committee, to highlight the official decisions regarding the pandemic. The final news update dates from May 2022, when most of the measures to limit circulation of the virus were cancelled. The website has also continued to serve as a platform to provide up-to-date information regarding e.g., the federal measures still in place; how and where to get tested for COVID-19; and why, how and where to get vaccinated against COVID-19. It furthermore provides links to the official websites with COVID-19 related information of the various federated entities (i.e., Flanders, Wallonia, Brussels Capital Region, and the German speaking community).

Since March 2021, epidemiological experts from Sciensano continued to be the voice of the press conferences that were regularly organized by the National Crisis Centre (NCCN) in cooperation with Sciensano and FPS Health. The final press conference took place in March 2022 before the ‘federal phase’ of the pandemic ended. Since then, Sciensano continues to follow-up on the pandemic and collect data and provides daily epidemiological updates and weekly reports that are freely accessible on its website. Furthermore, it continues to update the dynamic graphics of the epidemiological situation in Belgium twice a week; these graphics include data on, amongst others, rates of infection, hospitalization, mortality, and vaccination. Sciensano also continued to publish several thematic reports, which include a report on the surveillance of COVID-19 mortality in Belgium (September 2021), a report on the vaccination coverage and epidemiological impact of the COVID-19 vaccination campaign in Belgium (October 2021) and a report on SARS-COV-2 infections among children and young people between 0 and 12 years old in Belgium (September 2021).

2.2.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

For many organisations, communication is limited to providing links and directing their audience to official websites with relevant COVID-19 related information. Other organisations have been more actively involved, e.g., by giving advice on how to reach specific groups of people or by contributing to the development of tailor-made communication material. Rather than giving a comprehensive overview of these organisations, below we highlight some examples of communication activities. These are developed since March 2021 by a selection of organisations concerned with inclusive communication and reaching and informing vulnerable groups:

The Combat Poverty, Insecurity and Social Exclusion Service is an inter-federal public organisation established by the federal and regional governments as an instrument in the fight against poverty, insecurity, and social exclusion. It has been actively involved in the pandemic by, for instance, giving expert input in the Task Force Vulnerable Groups and the Task Force Communication, publishing various recommendations and advice documents, and developing a Communication COVID-19 vaccination webpage that aims to provide relevant information and communication material in the context of the corona vaccination campaign to reach and inform people who live in poverty and insecurity. Without claiming to be comprehensive in the information and links it provides, the webpage targets three specific groups across Belgium’s different regions: i) healthcare professionals and people who are responsible for vaccination, ii) social workers, and iii) people from precarious groups and the general public. While the organisation was mainly active during the initial phases of the pandemic, since March 2021 they continued to publish an overview of COVID-19 support measures from the various governments for people in situations of poverty and insecurity (most recent one dates from

July 2021) and developed an inter-federal note on the impact of the COVID-19 crisis in situations of poverty and insecurity (April 2021). The organisation also continued to upload relevant links on the Communication COVID-19 webpage, including links to various presentations on vaccination campaigns to reach vulnerable groups with relevant information for healthcare professionals and people who are responsible for vaccination, and for social workers, as well as links to a wide range of websites with relevant information for people from precarious groups and the general public.

The Flemish organisation for clear language '*Wabliefert*' has continued to develop, collect and upload information in straightforward language about COVID-19 related issues (measures, vaccination, travelling, quarantine and isolation, contact tracing, etc.).

Various Flemish non-profit umbrella organisations that represent Flemish general health practitioners (Domus Medica), pharmacists (VAN), general hospitals, mental health care initiatives and social profit facilities (Zorgnet-Icuro), and social entrepreneurs (SOM vzw) published a document called "Inspiration note: looking for a adapted vaccination strategy for the most vulnerable people" (Domus Medica et al., 2021). The document is intended to help professionals in directing "the most vulnerable and hardest-to-reach groups towards vaccination" (ibid: 1) and distinguishes two groups of vulnerable people: i) people who are willing to get vaccinated but who cannot go to a vaccination centre due to mobility issues, and ii) people who are not being reached by government-led or government-initiated initiatives. Especially the second group is considered difficult to reach and the document highlights that this group can only be reached through so-called "outreaching care", i.e., "actively reaching out to them and gradually building rapport with them without forcing it" (ibid.: 2).

The association of Flemish cities and municipalities (VVSG), a non-profit organisation that represents the interests of all Flemish cities and municipalities and offers advice and training to local authorities, developed a leaflet for local governments with 10 tips for inclusive COVID-19-vaccination communication (VVSG, 2021). These tips include: spreading information in multiple languages – emphasizing that this is in accordance with Flanders' language legislation (which is rather strict when it comes to using other languages than Dutch in official communication); using accessible and visual information material; cooperating with local influencers; using communication channels that are used by the specific target group, and recruiting diverse and multilingual volunteers for the vaccination centres.

Foyer, a *Brussels-based non-profit organisation* that focuses – among other things – on intercultural mediation and empowerment, developed a webpage called "back to normal: a multilingual vaccination campaign" with video material available in 19 languages (Foyer, March, 2021). With this webpage, the organisation aims to reach as many people as possible in their mother tongue with "a hopeful message about the vaccination campaign" (ibid). The webpage also links to a second video with practical information about vaccination in Brussels, which is also available in 17 languages and can be consulted here.

As a final example, the *Flemish organisation Health and Science (Gezondheid en Wetenschap)* is an organisation that focuses less on reaching vulnerable groups but more on critically assessing news media coverage regarding corona. Health and Science aims to provide patients and other citizens with trustworthy health-related information through a web-platform. The web-platform has a specific section that is dedicated to COVID-19 where it bundles all kinds of science-based, easy to reach information about the coronavirus and corona vaccines, written by independent doctors and other experts and regularly updated. It also has a Fact-check vaccination section, where - together with the

Centre for the Evaluation of Vaccines of the University of Antwerp - Health and Science critically assesses news coverage on (social) media about vaccines. Finally, there is also a broader Health in the Media section, where Health and Science critically assesses popular health-related news coverage by providing more background information to specific news items in order to bring more nuance to the message. To be able to do this, Health and Science cooperates with independent doctors and experts of the Belgian Centre for Evidence-Based Medicine (Cebam). Since March 2021 about 85 news items about corona have been assessed, including more than 35 fact checks of news coverage about corona vaccines.

2.2.4 Strategies: Methods used

As far as new communication strategies, plans, and practices are concerned, it is important to mention the coronavirus barometer as a tool for proactive policy preparation and communication. This coronavirus barometer was approved by the Consultative Committee (an official consultative body that includes representatives of Belgium's various governments) in January 2022. With this barometer, which uses colour codes to distinguish three phases that are intended to reflect the pressure on the healthcare sector, the authorities aimed to provide more predictability and transparency regarding the COVID-19 measures linked to each phase. The barometer focuses specifically on public events, the hospitality sector and leisure activities, while other sectors (e.g., education) are not covered by it. Given the positive evolution of the pandemic, the Consultative Committee decided to deactivate the coronavirus barometer on May 23rd, 2022, when most of the measures to decrease the circulation of the virus were scrapped. Since then, it has not been reactivated again.

The vaccination strategy identifies specific target groups who need tailor-made communication, including patients at risk, the elderly, young people and children, blind and deaf people, as well as non-native Dutch/French/German speakers and people who are low literate (Government Commissariat COVID-19, 2022: 28.). While the vaccination strategy applies to the whole country and describes procedures for e.g., priority groups for vaccination, the vaccination of young people (12-18 years old) and children (5-11 years old) and booster shots, the regional governments - i.e., Flanders, Wallonia, Brussels Capital Region and the German speaking community - are responsible for the roll-out and practical organisation of the vaccination as well as for the communication about it. Consequently, most of the communication campaigns happen at the regional level.

Since March 2021, a wide variety of information and campaigning material has been developed separately by the different regions and can be accessed on the official websites of the various regions: www.laatjevaccineren.be (Flanders), www.jemevaccine.be (Wallonia), <https://coronavirus.brussels> (Brussels Capital Region) and <https://ostbelgiencorona.be> (German speaking community). Campaigns focused on e.g., the vaccination of young people and children, and, more recently, on the so-called 'autumn booster' for the general adult population. Which groups are considered important to be targeted with tailor-made communication material is for the regional authorities to decide. For instance, while all regions developed information material in various languages (including sign language), in Flanders, people who are low literate or who speak another language than Dutch are specifically mentioned as a target group that need tailor-made communication material (Flemish Government, n.d.). An example of a tool to reach non-Dutch speaking people is the 'crisis information translated' app launched by the Flemish government in March 2021. The app aims to provide key government information on corona in real time in 18 languages by providing an up-to-date overview

of official COVID-19 measures and up to date information on the vaccination strategy (Agentschap Inburgering en Integratie, 2021).

2.2.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

n/a

2.3 Cyprus

2.3.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

Regarding Cyprus, there is a scarcity of available data on the communication strategy and the relevant vaccination campaign, due to the small size and population of the country. It is observed that the Central Government was responsible for informing the public on the epidemiological situation in the country with systematic and regular briefings about all relevant issues regarding the pandemic management decisions of competent authorities. The Ministry of Health (Υπουργείο Υγείας) in close cooperation with the Ministry of Interiors (Υπουργείο Εσωτερικών) have been given the authorization to draft and manage the communication strategy from the beginning and throughout the pandemic. These two aforementioned governmental bodies were, and still are, the firmest engaged governmental bodies with the responsibility to inform the public about any governmental decision concerning the pandemic including the publication of governmental gazettes which entailed all implemented protective measures and special guidelines against COVID 19.

A Scientific Committee of experts, which was created ad hoc from the beginning of the pandemic in order to monitor the epidemiological situation in the country, was responsible for advising the government on all vaccination related issues like population prioritization or vaccines safety. Since the communication campaign in Cyprus was centrally managed, the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Interiors, were the two governmental actors mainly responsible for the systematic media briefings that took place in order to inform the public about the progress of the vaccination program.

2.3.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The media briefings mentioned above entailed detailed information regarding the vaccination uptake percentages, the population groups eligible for vaccination according to the different phases of the vaccination program, any changes regarding the available venues and health infrastructures for vaccination or any variation or extension to their operating hours or even any updates to the appointment procedure. Also, a series of different informational videos and TV spots regarding the significance of vaccination were also posted on social media, mainly Youtube.

Overall messages disseminated also contained official advice regarding personal preventive measures against COVID-19, such as hand hygiene, use of face masks and social distancing while relevant informational leaflets and posters translated into many other languages such as French, Arabic, Georgian, Filipino, etc. were placed in health care facilities, schools, airports and ports (Gabriel, Theodorou & Kantaris 2020). Dedicated guidelines, protocols, frequently asked questions and answers and updates regarding the evolvement of the pandemic (e.g. number of confirmed COVID 19 cases, hospitalization rates and death rates) but also any other relevant information stemming from International Health Authorities like European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), European Medicines Agency (EMA) and World Health Organization (WHO) were conveyed to the

public through multiple press conferences, public statements, general information distribution, Ministerial speeches as well as social media posts published on the official governmental websites.

In this process, mainly the Ministry of Health official website is utilized, as well as a Press and Information Office website (Γραφείο Τύπου και Πληροφοριών) about the COVID-19 pandemic. The significance of the two websites, can be understood by the fact that the entire activity of the Ministry of Health is catalogued there. The Press and Information Office website is by far more detailed, with multimedia content and has the following sections:

- Important Announcements (Σημαντική Ενημέρωση) where all the announcements, covering all subjects since the 13th of March 2020 are available for download through pdf files.
- Decrees (Διατάγματα), where all the Laws passed by Ministry of Health and Ministry of Transport relevant with the new pandemic, are available for download through pdf files.
- Information Guidelines (Πληροφορίες/Οδηγίες), which is divided in seven subsections - Guidelines for workplaces, Infographics, Epidemiological Surveillance, Guidelines for the public, Information for Health Professionals, Guidelines for persons in isolation, Information Flyers - are available for download through pdf files
- Press Releases (Δελτία Τύπου), covering all subjects, since the 10th of March 2020, in various languages, are available for download through pdf files.
- European COVID Certificates' Portal (Πύλη Ευρωπαϊκών Πιστοποιητικών COVID), where there are thorough instructions on the steps required to access the EU Digital COVID Certificate, appearing in Greek and in optional English, along with Useful links, CovPassAPP and CovScan APP sections, on the right side of the new screen, that give beneficial additional tips
- Testing Units (Σημεία Δειγματοληψίας), where there announcements, about the specific districts, locations, operating hours and contact numbers of the free of charge mobile rapid antigen testing units throughout the island, for all groups of citizens, regardless of their vaccination history
- COVID-19 Vaccines and Treatment Protocols (Εμβολιασμοί και Θεραπευτικά Πρωτόκολλα κατά της COVID-19), where the entire anti-COVID strategy of the country and its differentiation since the 15th of December of 2020 is posted
- Information For All Stakeholders Concerning Flights From/to The Republic of Cyprus (Πληροφοριακό για τις Αεροπορικές Εταιρείες και τους Επιβάτες που Ταξιδεύουν στην Κ.Δ.), presented in English, French, German and Russian.

The website also has a video window, where there are five audio-visual instructions on several COVID-19 related issues (e.g., how to use a Rapid test, how to get a European digital certification for free and safe travel within the EU), and those video instructions, appeared in various television channels of Cyprus, being simultaneously available in the Covid19 Cyprus YouTube Channel, registered by the Cypriot government.

Several Ministries also made accessible hotlines for advice and information on a 24-hour basis (e.g., symptoms, legal requirements, emergency measures). The hotlines were communicated to the public, by the Press and Information Office website, along with tv and radio advertisements.

Finally, on behalf of the central government the official *Covid19 Cyprus* YouTube Channel, registered on the 14th of April 2020, aired seventeen videos, that offered guidance, information, statements by the President of the Republic of Cyprus Mr. Nikos Anastasiadis (Νίκος Αναστασιάδης), etc.

A distinct example of the effort made by independent institutions to raise awareness regarding the importance of vaccination to the fight against COVID 19, was the communication campaign funded and released by The Cyprus Electricity Authority (CEA / Αρχή Ηλεκτρισμού Κύπρου) with the central message “In this battle you are needed too: Learn. Judge. Act.”. The Cyprus Electricity Authority, wanting to actively contribute to the fight against the coronavirus, has launched this multi-level communication campaign in collaboration with the Ministry of Health, with the aim to highlight the benefits of vaccination and provide answers to concerns and reflections regarding this specific issue among other things, through the promotion of the available scientific data and arguments (Kathimerini, 2021).

2.3.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

As the pandemic waves unfolded from the last quarter of 2021 and all through 2022 and as the restrictive measures were eased aiming to establish a safe return to normality, all communication efforts have been concentrating on promoting the administration of the booster doses for individuals aged 18 years old and over and enhancing further vaccination uptake at minors aged 12-17 years old and children. In this context various communication and informational programmes were initiated in order to bend the observed vaccination hesitancy at these age groups. The information campaign on the vaccination of children disseminated by The Pediatric Society of Cyprus (Παιδιατρική Εταιρεία Κύπρου / ΠΕΚ / ΠΕΚ) had exactly that objective, meaning to provide scientific information to parents and guardians about the safety of the available vaccines and underline the necessity of immediate vaccination of children over 12 years old against COVID-19 (Pediatric Society of Cyprus, 2021). The campaign included video spots broadcasted to social media, mainly YouTube, and the distribution of informational material such as posters and leaflets. The main concern of ΠΕΚ has been not only the promotion of reliable scientific data and the elimination of misinformation on the issue but above all the protection of children themselves accomplishing the widest possible vaccination coverage for the Cypriot population as a whole.

A distinct example of the effort made by independent institutions to raise awareness regarding the importance of vaccination to the fight against COVID 19, was the communication campaign funded and released by The Cyprus Electricity Authority (CEA / Αρχή Ηλεκτρισμού Κύπρου) with the central message “In this battle you are needed too: Learn. Judge. Act.”, aiming primarily young people, children and pregnant women. The campaign entailed a series of different informational videos regarding the significance of vaccination and a dedicated website with among others useful information on vaccines safety and probable side-effects, information on issues regarding the psychological impact of the pandemic, pregnancy and fertility but also frequently asked questions (<https://mathe-krine-praxe.com>).

2.3.4 Strategies: Methods used

From the first quarter of 2021 and all through the summer of 2021, the vaccination plan continued to be focused on young people, even though Cyprus had achieved to rank 4th among the European Union countries in terms of COVID-19 vaccinations per 100.000 (65,35 doses per 100 inhabitants) as of early May 2021 (Ministry of Interiors, 2021). In this context and in an attempt to deal with the relative high infection rates that were observed to people under the age of 40 during the summer of 2021, an extensive programme of vaccination incentives provided by specific private companies and organisations under the title “Be Safe” was announced. The programme aimed to increase the vaccination coverage among young people mainly up to 30 years old and contribute to reinforcing

further the immunity against COVID 19 in the community (Commissioner for the Citizen, 2021). This initiative that was developed within the framework of the private sector social corporate responsibility included a package of different offers by 13 companies and organisations such as discount coupons, gift cards, vouchers, theatre or football tickets, discounted stay to local hotels, plane tickets etc where young people aged between 18 and 30 were eligible to obtain them if they would get vaccinated.

Thus, a dedicated website was created (www.besafe.gov.cy) and a respective campaign was disseminated providing information vis-à-vis the incentives offered, in order to inform and facilitate those interested. The list of the incentives also posted on the Press and Information Office's official coronavirus website, was valid until end of August 2021 since it was not widely accepted by the young people as it was more or less associated with an attempt of the government to bribe them and as an extortion of their individual free will (Pitta, 2021).

The Cyprus Electricity Authority, wanting to actively contribute to the fight against the coronavirus, has launched a multi-level communication campaign in collaboration with the Ministry of Health, with the aim to highlight the benefits of vaccination and provide answers to concerns and reflections regarding this specific issue among other things, through the promotion of available scientific data and arguments (Kathimerini, 2021).

Another example consists of the vaccination Awareness Campaign launched by the University of Nicosia titled "Every Shot Matters". In the context of the campaign, a series of witty and humorous taglines and posters were deployed in social media, encouraging the students community to take a fresh approach in assessing the possibility of getting vaccinated and contribute this way to the collective effort to tackle the pandemic (University of Nicosia, 2021). The relevant posts also provided useful information to EU students living in Cyprus about the relevant standing appointment and the vaccination procedure.

2.3.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

A lot of effort and emphasis was given in reducing public concern and misinformation about the safety and efficiency of specific available COVID 19 vaccines (e.g., The AstraZeneca vaccine) through systematic public announcements, press briefings, release of frequently asked question and answers, dedicated video spots broadcasted on social media etc, disseminating further the official argumentation provided by the scientific community on the subject.

2.4 England

2.4.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

Moving forward to the years 2021 and 2022, the UK government released a new communication plan titled 'UK Government Communication Plan 2021/2022, Build Back Better'. Covering a range of different priorities to be communicated to citizens during both years, COVID-19 priorities have focused on helping "drive the pace and scale of our recovery by articulating how we intend to recover from the COVID-19 pandemic and build back better."

When preparing this plan, colleagues across the Government Communication Service have contributed towards the collaborative effort. Either contributing towards the plan's content or design. Note that most of the contributors' work is within the Cabinet Office, a governmental department responsible

for supporting the UK Prime Minister and Cabinet. It comprises a variety of units that assist Cabinet committees and which manage the provision of government objectives through other departments.

Some of the new communication priorities touching on COVID-19 include:

- Beat COVID-19 and Back the NHS – motivating people to take better care of their health, alter the way they access NHS services and strengthening trust and confidence in the health system
- Build Back Better – supporting economic recovery, heightening job opportunities and levelling up across all four corners of the UK
- Build Back Stronger – capitalising on post-Brexit opportunities, solidifying the Union, and addressing a coherent message to international partners about what Global Britain represents.

The afore-mentioned priorities which touch on COVID-19 communications are outlined below in further detail.

- *Beat COVID-19 and Backing the NHS:* After it was reported that COVID-19 communications were estimated to have saved between 22,629 and 27,658 lives and averted between 1.5 and 1.8 million infections between April and December 2020, the priority in 2021 and 2022 focused on continuing to accelerate alterations in public behaviours to help combat COVID-19, safeguard the NHS and protect lives.
- *Build Back Better:* In 2021, it was announced that as the country emerged from the pandemic, the UK government would carry on supporting the economy and boosting recovery (ibid). In 2020, the government spent £280 billion on an extraordinary package of economic support to safeguard people’s jobs and livelihoods, while also helping businesses and public services across the UK.

Published on 23 March 2021 and last updated on 14 July 2022, the National Institute for Health and Care produced a guideline titled ‘COVID-19 rapid guideline: managing COVID-19’. Outlining the management of COVID-19 in all care settings, the guideline brings together “existing recommendations on managing COVID-19, and new recommendations on therapeutics, so that healthcare staff and those planning and delivering services can find and use them more easily” (ibid).

With a focus on COVID-19 treatments, a number of recommendations were communicated and integrated into the NICE guideline in 2022. The new recommendations included using remdesivir (a medicine that fights viruses) in hospital and using vitamin D for treating COVID-19 (ibid).

In 2021/22, Public Health England prioritised communications relating to COVID-19 vaccinations. To be specific, NHS England, NHS Improvement (NHSE&I), and the Pharmaceutical Services Negotiating Committee (PSNC) agreed that contractors will be approached to take part in a COVID-19 vaccination campaign as the first mandated health campaign for 2021/22 (ibid). Contractors were expected to take up this new campaign, especially since it constituted a key part of their NHS contractual obligations (ibid).

With a focus on COVID-19 communications, a number of recommendations were made by the committee for the UK government to consider. The recommendations include the following: *Public Health Annual Report: Recommendation 5:* “Arrangements should be established and tested to allow immediate flows of data between bodies relevant to an emergency response with a mechanism to resolve immediately and decisively any disputes” (ibid).

Following government acceptance of this recommendation, the newly established National Security Council (NSC) within the Cabinet Office enforced the lessons it learnt from the COVID-19 pandemic

and advanced the government’s modernisation of the use of information (ibid). The NSC applied data and insights from across government and beyond to aid circumstantial awareness and response on national security, crises, and civil emergency problems (ibid).

At the time of reporting, the government were focusing on the development of a Resilience Strategy, whereby particular attention would be given to evaluating the way that it evaluates risk (ibid). The following themes were prioritised for the strategy:

- The nature of the information it collates and examines
- The means for communicating and distributing that data
- The way in which recipients alter and implement data to regulate risks (ibid)

2.4.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The campaign fell under the 2021 ‘Join the Millions’ national advertising campaign, which saw particular materials being produced for both community pharmacies and general practices. In order to inform the public about the COVID-19 vaccine and encourage people to get vaccinated when it was offered, the following communication packs were considered:

- A pharmacy team briefing sheet outlining what the materials are and how to make use of them;
- An information leaflet for use with patients, responding to frequently asked questions;
- Posters; and
- A window sticker

With a key focus on the education sector and universities in particular, the importance of communicating effectively with students and local communities was recognised for the years 2021/22. Although the checklist created took into consideration the lifting of COVID-19 restrictions, it was acknowledged that the public health situation in the UK would remain incalculable. At the time of reporting, University communications played an important role in ensuring the following priorities:

- Students comprehending what the university experience will look like in 2021-22 (especially in different public health circumstances)
- Students being aware of the different forms of support available to them before returning to campus. Students would also be aware of how to access specific support
- Students being aware of the behaviour that is required of them to enable accountable and well-mannered behaviour
- Motivating students to get the COVID-19 vaccine, and how to obtain a COVID-19 vaccine
- Students are provided with coherent advice on any ongoing asymptomatic testing they must perform
- Local communities being reassured about students going back to campus.
- Proposing a timetable for “the release of results and the “decoupling” of results from the UCAS process.” Note that UCAS stands for the Universities and Colleges Admissions Service, whose primary role is to administer the application procedure for British universities
- The effect of arrangements on deprived and marginalised groups

As stated in the checklist, the guidelines could be utilised by universities to help spot actions prior to the new academic year. Moreover, the guidelines can be modified to individual settings and circumstances. That said, it can also be used in conjunction with a range of different university approaches.

Touching on changes to COVID-19 communications within the transport sector, Transport for London (TfL) considered vigorous evidence regarding the demonstrated effectiveness of face coverings as well as results of independent testing by Imperial College London for coronavirus on the public transport network since September 2020, as well as feedback from stakeholders (ibid). At the same time, TfL continued to encourage travellers to wear face coverings to slow down transmission of the COVID-19 virus and help keep people safe as possible. In a press release authored by The British Medical Journal, the following statement was brought to light: “Face masks will no longer be mandatory on public transport or in shops, and this requirement has been dropped immediately for secondary school pupils in classrooms. However, people are still advised to wear face coverings in closed or crowded spaces, particularly if encountering people they do not normally meet.

Alongside public health, business support, and licensing, planning and enforcement, the communications focus highlighted the “need for a clear communications plan which builds public, consumer and business confidence, with a single London-wide message informed by engagement with business. Crucial to this is adequate notice from national government of changes to restrictions, recognising these may need to be reimposed as infection rates change.

2.4.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

To support the economy and boost recovery amid the COVID-19 pandemic, the COVID-19 Business Support campaign was introduced. What is known is that the support provided reached 94% of all small and medium-sized enterprises (ibid). The Coronavirus Job Retention Scheme also provided support with 10 million jobs. In addition, more than 1.4 million people visited the Jobhelp advice website and, following the opening of applications in November, the Kickstart campaign led to more than 700 firms providing job placements to 120,000 young people vulnerable to long-term employment (ibid).

In 2021, communication efforts continued supporting the government’s dedication to businesses and the employment of citizens across the country (ibid). At the heart of this commitment is the Plan for Jobs campaign, which reached more than 26 million people (resulting in approximately 185 million impressions) in the first two months at the start of 2021 (ibid). The campaign specifically helps all sectors and regions to help, safeguard, and form jobs – whether that may be through encouraging T Levels to develop skills, recruiting for the Armed Forces to gain Universal Credit (ibid). In the UK, T Levels are an alternative to A Levels, which are subject-based qualifications that can result in enrolment at universities, further study, training, or employment.

In 2021, a number of public health reports focusing on new communication strategies were also released, for instance: *‘Public Health Annual Report 2021: Rising to the Challenges of COVID-19’*. With a focus on COVID-19 communications, the report states the following: “In October, when more was known about tackling the virus, ADPH published Protecting our communities’ guidance on ‘combination prevention’ setting out a menu of evidence-based measures, ranging from infection control to communication and engagement, which could be used in combination and adapted for the needs of local areas.

When accepting the recommendation, the government announced that the development of the Resilience Strategy would help improve the communication and sharing of data during emergencies (ibid). With a focus on communications targeted at specific groups, recommendation 31 of the report suggested the following: Public Health Annual Report: Recommendation 31:

“In planning for future health emergencies, the Department of Health and Social Care and the NHS should consider the specific difficulties faced by people with learning disabilities and their families and recognise the barriers to understanding and communication which, if not overcome, can lead to avoidable deaths of vulnerable people” (ibid). Once again, the government accepted the recommendation and realised the significance of considering the precise needs of people with a learning disability, autistic people and their families in health emergencies (ibid).

Besides practical assistance, the government recognised the significance of endorsing effective communication with people with learning disabilities and autism (ibid). Also realising the importance of public information on COVID-19 being accessible to everyone, the government expressed their dedication to solidifying important COVID-19-related communications in a way that is reachable and inclusive (ibid). Progression in this area had to involve critical health communications, such as COVID-19 symptoms, and Stay Alert and NHS Test and Trace content, all of which would be accessible in different layouts, including easy read (the presentation of text in an accessible, easy to comprehend format), British sign language, and audio (ibid). To date, the government has accepted a number of different partnerships, including with disability organisations, that have assisted with the dissemination of critical messages and advice (ibid). The Department of Health and Social Care in particular worked in collaboration with the Cabinet Office Disability Unit, who took into account cross-government advice on generating different layouts (ibid).

A co-production group within NHS England also worked to assemble easy-to-read and attainable COVID-19 data for people with learning disabilities and autism. This data produced has comprised of:

- Easy-to-read vaccination invite letters
- Accessible information sheets
- Guidance and films on (a) the COVID-19 virus, (b) the risks, (c) staying safe guidance, and (d) the importance of getting the COVID-19 vaccine

Within the charity sector, organisations began to express their concern about how to communicate constructively with those digitally excluded or who find it difficult to obtain online tools that “have become the norm during the pandemic.”. In order to address these issues, organisations acted on the following considerations:

- Advancing organisation understanding of communication preferences of the people they work with
- Ensuring that a variety of methods are used to stay in touch and offer support to certain groups. Organisations spoke of forming telephone groups, online groups and WhatsApp groups
- Customizing communication to the needs of people. This would include utilising resources that have been explicitly advanced to assist minority groups impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, some organisations expressed interest in returning to offline procedures of communicating, such as face-to-face interactions and paper formatting.
- Considering the time of the day when communications are broadcasted. It was recognised that sending out communications at different times may heighten readership.

In October 2020, the ‘Community Champions’ scheme was introduced across the UK to assist groups most at risk of COVID-19. This would include ethnic minority groups and communities that have been disproportionately impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. In Birmingham and during the period of 2021/22 in particular, it was realised that communication and engagement from the community would

play a key role in addressing the inequalities that the COVID-19 pandemic has generated and even gone to exacerbate. The inequalities include poverty and obesity.

2.4.4 Strategies: Methods used

The NHS Confederation, previously known as the National Association of Health Authorities and Trusts, is a membership body for organisations that commission and supply NHS services. In a January 2021 blog post titled ‘Communications as a key weapon in tackling COVID-19 falsehoods,’ the NHS Confederation began their work in tackling COVID-19 misinformation, which they saw as “damaging NHS morale and endangering public health.”.

To tackle COVID-19 misinformation, the confederation formed the #CovidEmergency campaign. The campaign focused on “tackling sceptics head-on and standing in support of our members,” and stressed the following truths:

- The COVID-19 pandemic is real
- The added pressure on the NHS is real and soaring
- This is different to any ‘normal’ winter pressures the NHS has ever faced
- Bed occupancy is a deceptive measure
- The NHS is being held back by reduced capacity
- The NHS is not ‘wasting’ extra capacity in the Nightingale hospitals

Every week, the confederation would produce infographics, Twitter cards and other content that supplies facts and figures on the seriousness of the COVID-19 emergency. Upon completion, the content would be shared with communications teams in NHS organisations across the country.

At present, the Mutual Aid Groups (MAGs) are informal (ibid). Generally speaking, they have little safeguarding policies, which are intended to help safeguard the groups’ members themselves and the people they are assisting (ibid). Formalisation of these components, safeguarding, and systems to administer fundings, are often a crucial requirement for the longer term (ibid). Local authorities and larger charities can assist mutual aid groups with this procedure, whilst also considering ways to avoid undermining the way mutual aid groups work. It has been reported that some groups are opposed to “becoming more formalised,” as it removes the “neighbour to neighbour” approach which enables the groups to respond swiftly and casually to local issues (ibid). To date, COVID-19 MAGs are still in operation and resources and links can be accessed in the same way, as stated in the D7.1 baseline report.

In August 2021, it was announced that the UK would transition into the final step of the government’s roadmap for controlling the COVID-19 virus. The changes of the roadmap stressed that as of 16 August 2021, “anyone identified as a close contact of a positive case will no longer have been fully vaccinated and are not displaying any COVID-19 symptoms” (ibid). The pack designed for community leaders, groups and charities contained the following information:

- As a community leader, group or organisation, it has been advised to share the advice within the information pack with members of the community, to help hinder the transmission of the COVID-19 virus
- Distributing the information back to local community members so that they can follow the advice and data provided in the pack
- Community leaders, groups, or organisations being given useful resources to encourage testing and vaccination straight from the local authority. The resources made available

included the Public Health COVID-19 resource centre (phe.gov.uk), including resources to advertise frequent testing and COVID-19 vaccination uptake. The information could be disseminated through the community network and through communication channels such as email, social media, and websites (ibid).

2.4.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

In terms of whether there were any predicted actions or actions taken for targeting and/or dealing with misinformation, disinformation or malinformation regarding the strategies, plans, and practices, the NHS confederation's work in 2021 mentioned above is noteworthy.

Moreover, both in 2021 and 2022, the following efforts are relevant:

Cross-departmental counter-disinformation unit:

On 9 March 2020, a press release announced that the UK government established a cross-departmental counter-disinformation unit to combat lies, conspiracy theories and cyber security threats associated with the COVID-19 virus. To be specific, the unit is run by the Department for Digital, Culture, Media, and Sport (DCMS), and the unit united teams from across Whitehall (a road and area in the City of Westminster, Central London) to construct a comprehensive picture on the extent, scope and impact of disinformation relating to the virus. At the time of reporting, DCMS explained that officials were working closely with strategic communication experts to ensure that the government is fully prepared to respond, and that it is collaborating with social media companies to keep track of interference and reduce the spread of misinformation (ibid).

In a July 2022 policy paper titled 'Government response to the COVID-19 Committee's Living in a COVID world: A long-term approach to resilience and wellbeing report,' it was announced that the DCMS-led Counter Disinformation Unit would continue its work taking the lead in information-sharing systems and partnerships across sectors by collaborating with important stakeholders on the topic of misinformation and disinformation. It was also reported that DCMS frequently met with platforms, researchers, and media and civil society organisations to comprehend developing issues, share lessons learned, and advise on future approaches.

Government social media campaigns:

Published on 11 March 2021, a government press release announced the formation of a new social media campaign to combat false vaccine information. Supported by the world's largest social media companies, the campaign was specifically aimed at ethnic minority communities (ibid).

The Department for Digital, Culture, Media, and Sport (DCMS) developed a toolkit with content created to be shared via WhatsApp and Facebook community groups, as well as Twitter, YouTube and Instagram, to combat false information spread via private channels (ibid). The creation of the toolkit came after the Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE) expressed worries around low vaccine uptake amongst ethnic minority communities. In addition, worries were also based on an Ofcom study which highlighted that people originating from a minority ethnic background were twice as likely as white respondents to rely on people they know, people in their local area, or social media contacts for COVID-19-related data (ibid).

As stated in the press release, this was the first government campaign created for private instant messaging services where there were worries that inaccurate data about COVID-19 is spreading – and that not enough was being done to combat its spread, especially where it would have affected vaccine

uptake (ibid). At the time of reporting, the Minister for Digital and Culture Caroline Dinenage said: “We want to harness the power of social media to tackle false information and encourage take up of life-saving vaccines among ethnic minorities. Our new toolkit and campaign will help people access reliable and factual information on vaccines and builds on the good work platforms are already doing to promote trusted quality information” (ibid).

Worth noting is that the new toolkit is based on the fundamental principles of the government’s SHARE checklist, which motivates people to identify the origins of the data before they share it, to think seriously about the information and whether they originate from an expert to make sure what they’re sharing is correct (ibid). The toolkit, otherwise known as ‘Check before you share,’ can be found here.

GoViral! Game:

Introduced in 2021, GCS International (a leading Fintech based in the Dominican Republic) in collaboration with the University of Cambridge (England, UK) built a game called GoViral! Designed during the COVID-19 pandemic, the game lasting for approximately five to seven minutes, introduced players to the basics of online manipulation, acting as a basic guide to common techniques. For example, the game uses “emotionally charged language to stoke shock and alarm, fake experts to sow doubt, and mining conspiracies for social media likes.”

Based on a pre-COVID-19 iteration, Bad News, the research team of GoViral! utilised research on surges in coronavirus conspiracies (named an ‘infodemic’ by the World Health Organisation) to sharpen the game (ibid). This naturally formed a more immediate model that is quicker to complete and simpler to modify for different languages and cultures (ibid). Revealing the most pervasive ‘infodemic’ tactics, players are able to discover how authentic news gets debunked by exploiting fake doctors and remedies, and how incorrect rumours such as the scandalous 5G gets advertised (ibid). The game also sheds light on how “out of context” videos are utilised to add credibility to fake news – and finishes with “conspiracies slipping beyond your control, even seeping into the mainstream” (ibid).

2.5 Germany

2.5.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

In Germany, no single, formal health and risk communications strategy or plan has been published that supersedes the strategy outlined in the National Pandemic Plan (Pandemieplan), which was issued in March 2017 by the Robert Koch Institute (RKI). However, between March 2021 and September 2022, numerous official documents have been published containing: 1) evaluations of past health and risk communication measures, and 2) recommendations for future measures, both on the level of general strategy and the level of specific measures and campaigns. These include, in chronological order:

- Inquiries submitted to the federal government by members of parliament, and statements by the federal government in response to these inquiries, published in the parliamentary record in May and September 2021 (so-called “Drucksache”). The inquiries and responses deal with numerous aspects of COVID-19 responses, including health and risk communication.
- Statements by the governmental Coronavirus Expert Council (ExpertInnenrat mit der Beratung der Bundesregierung auf der Grundlage aktueller wissenschaftlicher Erkenntnisse zur COVID-19 Pandemie), which was established in December 2021 and has been active ever since. The

statements focus on different aspects of COVID-19 responses, including health and risk communications.

- A comprehensive policy evaluation report prepared by a multidisciplinary Expert Committee empowered by the Infectious Disease Law IfGS (§ 5 para. 9), published in June 2022. The report includes a section focused specifically on health and risk communication (although it should be noted that this focal area was not specifically ordered in the IfGS).

The German COVID-19 communications planning is centralized and includes key actors such as the Ministry of Health (BMG), the Robert Koch Institute (RKI), and the Federal Center for Health Education (BZgA). A steering committee including representatives from these institutions meets regularly to monitor and evaluate communications strategies and campaigns. In 2021, a transparent evaluation cycle became a key attribute of German COVID-19 communications planning, with the government establishing an independent panel of experts to evaluate COVID-19 policy and give recommendations. In response to criticism, a pandemic working group was established within the RKI Standing Committee on Vaccines (STIKO) to improve communication between the STIKO and the BMG.

However, the bidding and contracting processes have not been without controversy: for instance, the Q3 2022 decision to award a vaccination communications contract to Hamburg-based agency Brinkert Lück, which had previously run election campaigns for the governing SPD, was criticised by opposition politicians and some press outlets as nepotistic.

Alongside centralised planning, the evaluations and recommendations published during the reference period consistently argue for the expansion of communications measures that actively involve the general public, specific target groups within the public, and civil society stakeholders alike. The source documents several practices that have been implemented as good examples:

- Enabling regular two-way communication with the general public via multilingual hotlines (or videoconference hotlines), as well as dedicated events, such as digital town hall meetings (cf. eleventh statement of the Coronavirus Expert Council).
- Engaging, training, and empowering local communications "multipliers" such as health practitioners, social workers, care workers, teachers, clubs, churches, unions, sports/cultural celebrities, public and private insurance companies, etc. (cf. Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy).

On a state level, the Baden-Württemberg Pandemic Influenza Plan designates the RKI as the authoritative source for medical information, the State Health Office for epidemic info, and the PEI and BfArM for information on vaccines and drugs. On Mannheim municipal level, the municipal Health Office is assumed to supplement data from state and national sources. German risk communication follows a centralized structure where regions and municipalities align with federal strategies, as established in the National Pandemic Plan to ensure uniform information, and prevent misinformation.

Regarding the distribution of communication responsibilities between federal, state, and municipal authorities, §8-15 of the the General Administrative Regulation on the Coordination of Infection Protection in Epidemically Significant Cases (Allgemeine Verwaltungsvorschrift über die Koordinierung des Infektionsschutzes in epidemisch bedeutsamen Fällen, IfSG Koordinierungs-VwV) establish that:

- Federal and state authorities must cooperate on defining pandemic measures and communications, with the Robert Koch Institute (RKI) as the definitive coordinator for technical information and external expert input;

- Public (“external”) crisis communication tasks should be divided between the federal and state governments “by mutual agreement”;
- Federal authorities are fundamentally responsible for communicating: 1) information on scientific questions; 2) facts on the international development of the situation; 3) international references (e.g., to data collected by other national health authorities);
- State and municipal authorities “should supplement the information provided by the federal government with a description of the respective state-specific or regional situation”;
- The RKI is responsible for providing situation reports and holding press conferences for the general public and the media, as well as for specialist professional audiences;
- The Federal Centre for Health Education (BZgA) is responsible for adapting the data provided by the RKI into informational material oriented to the general public;
- If a state or municipal authority intends to transmit information to the public that “deviates significantly from the facts communicated nationwide or contains significant innovations”, they must give the RKI an opportunity to make an assessment before doing so.

On a state level, the Baden-Württemberg Pandemic Influenza Plan recognizes the IfSG Koordinierungs-VwV as the authoritative source for responsibilities between the federal and state levels, designating the Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, and Integration as responsible for coordinating public relations work on health issues during a pandemic. On Mannheim municipal level, a formal distribution of roles and responsibilities has not been made public, with various departments (Health Office, Citizen Services, Education, etc.) appearing to be involved.

Regarding governmental risk communications in general, the source documents stress the importance of providing transparent, understandable, reliable, and consistent information about specific health risks, health in general, and the public health policymaking process. They regularly mention a coherent set of guidelines and goals, which are most concisely summarised in the Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy:

- Coordination: the core communication strategy is to run a nationwide “umbrella campaign” (Dachkampagne) – “Zusammen Gegen Corona” (Together Against Corona) – which is centralised with regard to data collection and interpretation as well as policy aims, and which is coordinated from a central point to avoid contradictions and mixed messaging;
- Factuality, timeliness, and transparency: all communications should reflect the current scientific state of the art, with transparency of sources, and acknowledgement of the boundaries of scientific knowledge and divergences in scientific opinion;
- Relevance to everyday life: communications should be relevant to target audiences’ everyday lives, support everyday decision-making, and address target audiences “at eye level” in a non-patronising and non-coercive tone;
- Transparent political communication: the political decision-making process should be described transparently, and the basis for decisions must be argued coherently, in order to promote trust in political actors and institutions;
- Participation: the public must be given a voice and channels for input to gain needed insights and maintain trust in democratic institutions; this must include the recognition and respectful handling of controversial opinions.

Several of the source documents emphasise the importance of centralised internal and public-facing information management platforms. With regard to internal information management, this entails maintaining a centralised database as the definitive source for all data communicated by governmental

and public health stakeholders, to improve the consistency of communication across platforms, etc. With regard to public-facing information management, this entails maintaining a single website, www.zusammengegencorona.de, that links all official information sources.

During the reference period of Q2 2021 to Q3 2022, there were no shifts in the main scientific sources of information communicated in governmental campaigns. The Robert Koch Institute and Paul Ehrlich Institute remained the scientific authorities of record.

2.5.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The Pandemic Influenza Plan furthermore identifies three central channels for state-level pandemic communication (p. 61):

- Press releases by the state Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, and Integration;
- The websites of the state Ministry of Social Affairs, Health, and Integration and State Health Office (Landesgesundheitsamt), as well as the state information service website;
- Communications released by radio stations and other press outlets, for instance as per a standing health communication dissemination agreement between the state Ministry of the Interior and the Südwestrundfunk radio station (SWR).

On a municipal level, several actors' public information sites' sections on COVID-19 redirect to a central COVID-19 information portal on the municipal site (www.mannheim.de/corona/). This is in accordance with the national-level recommendation to centralise public-facing pandemic-related information and service provision.

The "ÄrmelHoch" and recent campaigns in Germany changed their approach in vaccination communication. Instead of focusing on vulnerable groups and priority rules, the focus shifted to making it clear that anyone could get vaccinated, with the aim of making the message broadly accessible and appealing. The campaigns used video testimonials from diverse social, cultural, and professional backgrounds and regions, with a special emphasis on under vaccinated groups and regions. The strategy was multi-level, with federal-level messages being adapted for use at the regional and local levels, but the local adaptations were not monitored.

The first statement by the Coronavirus Expert Council, established in December 2021, that focuses specifically on risk and health communication. It is based on the premise that the majority of the general public want to support the fight against the pandemic, but must be provided with "responsive, evidence-based, target-group- and user-specific risk and health communication" in order to do so (p. 1). Specifically, a communication strategy is required that maintains awareness and supports "self-efficacy and risk-competent behaviour". To this end, the statement identifies four "building blocks" of effective communications:

- Establishing a foundation of the best available scientific knowledge: medical and epidemiological statistics and models, data on public behaviour and attitudes, and observations of informational trends in classical and social media;
- Translating data into user-oriented, target-group-specific, understandable, and actionable information formats (including participatory formats and tools such as decision trees), with the aim of "enlightenment rather than advertising or persuasion" within an atmosphere of informational competition and saturation (p. 1);
- Disseminating these formats via multiple channels, with attention to the informational behaviours of the intended audiences;

- Consistently evaluating and iteratively improving these communication measures.

After identifying these four building blocks, the statement notes that the pandemic has proved the critical importance of effective risk communication during crises. Accordingly, the statement argues that the “infrastructure for risk and health communication should be expanded quickly” by reinforcing existing multidisciplinary competencies, while building up missing ones (p. 2).

The Coronavirus Expert Council made several statements regarding communication during the pandemic. The 6th statement emphasized the importance of coordinated, health-protective communication on a federal level and increasing acceptance of regulations and recommendations. The 7th statement stressed the need for informational materials directed at parents, especially regarding child vaccination. The 9th statement called for informational campaigns on long COVID, targeted at both the general public and professional groups, following guidelines of the Association of Scientific Medical Societies. The 11th statement emphasized the need for simpler, more transparent and understandable regulations and recommendations, frequent two-way dialog with the public, and countering misinformation. It also suggested using checklists, digital nudges, and local "multipliers" for decision support and communication.

The purpose of the Evaluation of the Legal Basis and Measures of the Pandemic Policy is to assess the effectiveness and legal basis of pandemic measures taken during 2020-21 and propose recommendations for future measures, with particular focus on the protection of vulnerable groups. Specifically, it covers four topics: data management; risk communication; measures to combat the COVID-19 pandemic (e.g., social contact restrictions, hygiene recommendations, etc.); and an analysis of the legal basis of all dimensions of COVID-19 policy. The report is critical in tone, including in its very definition of risk communication:

“Risk communication, as a governmental task, should inform the public in a targeted manner about the magnitude and characteristics of the risk, about its significance, and about decisions and measures to deal with the risk. Furthermore, it should enable informed decisions, promote protective or life-sustaining behaviour, maintain trust in public institutions, and strengthen social cohesion. The quality of risk communication has a decisive influence on the perceived legitimacy and acceptance of the measures taken to combat the pandemic, and thus on their effectiveness. However, the potential of risk communication has remained largely untapped in Germany” (p. 13). The section on risk communication follows from this definition, covering:

- The meaning and central aims of risk communication
- Guidelines for effective risk communication based on the scientific state of the art
- The organisation of communications roles during the pandemic in Germany
- Means for communicating risks and insecurities
- Means for communicating numbers and trends
- The target-group-specific dissemination of information
- Participatory processes
- Recommendations for future crisis situations

Regarding immediate and long-term health information, the source documents emphasize the importance of transparently communicating factual and relevant health information based on current scientific knowledge, taking care to adapt recommendations to the scientific state of the art while maintaining understandability and consistency. The documents include specific recommendations for communication and aim to increase the overall health competence of the population. Long-term

health information, such as potential risks of "Long Covid", should be communicated to the public to allow them to adjust their risk calculations and take precautions.

With regard to the implementation of specific centrally planned campaigns, governmental stakeholders generally established framework contracts with different (private) communications agencies to design and distribute materials along multiple online and non-online channels.

2.5.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

The response to the "Statement on an inquiry" mentioned above goes on to emphasise that governmental communications aim to reach every part of society, including migrant-background and ethnic minority residents, the elderly and young, the deaf, and medical personnel. Measures taken to this end include:

- Use of multiple channels, e.g., mass media and social media;
- Use of multiple languages;
- Use of testimonials representative of different social and cultural backgrounds;
- Consultation with specialists in cross-cultural communication;
- Proactive cooperation with "multipliers" with connections to vulnerable groups.

It asks what measures have been taken to reach vulnerable groups (non-German-speakers, the socio-economically precarious, etc.), and raises the question of whether these measures are adequate. It also introduces the topic of vaccine hesitancy and how to address it, for instance among young people.

On a state level, the Baden-Württemberg Pandemic Influenza Plan acknowledges the need to ensure that critical information is accessible to the entire public; however, it does not define specific measures to reach vulnerable or socially marginalised groups. Likewise, on a Mannheim municipal level, general strategies for addressing vulnerable or socially marginalised groups have not been defined on a formal level.

Specific practices and campaigns on both the state and municipal levels do demonstrate an awareness of the need to address vulnerable and marginalised groups. These practices and campaigns normally adhere to national-level recommendations:

Multilingual and easy-to-understand COVID-19 information (target group: non-German speakers):

The Baden-Württemberg state and Mannheim municipal governments both host COVID-19 information sites in multiple languages, including German, English, French, Italian, Spanish, Portuguese, Turkish, Polish, Croatian, Romanian, Ukrainian, Russian, Arabic, and Farsi. The state site provides information on state-level pandemic measures and ordinances. The Mannheim site links to the state site, a multilingual COVID-19 hotline, multilingual vaccine information, and information on traveling to Germany. The Rhein-Neckar-Kreis district also maintains a COVID-19 information site with actual case numbers, hygiene and behavioural recommendations, and links to other multilingual information sources.

Broad visual representation (target group: all residents regardless of personal characteristics):

State- and local-level informational materials generally feature visuals representing people with varying skin tones, body types, gender presentations, etc. An example is the #dranbleibenBW website, which features diverse and inclusive cartoon visuals, as well as videos narrated by experts with diverse ethnic backgrounds.

MALUmat (target group: Turkish-speaking residents):

In Winter 2021/2022, the BKK ran a public consultation with Turkish-speaking residents of Mannheim and Ludwigshafen (MALU) on the topic of crisis and disaster warnings: specifically, on channels (what channels can be used to reach people most quickly and effectively) and content (what are peoples' needs with regard to warning messages). The first stage, an online workshop, was held in December 2021, while the second stage, an open online call for commentary, was held in February 2022. The initiative – which was based on the recognition that “experiences and needs with regard to emergency warnings are as heterogenous as the population” – was to provide input for the further development of the BKK-NINA-App and serve as a “model project for other cities, regions, and population groups in Germany.” Promotional materials included a German/Turkish website and a German/Turkish printable brochure.

Impf-O-Mat (target group: the elderly and vaccine sceptics):

The Impf-o-Mat was an online tool launched as part of the #dranbleibenBW state-level campaign to help users calculate the risk-benefit of getting vaccinated against COVID-19. The tool produced an individualized list of reasons for and against vaccination based on information such as age, gender, previous illnesses and other risk factors entered by the user. The concept was first suggested in a government inquiry in 2021 and developed by two doctors in early 2022. The Impf-o-Mat was implemented by a digital media studio at a cost of 142,176.65 EUR, with the goal of providing personalized and understandable communication to overcome doubts and close the vaccination gap between different population segments. The tool stopped functioning in October 2022.

2.5.4 Strategies: Methods used

The “Statement on an inquiry: Health communication of the Federal Government and the Federal Centre for Health Education in the Corona pandemic (04.05.2021)” responds to an inquiry made by a group of health-system-focused politicians of the Green Party, spearheaded by Dr. Kirsten Kappert-Gonther, Kordula Schulz-Asche, and Dr. Janosch Dahmen. The inquiry is critical in tone, alleging that governmental communication strategies lack clarity and consistency. The inquiry suggests that this causes confusion among the public about current rules and recommendations, as well as affecting public risk perceptions and willingness to adopt protective behaviours. It is particularly critical of communications targeted at socially vulnerable groups, such as non-German-speakers and the precarious. Specific question areas include the government’s general communication strategy, its basis in behavioural and science, what actors are involved, how campaigns are coordinated and evaluated, and what measures are taken to ensure clarity for particular vulnerable groups.

In its response to the inquiry, the CDU-SPD coalition government indicates that its communications strategy is based on a national “umbrella campaign” (Dachkampagne) – “Zusammen Gegen Corona” (Together Against Corona) – accompanied by smaller targeted campaigns. The strategy’s guiding principles are transparency, factual currency, understandability, and reliability. The coordinating actors are the Ministry of Health (BMG) and the major federal public health institutions (RKI, PEI, BZgA), which meet multiple times weekly. Under this umbrella, the central communication device is the “AHA – Abstand-Hygiene-Alltag mit Maske” (distance, hygiene, everyday masking) campaign, which is designed to be agile, so it can be supplemented dynamically with additional statements (such as “L” for “lüftung” or ventilation), while the central vaccination campaign is “Deutschland krempelt die #ÄrmelHoch” (Germany rolls up the sleeves).

Two apps have been used by governmental and public health stakeholders to convey warnings and alerts. On a basic level, critical COVID-19 information, such as nationwide and local case rates, have been broadcast in the BKK-NINA-App, a general crisis and disaster warning and alert app launched by the BKK in 2015. On a COVID-19-specific level, the Corona-Warn-App functions as a track-and-trace system, a channel for warnings and alerts, and a channel for more general information dissemination. The Corona-Warn-App is an open-source project initiated in May 2020 at the request of the federal government by SAP and Deutsche Telekom subsidiary T-Systems, with support from a very wide range of governmental, civil society, and private sector partners. It maintains a rotating unique cryptographic identifier (key), scans for the identifiers of other nearby mobile devices using the app and stores them for 14 days.

Based on backend and EDUS data, the eleventh statement of the Coronavirus Expert Council on “Pandemic preparation for Autumn/Winter 2022/23” recommends maintaining and adapting the current functionality of the Corona-Warn-App, while building out its potential as a means of directly transmitting health information to users and as a prevention tool (p. 15). A full version log, including updates made during the reference period of Q2 2021 to Q3 2022, is maintained on Github.

2.5.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

On a state level, the Baden-Württemberg Pandemic Influenza Plan recognises misinformation on social media as a problem, but does not define specific measures for combating it. The state-level umbrella campaign #dranbleibenBW, however, does include a Q&A section and various videos oriented toward debunking vaccine myths. On a Mannheim municipal level, specific measures for combating misinformation do not appear to have been defined.

The CDU-SPD coalition government’s response identifies the RKI COVIMO and Universität Erfurt COSMO as important sources of insight on vaccination behaviour and barriers, notes that the RKI COVIMO would start to run surveys in languages other than German, and introduces the BZgA CoSID study on vaccination communication, initiated in July 2021. Measures against misinformation are also specified, including the regular screening of social media and creation of refutations and preventative messages (“Debunks”) targeted for the relevant audiences, as well as the flagging of bad actors.

2.6 Greece

2.6.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

In the case of Greece, a formal communication plan was implemented from the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, each wave demanded changes both to messages and key communicators. It must be mentioned also that all communication plans and strategies as well as messages distribution were drafted and issued through governmental actors, experts, epidemiologists or Ministers.

Most communication initiatives were taken by the General Secretariat of Civil Protection (GSCP) which has had a pivot role in coordinating the country’s response to COVID-19 crisis.

Late in December 2021, weekly governmental press briefings begun with the participation of The President of The National Vaccination Committee and The General Secretary of Primary Healthcare of

the Ministry of Health with the exclusive purpose of informing the public for all vaccination related issues and updating them about the National Vaccination Plan for COVID-19 (Emvolio.gov.gr, n.d.).

As the pandemic waves unfolded the Greek Government adapted the communication strategy according to the vaccination rates, the respective epidemiological situation of the country and the implemented measures. Although the Greek Authorities were responsible for creating and distributing all COVID-19 related messages, scientific experts were involved since the beginning of the pandemic, expressing their views in the media coverage, which was sometimes contradictory or even opposite to the official governmental policy. This often created confusion and misinformation influencing people's attitudes towards vaccination and health measures compliance (Tovima, 2021).

It can be observed that officials understood the importance of accessibility to the communicated messages ensuring at the same time the greatest possible acceptance of these messages through synergies and partnerships across all levels of government and involved stakeholders.

As the pandemic evolved, Greek Authorities adopted their communication strategy according to new needs that emerged following the example of international organizations and agencies.

Concerning the other stakeholders involved in the communication strategy and the relevant vaccination campaign, it is observed that the National Public Health Organization/NPHO (Εθνικός Οργανισμός Δημόσιας Υγείας/ΕΟΔΥ) was the one that was the firmest engaged, with press conferences and public statements, utilizing its website in order to further inform citizens about the pandemic.

9 high profile officials were involved in COVID-19 proceedings, related to NPHO or other stakeholders. These officials are: the Minister of Health (Vassilis Kikilias & Thanos Plevris), Deputy Minister of Health (Mina Gaga), Deputy Minister for Climate Crisis and Civil Protection (Nikos Hardalias), Deputy Minister of Labour and Social Affairs (Domna Michailidou), Minister of Education and Religious Affairs (Niki Kerameus), President of NPHO (Theoklis Zaoutis), a member of the panel of experts (Gkikas Magiorkinis), and the first COVID-19 crisis spokesperson (Sotirios Tsiodras).

Regional and local authorities in the context of social responsibility and citizen awareness, contributed in practice to the protection of public health by informing the public about the benefits of vaccination against COVID-19 amongst many other activities (Lampropoulou, 2021).

2.6.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The first communication strategy in Greece was shaped from two key actions. The first one was daily briefings from the Undersecretary of Civil Protection and Crisis Management alongside with the President of the Experts Committee. Additionally, the first holistic communication campaign was the "We Stay at Home" (Μένουμε Σπίτι/Menoume Spiti) which motivated citizens to stay at home and avoid unnecessary movements to reduce infections. The campaign, which was initially launched during the first lockdown, was adopted from both public and private entities, and was distributed all over the country. Tv and radio ads, print, digital and traditional channels were utilized, and efforts from private entities have also been made to repost the produced logo of the campaign and the slogan, so to appear almost everywhere. As for example, telecommunication companies adopted the relevant hashtag #MenoumeSpiti for their signal on smartphones. The following periods the campaign remained more or less the same with the difference that messages were shaped according to the epidemiological situation. For instance, after the ease of the first measures the "We Stay at Home" campaign was changed to "We Stay Safe" (Μένουμε Ασφαλείς/Menoume Asfaleis). Messages and ads were adopted

consequently to inform people how to stay safe and avoid getting infected following a three-pillar rule: hands-distance-face masks.

The following period, communication efforts were more or less developed under the “We Stay Safe” umbrella aiming mainly to provide valid information to people concerning the fight against COVID-19 and raise public awareness about the pandemic.

Communication initiatives taken by the GSCP entailed General Public Guidelines published not only in Greek language but also in English, French, Arabic, Albanian, Russian and Farsi, Guidelines for vulnerable groups, Questions and Answers about the pandemic, useful information about the COVID-19 designated help line (1135) but also informational videos and TV spots (GSCP,n.d.).

It was only when the vaccination program began, that new messages were created, and the promoted campaigns started to be intensively focused on this issue. The plan, as well as the relevant communication campaign, begun simultaneously aiming to inform citizens about vaccination procedures and importance, together with the goal to motivate them getting vaccinated.

The daily briefings with key spokespersons as in the first pandemic wave, were broadcasted at less frequent intervals around late May 2020, initially three times a week and then became weekly until they gradually stopped. In the pandemic waves that followed press briefings were made on an ad hoc basis depending on the emerging issue each time (implementation of new measures for example) and were led mainly by the Minister of Health accompanied by members of the public health experts National Committee.

Through the times the Greek Government which was responsible to create and distribute the COVID-19 communication messages, evaluate either by analysing raw data or by assessing public responses the acceptance of each message from the public. For instance, a message created from General Secretariat of Civil Protection (GSCP) communicating the importance of distance measures was forced to be withdrawn since it was criticized for sexism (Naftemporiki, 2020).

More precisely, the “Freedom” Plan included a holistic communication campaign with ads broadcasted in tv, radio, social media, print covering, and in a wide range of both digital and traditional advertising methods. Further, since the strategy was initiated by the government, a dedicated website was created (www.emvolio.gov.gr) which included information about available vaccines, statistics, as well as was hosting the vaccination booking platform.

All videos were also available in the official governmental YouTube channel. The promoted communication strategy aimed to enhance further people’s trust to the authorities and the scientific community, promote awareness about the effectiveness of the vaccines and ultimately motivate people to vaccinate (Ladi, Angelou & Panagiotatou,2021).

The Prime Minister Kyriakos Mitsotakis himself, who since the beginning of the pandemic very often addressed the Greek people highlighting the significance of compliance with the measures applied to protect public health against COVID-19 (Poulakidakos, 2021) promoted with greater intensity the message to strengthen vaccination in order to build a strong immunity wall as a personal responsibility towards society, disseminating respective appeals to the public through press interviews (Tziouvaras,2021, Papandoniou, 2021) or by posting relevant spots and messages on his social media (Ethnos, 2021). Kyriakos Mitsotakis wrote on his social media accounts: "Day by day we build a strong wall of immunity for ourselves and for those around us. Make your own appointment of a lifetime and

become part of the shield that will protect your own health, the health of your loved ones and the entire society.

Another example of the Greek Government's efforts to harmonize the broadcasted messages with the applied preventive measures, was the most recent campaign on the mandatory use of masks in urban public transport launched in July 2022 as an initiative of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, placed in stations, stops and lines of fixed transport (Naftemporiki, 2022). The aim of the campaign was to convey the message to the passengers not only of the obligation to wear a mask in public transport but also the importance of it, in a period of increased use of public transport due to the touristic season and the presence of foreign visitors in the country. Using its own promotion media, the Public Transport Company (STASY) informed the passengers that the use of a mask with high respiratory protection (FFP2 or N95) or alternatively a double mask (surgical and fabric) remains mandatory on public transport.

The Daily epidemiological surveillance infection reports together with the public proceedings were the main tools of information distribution not only to the press, but also to the general public, thus playing a critical role in passing along sanitation and safety regulations as well as the need for vaccination, in accordance with the "We Stay at Home", "We Stay Safe" and "Freedom" campaign initiatives, formulated by the communication strategy of the central government.

Most organizations communicated relevant messages regarding vaccination mainly through their websites or social media but without creating a dedicated campaign.

2.6.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

The vaccination communication campaign included videos of persons of an older age since they were the first group to be vaccinated. More precisely, two well-known actors, Giorgos Konstantinou and Maro Kontou, which have starred in multiple old Greek movies and were a notorious movie couple, participated in the first vaccination spot intending to inform and motivate older people to get vaccinated, since their group was eligible for vaccination.

All messages were shaped accordingly targeting not only each vaccination group, but also vulnerable groups and/or groups of people that were sceptic, such as pregnant women, teenagers, children, etc. For each group the communicator was chosen carefully, in order to match the message, for instance pregnant women messages and information were communicated by gynaecologists, whereas messages for the general public were made mainly thought well-known and generally accepted persons.

Messages, as well as press briefings started to be broadcasted also in sign language especially during the second pandemic wave.

The Hellenic Ministry of Health launched a dedicated campaign, with the aim of informing the public about the Long Covid syndrome, its effects, but also the ways of protection highlighting once again vaccination against COVID 19 as a primary priority (Ministry of Health, 2022). The central message of the campaign was "The best protection against the Long Covid syndrome is vaccination", aiming first, at young ages, children and pregnant women, with the scope to further increase vaccination rates, especially at a time, when the acute phase of the pandemic subsides, and the main concern is focused on the longer-term effects on public health.

Information campaign by the Public Transport Company was conveyed in Greek and English while large stickers on the station platforms, floor stickers in front of the ticket validating machines, posters, and banners in the station registers, notice boards and ticket offices, as well as stickers at all the doors of the trains were placed (Ethnos, 2022). At the same time audio messages were broadcasted at Metro and Tram stations and stops, as well as inside all trains in Greek, English, German, and French. Focus was given to those stations of the network that are entry and exit gates for visitors, such as the Airport and Piraeus stations (where the largest port of the country is), as well as to stations with increased tourist traffic, such as Syntagma, Monastiraki, Panepistimio, Omonia and Acropolis, while the campaign remained in the "air" throughout the summer.

The Institute of Preventive Medicine, Environmental and Occupational Health (Prolepsis) which is a non-governmental organization, implemented a campaign to promote vaccination against COVID-19 on social media. The campaign was carried out in collaboration with Stanford University School of Medicine through sharing and promoting short messages and videos on Facebook. More precisely, the campaign focused on parents of teenagers, young people, women of childbearing age, groups with strong religious interests, Muslim Western communities, and Roma communities, etc., which presumably owned lower rates of COVID-19 vaccination coverage in relation to the average. The campaign, which consisted of dedicated public health messages in form of visual and short videos, includes volunteer doctors, nurses, university professors, journalists, actors, pharmacists, athletes, representatives of the Church and religious communities, and Roma mediators. The cost of promoting the campaign at Facebook was fully covered by the Medical School of Stanford University, while all work related to the design, preparation, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of the results was implemented by the Prolepsis Institute, without funding. In order to assess the effectiveness of the action, the campaign was aired on a trial basis since mid-October 2021 in 22 regional units with lower rates of vaccination coverage, based on data collected from official bodies (emvolio.gov, ECDC, EOD). The campaign was viewed 26,070,812 times from 1,878,601 Facebook users. The preliminary assessment of the data revealed that during the first 3 weeks of the campaign's implementation compared to the previous 3 weeks before the launch, there was a significant increase in vaccination appointments both in the country as a whole and in the 22 regional sections of the campaign launch.

The United Nations Refugee Agency provided all relevant information on a dedicated webpage of their official website, informing refugees on how and where to get vaccinated as well as multiple information about vaccines (The UN Refugee Agency, 2022).

2.6.4 Strategies: Methods used

The "We share memories, not the virus" campaign urged people to get tested against COVID-19 after their summer holidays and before going back to their everyday activities like work. The "Masks that smile" campaign mainly targeted school-age children promoting the reasons why they should wear a face mask during school lessons and was released right before the school year started (GSCP, n.d.).

The vaccination communication campaign included videos of two well-known actors. In the spot, entitled "The Rendezvous", the song "New Life" can be heard, in its first performance, by Sofia Vembo, a legendary Greek singer. The two actors meet but do not embrace. "No hugs, next time," says Maro Kondou and they walk together towards the vaccination centre. "A vaccination appointment is a lifetime appointment" is written in the last seconds of the spot. "We care, we protect ourselves, we get vaccinated." (Naftemporiki, 2021). These phrases were also used by Prime Minister Kyriakos Mitsotakis who also posted the spot on his social media accounts (@PrimeministerGR, 2021).

An indicative example is the partnership between the Ministries of Education and Religious Affairs, of Health and of Interior, the Municipalities, and the Hellenic Pediatric Society to boost vaccinations for children aged 12-17. The purpose of this collaboration was to promote additional ways of informing parents and guardians about the vaccination against COVID-19, in order to primarily protect the children themselves, safeguard the educational process and ultimately shield society as a whole (Ministry of Interior, 2021). In this context an informational online event was organized, during which members of the National Vaccination Committee (NCC) and reputable paediatricians discussed questions and answers to frequently asked questions, informing parents and guardians about the vaccination of children and adolescents while a dedicated tab has been created at the official site of the Ministry (Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs, 2021).

The Hellenic Ministry of Health vaccination campaign also aimed to raise awareness among citizens who have not been vaccinated or who have not yet received their booster dose. The information campaign consists of short video-personal testimonies, through which patients with Long Covid share the dramatic effects on their daily lives: the 45-year-old Stelios, who didn't have time to be vaccinated, saw his fingers deformed. Today, he finds it difficult to hug his children. The 35-year-old Anna who got infected together with her 4.5-year-old daughter is getting tired just as standing up while her daughter needs lots of breaks in any activity she's undertaking. The 59-year-old Iulia, for 730 days now, suffers from shortness of breath, tachycardia and daily fever (Lefimerida, 2022). The spot also informs the public about the activity of the Hellenic Union of people suffering from the long-term consequences of COVID-19 on the website of which the relevant spots are also available along with additional information.

Regarding the campaign on the mandatory use of masks in urban public transport, in case of non-compliance, an administrative fine of three hundred euros will be imposed by the Police.

The Municipality of Piraeus which is the county's largest Port City and its most recent Informative activity about the benefits of vaccination (Municipality of Piraeus, 2022). During the campaign that had as central message "I get vaccinated, I live carefree" an information sheet was distributed to residents, as well as free antiseptic gels and disposable individual protection masks. This initiative led by the Directorate of Public Health and Social Services took place in central points of all five Municipal Communities of Piraeus, in Primary and Secondary Education schools, in public markets and in every other place that public is concentrated. The purpose of this special action was to convince people to get vaccinated in case they were still sceptical about it, with special emphasis on informing children and their parents about the safety and significance of vaccination.

2.6.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

To combat misinformation and disinformation, especially during the vaccination period, the government created a dedicated tab in the official vaccination site (emvolio.gr) and respond in frequently asked questions but also included in designated Tv spots responses of health experts giving scientific arguments and answers to theories or worries of people. It can be observed that the Greek government addressed common worries or misunderstandings through their communication messages.

2.7 Ireland

2.7.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

Key actors responsible for implementing the new communication strategies, plans, practices include the Communications and Behavioural Advisory Group, the Health Service Executive (HSE), the Ministers for Health and the Taoiseach (prime minister and head of government of Ireland).

Focusing on the year 2021, Ireland's 'Resilience and Recovery 2020-2021 – Plan for Living with COVID-19' is relevant. The government plan, created on 15 September 2020, is aimed at "bringing some clarity to help everyone to plan over the medium term.". The plan details how COVID-19 communications should be delivered in the years 2020/2021.

With a focus on COVID-19 communications, the 2020-2021 plan would manage COVID-19 by considering the following communication priorities:

- "Clarity and transparency": All communications will be understandable and correct. Following the execution of the plan, the government will work to guarantee that the rationale for the measures, the public health triggers that elevated the risk level and the implications for certain groups, sectors, individuals are coherently communicated (ibid)
- "Cohesion and Co-ordination": Within the context of a pandemic, communication needs a high level of collaboration between bodies, agencies, and all broader stakeholders. It was recognised that when faced with difficult messages, it would be important to offer opportunities for engagement and debate, but eventually assure that the public receive coherent and explicit messages (ibid)
- "Rapid Response": Following the execution of the plan, it was stressed that it would be important to have an agile system put in place to handle enquiries (media, sectoral representatives, general public etc.) as promptly as possible (ibid)
- "Insight based": All communications to be tested and measured so that they would achieve planned aims (ibid)

The following points were emphasised in the plan:

- The upgraded decision-making framework and communications plan are composed to guarantee that there will be enough opportunity for punctual and extensive stakeholder information presentation and engagement, media campaigns/informational packages as needed, governed by the appropriate Ministers and Departments (ibid)
- The gov.ie/COVID page to be assessed with the intention of offering simpler guidance to relevant data (ibid)
- An organised calendar or briefings will be approved involving appropriate Ministers after certain Cabinet decisions, bi-weekly National Public Health Emergency Team (NPHET) disease updates and a weekly official update on general developments and execution of the new Roadmap (ibid)
- The Crisis Communications Committee have agreed to carry on meeting to assure the highest coordination between cross-government and sectorally-led campaigns and communications (ibid).

Commenting on public health communications during the COVID-19 pandemic, Dr Gerald Barry, a University College Dublin virologist explained to BreakingNews.ie in June 2022 that "on a Government/Department of Health, HSE level there doesn't seem to be much else going on in terms

of trying to stop people getting infected” (ibid). To stop the spread of COVID-19, Dr Barry recommended strengthened communications which would help with future waves. In his own words, Dr Barry said: “the Department of Health and the body which has replaced the National Public Health Emergency Team (Nphet), the Covid-19 Advisory Group, should focus on improving communication along with other measures to mitigate the spread of Covid-19 in the population” (ibid).

To date, there is limited information on what 2022 public health communication priorities have involved.

With a focus on the education sector, particularly in universities, a commitment was made to a notable increase in on-site further and higher education from the beginning of the next academic year. The commitment was declared on 29 April 2021 and the relevant plan created is called A Safe Return: Plan for a Safe Return to On-site Further and Higher Education and Research in 2021/22. The Department, its agencies, stakeholders, institutions, and providers have agreed a Pact of actions and commitments to support ongoing efforts in relation to the pandemic and to ensure that planning is well-grounded in safe and sustainable practices to be completed in time for autumn 2021 (ibid). With a focus on the commitment to provide regular and transparent communications, the plan emphasised the following Guiding Principles:

- “When we know, you know.” Plans, guidance and policies will be communicated as far in advance as possible, recognising that public health advice is subject to change and that some uncertainty will always exist
- The safety of our staff, students and learners is paramount (ibid).
- Institutions and providers commit to...
- Timely communications with staff, students and learners. If there is a reason for delay or uncertainty, that reason will be communicated
- Close engagement with each other and with public health to ensure that communications are consistent and evidence-based
- Close engagement with the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science (D/FHERIS) to support and inform national communications
- Clear communications to students and learners on the increases in on-site activities that they can expect (ibid).

Stakeholder bodies commit to...

- Close engagement to ensure that communications are consistent and evidence-based
- Develop specific but aligned messaging for members (ibid).

D/FHERIS commits to...

- Timely communication with stakeholders and institutions
- Supporting institutions in developing communications materials
- Communicating the plan nationally and internationally, and in support of institutions (ibid).

When looking for the right information for businesses to reopen, Fáilte Ireland, the National Tourism Development Authority, developed support materials for businesses to communicate with their customers which was made available on their website.

2.7.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

In the D7.1 Baseline Report, it was reported that communications predominantly focused on the introduction of strengthened social restrictions, with a focus on public health guidelines and recommendations; testing, contact tracing, and physical distancing. The focus of the communication was ‘Stay at Home, whilst new terms such as ‘cocooning’ were also introduced. In the afore-mentioned 2020/2021 plan, it is possible to see a change of focus whereby communications start to focus on assisting and encouraging people to take care of their health, prepare for the winter months, strengthen mental resilience, and assure that people know how to utilise the health services during the winter period (ibid).

In a 25 April 2022 press release, it was revealed that the NPHET did not communicate crucial COVID-19 possibilities and uncertainties as well as it should have done to the government. To be more specific, public health expert Professor Philip Nolan said that he did not communicate the COVID-19 models “as well necessary” to Government ministers, weeks prior to Ireland obtaining the world’s highest incidence of COVID-19 cases (ibid). At the time of reporting, Nolan, former head of NPHET said that as health experts, “we need to be better at communicating the range of possibilities and uncertainties.”

Three months later, additional criticism of NPHET communications were reported. In July 2022, for example, it was reported that the NPHET and the government of Ireland were not collaborating well in terms of COVID-19 communications to the public (ibid). As mentioned in a press release, this was “having a crushing effect on society,” (ibid) which was believed to “derail” the “collective response to COVID-19” (ibid).

At the time of publication, it was revealed that the government is “continually surprised by NPHET’s recommendations,” (ibid) and that it was forced to “scramble to review the data, deliberate and make decisions under pressure” (ibid).

According to Sarah Regan, author of the press release, public health communication was also having a negative impact on businesses. Regan said: “Businesses, too, are repeatedly blindsided by inconsistent and mixed messaging, impractical plans, and no clarity or certainty. Many, particularly those in hospitality, remain in limbo, unsure of how and when their businesses can open, with costly implications for staff and stock” (ibid).

The “disjointed” communications was said to sabotage confidence in the reopening of society, especially during a time when efforts were needed to assure workers and consumers that it is safe to leave their homes and go back to living life as normal (ibid). Indeed, the lack of clear messages was said to draw economic and psychological damage (i In a 25 November 2021 NPHET meeting note publication, it was declared that COVID-19 communications would focus on providing clear and consistent messaging focusing on the critical public health messages of:

- Getting the COVID-19 vaccine/booster once it is offered;
- Self-isolating and obtaining a PCR test if symptoms appear;
- Wearing a face mask;
- Washing your hands thoroughly and frequently;
- Prioritising and minimising the number of interactions with other people;
- Meeting outdoors whenever possible. When indoors, opening windows to allow ventilation;
- Staying clear of crowds (ibid).

In 2022 in particular, it was recognised that public health communications on COVID-19 must be improved.

2.7.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

In the plan, a number of new targets were identified. Using their experience, the appropriate Departments (Children, Equality, Disability, Integration and Youth, Housing, Social Protection, Health) in coordination with their agencies committed to updating plans to help safeguard the most vulnerable (Government of Ireland, 2020). The commitment to do this corresponded with the escalation framework laid out in the plan (ibid). The aims laid out ensure that certain measures are directed to homeless, and traveller/Roma communities. The measures are as follows:

- Sufficient public health support made accessible to diminish risk
- Vulnerable residents being safeguarded
- Providing accommodation if there is a requirement to self-isolate;
- Information and language obstacles being removed so that resident's comprehension and adherence with public health advice, their rights in the workplace, and access to public services are sufficiently communicated and acknowledged (ibid).

As mentioned in the D7.1 Baseline report, community support forums and helplines were formed by local authorities. They were collectively referred to as the 'Community Call' initiative. Following the NESC paper looking at how the Community Call was formed, how it has developed, and the learning from this innovative programme, the Department of Rural and Community Development (DRCD) hosted a webinar to reflect on how these new ways of working can be built upon for effective policy and service delivery in the future.

In addition to the webinar, there are a series of COVID-19 communication packs for community and voluntary groups. The relevant packs include:

- Sensible Volunteering in response to COVID-19
- How can I Volunteer in response to COVID-19
- Advice for Vulnerable People
- Advice on the Recruitment of Volunteers for Community and Voluntary Groups
- You, Your Community and COVID-19 – Information on Community Support
- The information packs can be downloaded

2.7.4 Strategies: Methods used

To address COVID-19 vaccine misinformation, key measures were put in place (ibid). For example, the HSE set up a multilingual ad campaign running on digital audio platforms such as TuneIn and Spotify (ibid). This was set up to guarantee that Ireland's immigrant community, who were considered to be more vulnerable to misinformation (due to linguistic barriers), obtain accurate health advice (ibid).

At the time of reporting, a HSE spokeswoman said: "Dynamic audio allows us to pick up the language setting on a person's phone to deliver a suitable ad" (ibid). The spokeswoman further added: "Polish ads are the most frequently heard of these so far. We will continue to monitor performance of available languages. Radio ads are also on community radio in Italian, Spanish, French, Polish, Punjabi, Urdu and Russian" (ibid).

Also known as the #ForUsAll, which launched in May, the campaign offers data on the vaccine rollout via social media. It is specifically targeted at young people to encourage them to "be part of the biggest

social movement of our time,” said the HSE spokeswoman at the time. According to the HSE spokeswoman, the Covid-19 Vaccine Community Network, which includes the Gaelic Athletic Association, faith groups and healthcare staff, helped strengthen confidence in the COVID-19 vaccine (ibid).

2.7.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

With a focus on COVID-19 vaccine uptake, especially amongst younger adults, the government of Ireland announced that it would “seek to fight the online spread of misinformation on coronavirus vaccines as the jabs are rolled out to younger people”. This statement was made on 28 July 2021.

In order to address the harm of misinformation being directed towards the youth, predominantly aged between the age of 12-18, Taoiseach Micheál Martin said: “We will be looking specifically at countering misinformation on social media” (ibid) that may be intended for young people. “Increasingly there is a sense that this is happening out there online. So we constantly reassess our communications around Covid, around vaccines and that is something that we will be focusing in on,” (ibid) added Mr Martin.

On 22 April 2021, the HSE created a page titled ‘Dealing with fake health information during the COVID-19 pandemic’. Recognising that online content can contain misinformation, also referred to as “fake news,” HSE stressed the importance of:

- Questioning where data has originated from
- Being vigilant of COVID-19 testing and vaccine scams
- Knowing how to identify and deal with misinformation
- Utilising reliable information sources (ibid).

On their webpage, HSE recommend referring to a number of sources which contain reliable COVID-19 information. The sources include HSE, DOH, World Health Organisation (WHO), and the European Centre for Disease Control (ibid).

In terms of social media platforms, HSE have worked in partnership with Google, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and TikTok to ensure that people living in Ireland are guided towards trustworthy HSE.ie content when they specifically search for information on COVID-19 and COVID-19 vaccines (ibid). For example, when you search for data on COVID-19 vaccines on Twitter, it will be possible to see ‘Know the facts and a link to COVID-19 content (ibid). Another example is the HSE COVID-19 information pop-ups in Instagram and Facebook.

In a 23 July 2021 press release, it was also reported that more than 800 posts comprising misinformation, or which were possibly detrimental to people’s health, was noted by the HSE to social media networks since February. In a statement, Dr Ronan Glynn warned that inaccurate data about COVID-19 vaccines, which began spreading even before vaccines had been created, was sabotaging vaccination efforts in numerous countries, “prolonging the pandemic and putting lives at risk.”

On 10 March 2021, Facebook Ireland revealed that they would be launching a new campaign in collaboration with the WHO and its European fact-checking partners to inform people on how to identify false vaccination news. The campaign, otherwise known as ‘Together Against Covid-19 Misinformation,’ was significant. As mentioned in the press release, the campaign “launches at an important juncture in the rollout of Ireland’s national COVID-19 vaccination programme.”

At the time of reporting, it was announced that the campaign would roll out to newsfeeds in Ireland via a range of ads encouraging people to connect with reliable information from credible sources such

as Ireland’s HSE, and reduce misinformation by asking them to check the following when viewing content online:

- Check The Source: Scrutinise content, even if it appears science based
- Check How It Makes You Feel: False news can manipulate feelings for clicks
- Check The Context: Look to public health authorities to confirm content

This campaign has been launched to provide further tools, knowledge and resources to help inform people on how to detect false news – and ultimately stop sharing it.

The HSE’s #OurHealthService COVID-19 vaccine stories featuring real people getting the vaccine have reached around one million people per post; while their Instagram posts have reached over 669,000 people. HSE chief executive Paul Reid: “Social media is an essential platform for us to communicate and we’ve used it very successfully to communicate our key messages to the majority of the population. We welcome the work Facebook is undertaking to help users spot false news in relation to COVID-19 and vaccines. Public safety remains our top priority and we will continue to share factual, up-to-date information from trusted sources, which will in turn allow people to make informed and confident decisions about COVID-19 vaccines.”

Dualta Ó Broin, head of Public Policy at Facebook Ireland said: “Throughout the Covid-19 pandemic we have been connecting people to accurate information and reducing misinformation on our platforms. We are removing harmful misinformation about vaccines and COVID-19. We also want to empower people to decide for themselves what to read, trust, and share. This campaign will encourage users to connect with accurate information around vaccines and will highlight the broader steps we are taking against misinformation on Facebook.”.

2.8 Israel

2.8.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

In August 2020, the management of Israel’s national program for addressing COVID-19 was assigned to Magen Israel, a new organizational unit with leadership from the Ministry of Health. Magen Israel then established a special task force charged with focusing on the population of ultra-Orthodox Jews and another special task force focused on the Israeli Arab population. These task forces were established in consultation with leaders of the relevant communities and included professionals from within those communities. Subsequently, a third task force was established to address the needs of the general population – Israelis who are neither Arabs nor ultra-Orthodox Jews. Toward the end of 2020, these task forces were also charged with promoting vaccine uptake. They did so through four main strategies: analysis of the reasons for slow vaccine uptake, partnership with community leaders, tailored messaging, and easing access to vaccination sites.

National elections on March 21st, 2021, and the escalation of tension and civil unrest led to a military operation (operation Guardian of the Walls) in May 2021.

Since May 2015, the position of the Head of the National Spokesperson Office was not occupied, resulting in lack of consistency and organization in the messages and communication strategies of the government and the ministries. In September 2021, after more than six years, a director was appointed for the position.

As government change took place on June 2021, the management of the pandemic was criticized by both parties, increasing the mistrust of the public in the measures taken.

Furthermore, prior to the pandemic schisms in Israeli society revolved around religion (secular vs. religious), ethnic origin, nationality (Arabs vs. Jews) and socioeconomic status rather than around issues of health. The way the COVID-19 crisis was managed and constructed in the news generated a new social schism in Israeli society that had never existed before: between the vaccinated and the unvaccinated, a phenomenon that has also occurred all over the world. Until the COVID-19 crisis, vaccination was an issue decided upon by each citizen as a matter of respect for human dignity and liberty.

2.8.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The MoH published information to the public in a dashboard website, that updates twice a day and contains accumulated figures and general data on new cases, mortality, vaccinations, COVID-19 in all the municipalities and cities, isolations, hospitalizations, the R value. The scope of the website gradually expanded, and includes now also beds capacity in the hospitals, child COVID-19 data, "Imported" cases, tests and samples, vaccination effectiveness, age and gender breakdown, reinfection and recovery, community data and more (Rosen et al., 2021).

Additional information and raw data for researchers became available, and includes information on the severe cases and hospitalization, and GIS information. This data became accessible to allow external researchers to perform their own studies based on the official data.

Political and health care leaders also communicated a vision of how widespread vaccine uptake would enable a return to normalcy within the foreseeable future.

Israeli public health experts played two very important roles in addressing the confusion created in early February 2021 by continued high infection rates despite growing levels of vaccination coverage. First, they immediately provided plausible explanations for the paradox. Second, they subsequently provided early, real world evidence that the vaccination program was having a demonstrable, population-level, positive impact in Israel. The explanations for the paradox included the arrival in Israel of a new, highly infectious strain (B.1.1.7, the UK variant), the necessity of a second vaccine dose to reach maximal immunity, and the lag time between vaccination and the full impact on immunity.

Attempts to ostracize and label anyone who criticized the official vaccination policy or refused to be vaccinated as an opponent or an outcast helped create a spiral of silence in society. The spiral of silence theory claims that when people notice that a group shares their personal opinion, they are more inclined to be confident and outward in expressing themselves. On the other hand, if people see that their opinion is not popular, they are more likely to be reserved and silent. In Israel, this spiral of silence spilled over into many areas, for example among doctors who noted that the system was pressing them to "toe the line" and was intolerant of any expressions of hesitancy.

2.8.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

The vaccine access and vaccine hesitancy challenges were addressed via a mix of messaging, incentives, and extensions to the initial vaccine delivery system. Many of the measures addressed the general population, while others targeted subgroups.

One of the main efforts undertaken to promote uptake and address vaccine hesitancy among young adults consisted of targeted messaging that highlighted expert opinion on vaccine safety. This included

messages about vaccine safety in general, messages about the lack of a scientific basis to claims about long-term risks or about risks to fertility, and messages about the limited risks for pregnant women (Rosen et al., 2021).

In addition, Israel invested significant efforts in communicating the message that, while the risk of mortality and severe morbidity from COVID-19 is particularly great among the elderly, the disease also has substantial risks for all age groups, including young adults. The messaging included systematic data and case reports of young people who had died or become seriously ill after contracting COVID-19. Over time, evidence accumulated that vaccinations of pregnant women were safe and did not have reproduction-related side effects. This information was added to the messaging (Rosen et al., 2021).

Tailored messaging:

While the uptake of vaccines among ultra-Orthodox Jews was slower than among the general population, it did not face substantial resistance. This contrasts sharply with the resistance by some sects of ultra-Orthodox Jews to physical distancing, school closures, and rules limiting the sizes of weddings, funerals, and prayer gatherings – particularly during the first wave of the pandemic. This general openness to vaccinations made it possible for the agencies and professionals involved in promoting vaccinations to rely almost exclusively on encouragement and facilitation, as opposed to more confrontational approaches (Rosen et al., 2021).

Messaging efforts increasingly made use of communication media specific to the ultra-Orthodox Jewish population, including magazines, newsletters, recorded phone messages, and billboard posters. These were written using messages, wording, and language (i.e., Yiddish in addition to Hebrew) tailored to the community. For example, many of the communications cited relevant Biblical verses, such as “Take good care of your life” (Deuteronomy 4:15) and “Do not stand idly by when your colleague is at risk” (Leviticus 19:16).

The messages themselves were also tailored to the Israeli Arab population and culture. For example, one of the health plans broadcast a clip of a woman wearing a traditional headscarf saying that it is permissible to get vaccinated during the Ramadan fast. In addition, some of the exhortations to get vaccinated cited traditional Arab proverbs on the importance of honouring the elders of the community.

Alongside framing the COVID-19 vaccination as the ultimate solution, both the MOH and the newscasts used the fear appeal strategy. This strategy involves conveying persuasive messages that seek to arouse fear through threats of impending danger or harm, thus changing the way people behave. Throughout the vaccination campaign, the newscasts stressed the high morbidity and mortality rates from COVID-19.

The communication started with the Israeli-French community, but very quickly the Task Force spread its activities in English, toward the international scientific community, and to a lesser extent, in Hebrew, where the need was already addressed by the Ministry of Health, the four health maintenance organisation (HMO), and associations such as Midaat, a Vaccine Safety Net member.

Within a year, the Task Force set up: 40+ webinars for healthcare professionals and professional associations, for the public, for high schools, or institutions, but also for experts in Pharmacovigilance, TV and radio interviews, Questions and answers in lay language, Scientific articles, General press review, twice a week through WhatsApp groups, Scientific literature review through WhatsApp

groups, Hotline: answering questions from health-care professionals and public (Fermont, Livneh & Benhamou, 2022).

2.8.4 Strategies: Methods used

Analysis of the reasons for slow vaccine uptake:

Within the first weeks of the vaccination campaign, it became apparent to the professionals working at the Arab population task force that vaccine uptake among Israeli Arabs was substantially slower than in the general population. The task force quickly undertook an analysis of the causes of the relatively low uptake and concluded that it was multi-factorial, and included barriers to access, insufficient appreciation of vaccination benefits, and exaggerated fears of vaccine risks. The task force's earlier work for and with the Israeli Arab population helped it complete this analysis quickly and effectively, as it had already built a team of dedicated experts and channels of communication with leaders of the Arab population. This, in turn, helped it to promptly develop and implement appropriate interventions.

The ultra-Orthodox task force undertook a similar analysis regarding its target population and acted accordingly (Rosen et al., 2021).

Partnering with community leaders:

Even before the vaccine had been approved for use by the Ministry of Health, the ultra-Orthodox task force solicited letters of support from rabbinic leaders encouraging vaccination, and rabbinic and communal leaders were recruited to encourage compliance throughout the vaccination campaign. In addition, senior physicians who had close ties to ultra-Orthodox Jewish communities (and who were highly respected by them) were enlisted to counter concerns about vaccine safety, and family physicians were mobilized to do vaccine promotion outreach among their patients. The task force brought together trusted physicians and rabbinic leaders to address the concern about possible side-effects on fertility, which were widespread particularly among young ultra-Orthodox women. These outreach efforts on the part of physicians built on the mainstream ultra-Orthodox community's long-standing acceptance of modern medicine and its respect for physicians. They were particularly important in dispelling concerns about fertility risks.

Many ultra-Orthodox Jews live in homogenous municipalities. Their mayors were successfully included in vaccination campaigns – both to call upon their residents to get vaccinated, and to provide practical logistical support (Rosen et al., 2021).

Similarly, many Muslim religious leaders, Arab physicians, and Arab soccer stars responded to requests from Magen Israel that they actively and publicly encourage Israeli Arabs to get vaccinated. Mayors and other leaders of Arab municipalities also spoke out in favour of vaccination and took concrete steps to make it easier for residents of their municipalities to reach vaccination sites. Moreover, Magen Israel learned to respond promptly and effectively to requests from municipal leaders to cooperate with them on promoting vaccination uptake. The Israel Defence Forces' Home Front Command also contributed to these cooperative efforts.

During recent disease outbreaks, health organizations and the media appear to have reinforced their apocalyptic narrative by using strategies of intimidation to make the public comply with instructions and guidelines.

Both the MOH and the news coverage used the attribution of responsibility frame, which is defined as a way of attributing responsibility for a cause or solution to either the government or to an individual or group. In this research results, this framing found expression in attributing responsibility for spreading the virus to what was referred to as “the group of unvaccinated people in Israel”.

The news often distinguished between vaccinated and unvaccinated groups, though the definition of vaccination status varied. That is, someone in the unvaccinated group may have received both the first and second dose but was still assigned to the “unvaccinated” group on the news. This strategy was designed to show that people from the “unvaccinated” group who were hospitalized placed a burden on the entire medical system.

One of the issues that played a key role in the MoH strategy was the fundamental role of primary health care nurses and physicians in promoting vaccination and targeting vaccination hesitancy. As all Israelis have a medical insurance (through 4 HMO) and are associated to a primary health care physician (known as the “family doctor”), those links were used, understanding the personal acquaintance. Dedicated webinars and information sessions were organized, and the primary health care physicians had to report on their talks with their unvaccinated patients.

Dedicated information sessions were also organized for community leaders, as religious teachers.

2.8.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

There was some anti-vax messaging and other forms of misinformation in the ultra-Orthodox communities, some of it originating with charismatic rabbis, particularly during the early weeks of the vaccination campaign. These messages were spread largely through flyers placed in mailboxes and posters pasted on billboards – both of which are typical and effective ways of spreading messages in ultra-Orthodox communities. However, the anti-vax messaging was relatively limited in scope, duration, and influence, in part due to effective responses on the part of local authorities and the Israel Defence Forces’ (IDF) home front command (Rosen et al., 2021).

Anti-vax messaging and misinformation was more widespread in the Arabic-language social media, which significantly exaggerated vaccine risks (particularly regarding fertility) and which promoted distrust of government. The vaccine promoting messaging – emphasizing vaccine efficacy and safety - was done via Arabic-language traditional media and social media, and via individual outreach by the health plans and Arab physicians. Muslim religious leaders and various voluntary organizations (such as the Association of Arab Physicians in the Negev) also played an important role in the messaging effort.

In a study on the effectiveness of a small size, private communication initiative by the Israeli Chapter of the International Society of Pharmacovigilance (ISOP), the private campaign is mentioned, starting early December 2020, just before the vaccination started. A long but didactic presentation was attended by 200 people and was followed by so many questions that it triggered the decision to launch a large information campaign. For doing so, within a month a Task Force was gathered in January 2021, with 20 volunteers, physicians, pharmacists, and scientists, their fields of expertise cover: pharmacovigilance, pharmaco-epidemiology, virology, laboratory, medicine, immunohematology, molecular biology, molecular genetics, veterinary, cardiac paediatric, intensive care, cardiovascular and thoracic surgery, neuro-sciences, general practitioners, engineers, webmasters, translators, social media, press review, and administration. The Task Force’s mission was to provide healthcare

professionals and the public with evidence-based information on COVID vaccines and COVID-19, and to fight back against infodemic.

Anti-vaccers became very violent in their messages and threats against senior health care officials (to the point that a bodyguard was appointed to the director of public health services), which caused a MoH campaign to back up the health care professionals, and call for legal intervention, to protect them. A heated discussion on the boundaries of the public discussion took place.

2.9 Italy

2.9.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

With regards to the period from March 2021 to September 2022, the major change with the past waves was the appointment of Mario Draghi as President of the Council of Ministers (PCM). To be precise, after the collapse of the government led by Giuseppe Conte in January 2021, Mario Draghi was conferred the appointment to build a new government by Sergio Mattarella, the President of the Republic. The formal acceptance of this task occurred in February 2021. Fabrizio Curcio replaced Angelo Borrelli as the new Head of the Civil Protection and the Army General Francesco Paolo Figliuolo became the new Extraordinary Commissioner for the COVID-19 Emergency after Domenico Arcuri. This change in the Italian government structure led to a series of modifications both in the people responsible for developing the communication strategies, plans, practices and in the communication organization itself, with different communication approaches adopted by the two Presidents of the Council of Ministers over the COVID-19 pandemic: “Conte’s emotional and massive communication” versus “Draghi’s informative and discreet style of communication” (Amoretti, Fittipaldi, and Santaniello, 2021).

2.9.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

Hence, to investigate the changes in the government attitude requires backing up a brief examination of the past communication strategy to be compared with the newly adopted measures. Overall, we can identify three major communication channels over the first wave (February-May 2020):

- press conferences organised by the PCM and live broadcasted through traditional and social media to inform about the containment of the epidemic (e.g., state of emergency, controls at regional borders, etc.);
- communication campaigns realised by the Presidency of the Council of Ministers to promote public awareness about the pandemic and encourage behaviours directed to reduce the contagion risk;
- daily (up to May 2020) and weekly (since May 2020 and afterwards) press conferences organised by the Civil Protection, the Ministry of Health, the Italian National Institute of Health (ISS) and the Technical Scientific Committee (CTS) to show the main data on the pandemic trend (the Ministry of Health and the Civic Protection also provided daily data on the pandemic trend on a dedicated website).

As noted in Ventura (2022), Giuseppe Conte organised thirty press conferences from late January to December 2020 to manage the pandemic, gave fifty-one interviews for the main national newspapers, while using Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter to officially communicate the new measures; Mario

Draghi, instead, did not have any social media account, held ten press conferences from March to November 2021 and did not release any press interviews over 2021.

As for the communication campaigns, the most important message transmitted by the government from March 2021 concerned the importance of vaccination of the population as a whole to defeat the pandemic. In particular, the Army General Francesco Paolo Figliuolo – the new Extraordinary Commissioner for the COVID-19 Emergency up to March 31st 2022 since on 1 April 2022, the Army General Tommaso Petroni became Director of the Unit for the Completion of the Vaccination Campaign – was given the task to rearrange and carry out the vaccination campaign. On 13th March 2021, The Extraordinary Commissioner Plan was launched in order to perform the national vaccination campaign through three main operational tracks, i.e., provision and supply, continuing monitoring, and widespread distribution.

In terms of communication about the pandemic and the vaccination campaign by public health stakeholders during the period March 2021 – September 2022, a brief analysis of press, newspapers, social media as well as informal conversations with doctors and health practitioners show both a decrease in the frequency of the “messages” spread and a change in the type of transmitted information. A particular focus was now towards vaccinations, in contrast to the prior attention on the virus itself and contagion reports.

For instance, as for the Italian regions, some works about the epidemic and the referring communication (such as Ducci, 2021; and Fissi, Gori, and Romolini, 2022) and other studies available on AGENAS (National Agency for Regional Health Services) website and recently published, still concern the first phases of the pandemic or just a brief sub-period of the last year and a half, and do focus on communication strategies instead of on the change in the communication approach applied by these and similar health stakeholders.

2.9.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

Like for the case of public health stakeholders, the investigation of the evolution of the communication strategies and practices by organizations is difficult to carry out because there are no reports and/or specific studies yet showing whether there were (or not) modifications in their approach over the last one year and a half. Hence, a trend can be traced by analysing the scarcity of information and news about e.g., non-governmental organizations (NGOs) dealing with the pandemic and vaccination. It seems that over the early phases of the pandemic, information about the help and the engagement of such organizations was more likely to appear on the press and/or on the web.

For instance, the webpage of AOI-International Cooperation and Solidarity, in the section “Dicono di noi”, that is “They say about us”, presents a series of National newspapers dealing with the engagement of solidarity, cooperation, and international volunteering organizations in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and all the shown articles date back the year 2020.

Another case of interest is Emergency: the dedicated webpage presents a series of projects launched since May 2020 in order to cope with the COVID-19 pandemic and to specifically help the population segment hit by the social and economic crisis due to the health emergency. The same organization explains how the aims of the mission “Nessuno escluso”, that is “Nobody left out”, realised in Milan, Rome, Piacenza, Naples, Catanzaro, Catania, Varese, changed the pandemic trend as following: while at the beginning, it pointed at food aid, since December 2021, it included a social intervention. Given the improvement in the contagion situation, the project ceased its activity in Rome, Catanzaro,

Catania, Piacenza and Varese, whereas it is still active in Milan. In the same town, in January 2022, due to the rise in the contagions number, Emergency joined again (the first phase of the mission dates back March 2020) the municipality in the project “Milano aiuta”, that is “Milan helps”, to help isolated, elderly, or immunosuppressed people.

The webpage of Fondazione Sodalitas as well shows how non-profit organizations are involved in helping fragile people hit by the COVID-19 pandemic, but no data about the start of the several projects and organizations listed are available. Carrying out an analysis of the potential changes in their communicated aims and missions is therefore difficult.

2.9.4 Strategies: Methods used

The following communication campaigns were launched:

- “Vaccini sui luoghi di lavoro. Uniti, per la ripresa in sicurezza”, that is, “Vaccinations on the workplaces. All together to a safe recovery”. The campaign was promoted in June 2021 by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies and the target population included workers, companies, citizens, and the public opinion. The major aims were:
 - informing about the opportunities for workers and companies to access vaccination in the workplace;
 - emphasising the importance of collaboration in terms of agreement between the government and the social parts to make vaccination points available at work;
 - and promoting the shared goal of recovery after the pandemic.

The advertisement was transmitted on RAI (Radiotelevisione Italiana) tv and radio channels and on Ministry social media.

- “Riprendiamoci il gusto del futuro”, that is “Let’s take back the taste of the future”, is the communication campaign launched in June 2021 by the Presidency of the Council of Ministers and produced by the Information and Publishing Department. It pointed to raise awareness on the need to get vaccinated against the COVID-19 virus. The campaign, broadcasted on both social and traditional media, involved general residents and celebrities.
- “Facciamolo per noi”, that is “Let’s do it for ourselves”, was a communication campaign produced by the Information and Publishing Department where testimonials – in November 2021, famous people, doctors, and researchers were involved in the referring advertisements – promoted the vaccination against the COVID-19 virus as well as specific behavioural measures as needed to cope with the pandemic. The target population were all citizens. The spots were broadcasted on RAI tv, on other tv channels, on the web and on social media.
- “Facciamolo per noi (dicembre 2021)”, that is “Let’s do it for ourselves (December 2021)”, produced by the Information and Publishing Department of the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, was launched in December 2021 as an evolution of the previous communication campaign. It involved famous people, doctors and scientists and aimed at promoting the vaccination recall as well as the opportunity of vaccination for children aged 5-11. The advertisement was transmitted on RAI tv, on other tv channels, on the web and on social media.
- In July 2022, the communication campaign to promote the second booster dose, i.e., the fourth vaccine dose, for people aged 60 and over and for fragile persons was launched by the Ministry of Health. The testimonial was the Nobel Prize Giorgio Parisi, and the spot was broadcasted on RAI tv and radio, on the web and on social media.

Also, as done before by the Ministry of Health for data on the pandemic trend (i.e., about new contagions, recoveries, and deaths), that are still weekly updated, information on vaccination has been made available online by the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, the Unit for the Completion of the Vaccination Campaign, and the Ministry of Health. In particular, daily data on total administrations, on those to children aged 5-11, on first and second booster doses, as well as on weekly administration trend are summarised and shown on a dedicated webpage, while the open data source has been available online for download since 2021 thanks to the Presidency of the Council of Ministers and the Extraordinary Commissioner for the COVID-19 Emergency.

2.9.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

n/a

2.10 Portugal

2.10.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

Overall, government organisations continued without developing a COVID-19 communication plan. Preparedness and response plans and implementation of measures against COVID-19 (including communication actions) continued to be assigned to the Health Authorities.

Communication is considered a key competence for effective leadership and the most effective organisations use communication as a strategy to support management. The communication teams of health organisations are responsible for supporting communication in its different aspects (institutional, health, crisis and risk, public health emergencies), and this function is transversal to all activities in their various phases (planning, development, implementation, and evaluation). However, leadership in health organisations in Portugal sometimes follows a very hierarchical model that does not truly favour communication, seeing it only as a technical support activity, without recognising its strategic role in supporting management. Communication professionals are often not involved from the beginning of the processes and are usually only called 'to the table' when it is necessary to communicate with the outside. Even so, there is a lack of actual application of the recommendations given by such experts due to several reasons.

In February 2021, the director-general of Health, dr. Graça Freitas justifies her "disappearance" with new communication strategy: "The Director-General of Health does not need to appear. The Director-General of Health needs to work. And this was a phase in which, from the communication point of view, other options were taken. And I continue to work exactly as I have always worked. Communication has had many forms of existence. This is just one of them, and so here I am to work as I have always worked around vaccination". Moreover, when asked about the resignation of the coordinator of the Vaccination Task force (at the time, Dr. Francisco Ramos), the director-general of Health declined to comment, but made a point of praising the career of Dr. Francisco Ramos. "It was a decision taken by Dr. Francisco Ramos, in a context that we all know. It is not my place to comment on his departure from the Task force."

In early March 2021, Vice Admiral Gouveia e Melo was appointed the new coordinator of the COVID-19 Vaccination Plan and his work was much appreciated. The Admiral was even awarded by the President of the Portuguese Republic due to his work success in reaching high vaccination coverage nationally.

In March 2021, several national newspapers reported that the Government had appointed a Task force of behavioural scientists to advise the Government until the end of 2021, conducting studies and presenting documents. However, the members of the team were not remunerated. Moreover, the Shared Services of the Ministry of Health supported the technical group and the articulation with the Government was made through Tiago Antunes, deputy secretary of state to the prime minister.

Already in the dispatch signed by Marta Temido it is stated that one of the objectives is that people maintain the "behaviours recommended as most effective in each moment and social context, in the response to the pandemic and in the moments that will follow". The "behavioural changes can only be achieved with the structured application of behavioural science", through which it is possible to "identify, explain, predict, and intervene on behaviours" (Expresso, 2021).

The immunisation strategy for the autumn-winter period was presented by the heads of the National Medicines Authority (Infarmed), the Directorate-General for Health (DGS), and the Nucleus for Coordination of Support to the Ministry of Health (NCAMS) which is also responsible for the logistics of vaccination.

There were several moments when the President of the Republic and the Prime Minister, both held citizens responsible for not spreading the virus, such as in March 2021 President of the Portuguese Republic, Marcelo, stated that the responsibility lied mainly with the Portuguese people and asked for discipline (Diário de Notícias, 2021): "The responsibility remains where it has always been: in the hands of the Portuguese people. The responsibility is not only in the hands of the President of the Republic, the Assembly of the Republic, or the Government. It is, above all, in the hands of the Portuguese people", considered Marcelo Rebelo de Sousa, in Lisbon (Diário Notícias, 2021). In September 2021, this view was reinforced by the prime minister, António Costa, stating that the pandemic was not over and asking for individual accountability (RTP Notícias, 2021). Moreover, in December 2021, they both also praised the successful behaviour of non-transmissibility as a "national unity effort" in the fight against the pandemic (Público, 2021), thanking the "true voluntary quarantine of the Portuguese", emphasizing the "civism, maturity, understanding, solidarity, and respect for others" (SAPO 24, 2021): "What unites us is much more important than that which could divide us. And we will win", said the president (Sapo Echo, 2021).

The Prime Minister also stated that: "As Mr. President of the Republic often says, the Portuguese are exceptional, and once again they have proved to be exceptional. The cohesion between The Prime Minister and the President in having "a common vision" on "the institutional role of the different sovereign bodies" and the "sense of solidarity" between them (Público, 2021).

According to data published by the website Acta médica, in the context of the pandemic of COVID-19, only two of the 68 members of the response Taskforce created by the Directorate General of Health (DGS), are specialists in the area of communication. This being a long-standing and cultural problem in the leadership of organisations. Despite the apparent growth in the recognition of communication in health institutions in Portugal, as evidenced by the hiring of professionals in this area for the first time from 2018 onwards, of a Communication and Public Relations Division in the Directorate-General for Health, there is still a lack of knowledge about its strategic potential.

For the school year of 2021/2022, the DGS, the SNS, and Portuguese Republic created a Referential for schools concerning several measures and guidelines, including a chapter on "communication and coordination with partners".

There hasn't been changes regarding risk communication for public health on COVID-19 from organisations such as The Portuguese Psychologists Association (OPP), which as mentioned in the previous report D7.1 provided information and strategies for decision makers and social mobilizers. Some other recognised public organisations took actions regarding communication dissemination:

- *The Social Sciences Institute* (ICS) also made a crisis communication guide, and a Crisis Communication Management Office of ICS was created with the exclusive purpose of following the official information flows and managing communication within the institute community.
- *The Human Sciences Faculty of Lisbon* (FCH) also developed guiding principles for risk and crisis communication based on risk perception.
- *The Portuguese Medical Minute* (“Acta Médica Portuguesa”, AMP) - a scientific journal published by The Portuguese Medical Association (“Ordem dos Médicos”) – developed a guide to formulate a risk communication strategy in relation to the COVID-19 vaccines - Guidelines to Think, Develop and Implement Health Communication in Portugal -, as well as another report *The Risk Communication and Community Involvement in the COVID-19 Pandemic in Portugal*.

2.10.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

COVID-19 epidemiological situation monitoring reports are still available on the COVID-19 Ministry of Health website, as well as the red lines report - available monthly. From the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic in Portugal until today, we can find around 1600 articles on the government website. Between news, press releases and press videoconferences - both from the prime minister and the council of ministers - the government has tried to provide all the necessary information to fight COVID-19 on its website.

From January 2021 onwards, the prime minister started appearing alone in Infarmed 20 minute sessions to the population with a Portuguese sign language translator or with the President, in which only one of them spoke and the other remained silent, standing at the back, probably a strategy to demonstrate more cohesion between the power figures and improve the strength of the message.

In early March 2021, the government released a 42-minute video (press conference of the council of ministers) in which only the prime minister and a Portuguese sign language translator appear, to reveal the deconfinement plan, with data demonstrated in power-point format and in a one-way communication channel, since YouTube comment box was deactivated.

In December 2021, the prime minister admitted some failures in fighting the pandemic “We can't always get there in time” and revealed that “Yes, the measures were not always coherent, but they sought to have a rationale and the population always understood the essential of that rationale”, and that the most difficult decision to take was that of closing schools, before a full room, where in the front row was the Minister of Health, Marta Temido, the Government leader made an assessment of the measures taken during the pandemic (DN, 2022).

In May 2022, the prime minister also stated that during the last two years, the Government held 128 councils of ministers exclusively dedicated to the topic of COVID-19, made 200 resolutions, decrees and laws, and organised 85 press conferences. He confessed that the councils of ministers were always very demanding because everyone around the table shared the same doubts: “(...) we were faced with the difficulty of having to make decisions knowing that we would not have unquestionable support for those decisions”.

In all channels, commentators/experts are identified, such as: infectious diseases specialists, immunologists, public health specialists, epidemiologists, pneumologists, intensivists, directors of hospital services in relevant areas, and health statisticians. This strategy aimed to add more elements and find alternative sources of information, in order to avoid the news being restricted to official information and becoming dependent on the governmental primary sources and the commitments made to the DGS. In this context, medical experts have become major media figures and opinion leaders. In another perspective, this trend is also a corollary of the growing importance of communication and health journalism, a context in which the literature assesses the value of specialized sources for a news discourse that is more rigorous in what it reports and more enlightening for citizens (Lopes et al., 2020, p. 207).

The political communication of these interlocutors was not always the most concerted and articulated. Without a team of scientists to assist it permanently in decisions and without an official spokesperson, the government was transmitting decisions through various interlocutors: Prime Minister, Minister of Health, Director-General of Health, Secretaries of State of Health, some governors, among others (Gonçalves et al., 2021). Throughout 2020, the Director-General of Health promoted press conferences, always flanked by government officials, and it is not clear whether the meetings with journalists were technical or political. Also, the frequency oscillated between a daily rhythm and then only on some days of the week, eventually disappearing from January 2021, paradoxically at the time when the pandemic reached the most serious rates worldwide. This suggests that there was never really a well-architected communication strategy to communicate with citizens. Rather than official sources, it was journalists who had the most regularity in promoting the news of this pandemic. And if in the first wave the official sources managed to quickly control the numbers of infected and deaths, deciding quickly and communicating clearly, throughout 2020 and 2021 the hesitations on these two levels increased. And so did the severity of the disease, and according to the authors, this was not by chance (Gonçalves et al., 2021).

The results of the study by Magalhães and colleagues (2021) revealed that the SNS is the official source that most favours communication on vaccination in the digital environment in the analysed channels, through a fruitful publication of contents on its website and the continuous publication of information on online social networks. Given that the SNS corresponds to the "armed arm" of the Ministry of Health to society, this result seems expectable and an indicator of a "good communicative health" of the SNS, at a time when it was systematically put to the test. SNS was more proficient in the production and publication of contents than other national official sources. Moreover, it is the closest source to citizens and the one most attentive to the need to decentralise information.

When selecting online social networks to promote content on vaccination, the SNS, the Infarmed, and the Government all favoured Twitter. When the pandemic was decreed in Portugal, around mid-March 2020, the number of active users grew from 133,000,000 to 162,000,000 users in the last quarter of 2020, an increase of about 22% (Elfira & Indrawan, 2021). However, we know that this is not the most used social network in Portugal, being surpassed by Facebook and Instagram. As opposed to this, the DGS favoured the use of Facebook, which is not surprising, since it has 701,400 followers on Facebook and only 47,000 followers on Twitter (Magalhães et al., 2021).

The DGS favoured direct communication with citizens through online social networks, allowing to convey messages more effectively with a strong intent to induce behaviours and encourage vaccination. In fact, the results corroborate this thesis, revealing that two thirds of the posts that had a persuasive framework were published by DGS. Still, the authors suggested that the DGS may have

underused its communication capacity on Facebook, since the total number of posts published on vaccination was relatively small. Most of the content published by official sources on their websites and online social networks is of a news nature.

In addition to the fact that 65% of the content disclosed by official sources on the websites correspond to institutional news, the author's found that, on social networks, posts are often composed of informative texts accompanied by photos. There is, therefore, a news language underlying the production of the sources' contents, in the digital environment, which may derive from the long tradition of media advisory associated to the Portuguese official sources. While the journalistic style is desirable in the context of media advisory, it may not be the most appropriate when the intention is not only to inform, but also to persuade the message receivers to adopt a certain behaviour.

On the website of the Ministry of Health, a COVID-19 Resources Communication link was created where you can find images, videos, and PDF's advised to be downloaded, shared on your social networks, sent or printed and posters at workplaces and so on) with some thematic campaigns, for instance: Good practice (controlling the pandemic; stay at home; masking; terraces); Sectors of activity: (Gyms, terraces, shopping; hairdressing). Moreover, there was an updated section from Spring 2022 onwards, concerning the deconfinement plan (10 images with the general rules of the containment plan) and frequently asked questions (4 images on the rules on weddings, day centres, esplanades, gyms, and grocery shops), another section with videos on "don't let the virus in" (control the pandemic, stay at home; mask; esplanades). The material used for these images and videos was also depicted in billboards across the country, mainly in bigger cities.

In March 2020, the Government launched a website www.covid19estamoson.gov.pt/ with the aim of presenting on a single platform all relevant information about the measures to prevent and contain the new coronavirus which is still on today. An app "Stayaway COVID" was also launched, but failed for several reasons, for instance, malfunctioning of the app (not letting users know of a risk contact), improper access to users' personal data, trying to make it mandatory.

The participation of actors external to the government occurred through videos (35 personalities acted in a DGS campaign also shown on TV) and the use of the song "Juntos somos mais fortes", by the band Amor Electro - soundtrack of the posts about professionals in the fight against the virus. The government added 58.0% of the posts' tags and celebrities 52.0% (Cádima & Ferreira, 2021).

2.10.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

At a national level, the Government has frequently communicated (via news on the website) that, in coordination with local authorities, it will "remain attentive to the needs of the most vulnerable populations in the face of the pandemic, including some Roma communities, and provide the necessary measures to help these vulnerable communities".

At a local level, for instance, in 2021 the Alentejo region Health Unit created a link on its website targeted to vulnerable communities, with two topics: "Information for the Roma Community" and "Information for Migrants". In the case of Roma Community Information, there are three videos produced by the High Commission for Migrations. These videos depict several people, including Roma people, which represents an attempt of representativeness, in partnership with local associations whose work is related to helping more vulnerable communities and groups.

Regarding general information on access to the National Health Service's health care, the website of the General Directorate of Health (DGS) provides information in five languages. On a scale of greater

proximity to the public, practices have been observed in the use of Cape Verdean Creole in information posters in some health centres with a significant presence of the population speaking the language. The DGS also launched videos with prevention recommendations against COVID-19 in 11 languages, including Portuguese sign language.

There were also some national initiatives implemented locally, regarding youth volunteering to help communities in need. "To support, strengthen, and qualify the community support responses carried out by Portuguese parishes during the isolation period, the Portuguese Institute for Sport and Youth (IPDJ), in partnership with the National Association of Parishes (ANAFRE), promotes the volunteering action "Greater Support". This volunteering project counted with the participation of about 150 young volunteers, aged between 18 and 30 years old. The volunteers properly equipped and complying with safety standards, among other safety measures, provided clarification of doubts to the community and telephone and digital dissemination of health support programs.

The "CO(m)VID(a)" project was implemented in a Roma community. At least two home visits were made to the families of this community, before and after the Health Education session. The session held, as a Health Promotion strategy, was based on clarifying to the community: the disease, the vaccine and its benefits, highlighting the protection at individual and collective level (in the community); and the disadvantages of non-adherence to vaccination. The project showed that the Health Education programme contributed to increasing the level of health literacy and, consequently, to the adherence to Covid-19 vaccination. The intervention of the community nurse promoted positive change in this community. The results of the project were shared with other community nurses, and it is expected that it will be implemented in other Roma and ethnic communities (Frazão et al., 2022).

Alongside with the DGS, CoronaKids is a playful-pedagogical website created by a publishing company called "Ideias com História" with the aim of informing children about COVID-19. News every day, useful information about COVID-19, curiosities, games, videos, and many activities.

2.10.4 Strategies: Methods used

In 2022, in an interview to a researcher in the areas of television information and health communication, Felisbela Lopes, stated that a "simple and effective" communication was a concern since the first day of activities when we adopted as a communication strategy that all the proposals were presented, first hand, in Infarmed meetings since these were the stronger option to communication at the right moment.

It is also important to separate two different times: that of the specialists' recommendations and that of the political decision. For this reason, the media intervention of the group of experts was usually limited to the interval between the Infarmed meeting and the following Council of Ministers meeting.

"From the moment the group spokesperson [Raquel Duarte] spoke at Infarmed, I would send the media all the material supporting the proposals and Raquel would be available for interviews where she would explain the recommended measures. After the meeting of the Council of Ministers we distanced ourselves, because that was the time for political decisions, and we could not create entropies. It doesn't mean that we didn't have anything to say about the political decisions taken - but at the time, this would only create noise" – as Felisbela Lopes sums up.

Raquel Duarte, former Secretary of State for Health stated that despite being a "very heterogeneous" group, comprising specialists from different areas of Health, but also mathematics and communication, these experts did not work alone:

"We consulted a number of specialists from other areas, we used several tools to assess the population's perceptions, and that helped a lot in the decision-making process. The analyses made always had a much broader spectrum than the mere epidemiological parameters and their potential direct danger to people's health. We always analysed the pandemic and the consequences of the proposed measures in all its dimensions, from the impact on health to the impact on the lives of families, to social and economic aspects. The idea was always to try to find a point of balance for the recommendations made".

Moreover, they both guarantee that despite the enormous pressure, from the most diverse sectors, that boiled over in the media universe throughout the process, sometimes demanding more freedom and sometimes advising greater prudence; and that they always felt "a lot of independence" in their work, but also "an enormous sense of responsibility".

Felisbela Lopes highlighted that the task-force mission was faced with a spirit of public service, pro-bono, in parallel with the professional activities of each one, adding that communication between the various experts was done remotely, in chats and virtual meetings. Raquel Duarte also highlights the importance of working together as one of the most valid lessons that this pandemic leaves for the future, and more importantly "a critical look at what was done is fundamental, knowing that there were some not so good aspects on which it is necessary to act in order to organise better future answers to this or other pandemics, and that the most negative lesson is our incapacity, at a global level, to guarantee equity in the access to care and vaccines" (Diário de Notícias, 2022).

2.10.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

Since the beginning of the pandemic there has been some important strategic developments. Polygraph and Observador, the two main national fact-checkers, appear in prime-time news slots, on SIC and TVI channels. The private television broadcaster SIC launched Portugal's first private streaming service, OPTO, while the public broadcaster, RTP, invested considerable resources in expanding its existing free streaming service, RTPToque. Diário de Notícias, one of Portugal's oldest newspapers returned to daily print edition, after abandoning it in June 2018 for a seminal print edition alongside a daily digital-only presence. From March 2020 to nowadays, the Polygraph and the DGS established a partnership against "fake news". These entities decided to ally themselves in the fight against misinformation about COVID-19. The partnership, consists of identifying, assessing, and classifying the information that is being publicly shared on a topic that is already a global case study in terms of misinformation (DGS, 2020).

Research by DN and MediaLab of ISCTE Disinformation does not seem to have played a very relevant role regarding the "Coronavirus" topic in Portugal. The examples that do exist of disinformation happen mostly on Facebook pages (and less in groups) and tend to be based on international disinformation narratives about the virus, imported from the USA. However, although disinformation per se is not detectable, within the Facebook groups we monitored there is a significant volume of posts of political spin, seeking to attribute to the Portuguese political authorities the responsibility for the failures in the prevention or treatment of the epidemic that are allegedly pointed out. On YouTube

there are many international videos on the topic, some with narratives of doubtful credibility, but in general they are of little relevance in Portugal.

In August 2020, the OPP had already released a report on "Disinformation, fake news and pandemic covid-19 the subject cognitive processes and the role of psychologists".

It seems that most of the actions aimed at curbing disinformation, were taken before March 2021.

2.11 Romania

2.11.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

By the end of 2020, the Romanian Government adopted the Vaccination against COVID-19 Strategy, which included also some specificity related to the communication strategy. The National Committee for the Coordination of Activities on Vaccination against COVID-19 carried out the organization and coordination of activities within the vaccination process. It was an inter-ministry body, without legal personality, subordinate to the General Secretariat of the Government and under the coordination of the Prime Minister.

The development of the communication strategy to promote vaccination at the level of the target groups was focused on the following types of interventions, without being limited to them:

- Analysis of the vaccination determine factors and of the context and influences
- Create a unique information platform, both for the public and the medical staff
- Implement a communication, information, and education campaign
- Provide on time information about vaccination and COVID-19 to the public, through hotline and other digital means.

In the strategy document it was also mentioned "Information and communication campaigns will be carried out by involving representatives of professional associations, patient associations, personalities from the cultural and educational environment, representatives of civil society, respecting the principles of transparency and correct, factual and complete information, and the public".

The structure of the national committee for the coordination of activities regarding vaccination against SARS-CoV-2.

- The General Secretariat of the Government
- Ministry of Health
- National Institute for Public Health
- National Medicines and Medical Devices Agency
- Ministry of National Defence
- Ministry of Internal Affairs
- Ministry of Public Works, Development and Administration
- National Agency for Public Procurement
- College of Doctors from Romania
- Profile professional organizations

The president of the Committee became a military doctor (Valeriu Gheorghita) and he was the one communicating all the information on the vaccination campaign and COVID-19 situation. The activities of the committee were organised on three major components:

- public communication and information;
- logistics;
- medical assistance – vaccination and monitoring of vaccines side effects.

The information of the population, mass media and medical personnel was one of the main activities of this committee. The committee functioned in this way and communicated from early 2021 until June 2022, when the government issued a decision where the organization and coordination of the activities within the vaccination process is carried out by the Ministry Health, through the specialized departments and the National Institute of Public Health, with a specialized unit from its subordination.

The Ministry of Health (MOH) was responsible for:

- Carrying out information and communication campaigns regarding vaccination against COVID-19 for the medical personnel and the general population;
- Ensuring the communication with the population and mass media regarding the evolution of the vaccination situation and measures taken to coordinate the vaccination activity;
- Ensuring, in collaboration with the INSP (National Institute for Public Health), the continuity of the administration, development and maintenance of the social media instruments that were used during the vaccination campaign against COVID-19;
- Administering and ensuring, in collaboration with STS, the development and maintenance of the National Platform of information on vaccination against COVID-19, <https://vaccinare-covid.gov.ro/>.

The main communicator was dr. Valeriu Gheorghita who had weekly appearances on public channels. In May 2021, a decrease in the vaccination process was registered and the National Committee came with a new concept “The town vaccinates the village”. Gheorghita stated for the national media: "I don't think it's an inhibition of appetite, as far as we know, it was estimated from the beginning that about a third of people were determined to get vaccinated, a third are hesitant and a third don't want to, I think we're now reaching the hesitant population segment.”.

NGOs in Romania and the International organisations contributed to the information / education campaign against COVID and promotion of vaccination. The element of novelty for the national context was the mental health topic that was introduced and analysed. The Romanian Red Cross offered its support to the National Committee for the Coordination of Activities on Vaccination against COVID 19 and for the implementation of the communication campaign at local level, especially in the rural areas. Volunteers were trained and materials were drafted to be delivered door to door to the population in the villages.

2.11.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The web platform #RoVaccinare.ro was created and it is the main information source regarding COVID-19 vaccination in Romania. It contains information about the vaccination process, vaccines, statistics, news, answers to asked questions and it is developed and administrated by the Special Communication Service under the Romanian Government. <https://vaccinare-covid.gov.ro/>. A Facebook page was also created, linked to the national vaccination platform <https://www.facebook.com/ROVaccinare>.

Data about the vaccination steps were presented on the main media channels, taken from the official national platform. Another official information platform that is also functioning <https://covid19.stirioficiale.ro/informatii> - a pro-bono project carried out by Code for Romania volunteers, an independent non-governmental organization, politically unaffiliated and apolitical. The

pro-bono project is carried out within the Code for Romania Task Force in partnership with the Government of Romania through the Authority for Digitization of Romania and the Department for Emergency Situations.

At the level of the institutions there is not a structured written regulation regarding communication channels and tools to ensure public consultation. They stated that they did not consider it necessary to consult the general population, arguing that citizens do not have decision-making power, nor do they represent health professionals. At the level of medical practices, no structured communication tools for providing feedback are made available. The results of the group interviews showed that they receive feedback from patients during office consultations. During the pandemic, feedback is mainly provided through telephone communication and online through messages in the WhatsApp application or on the Facebook social media platform. All DSP representatives confirmed increased access to the institution's web page by the general population, but the identification and access monitoring was not among the activities carried out within the institution.

Most DSP representatives stated that there is a health promotion department, with budgeted activities, such as the development of leaflets, brochures, infographics, posters, or video materials and of other health promotion materials, these being printed and distributed among the population, and then revised as many times as the department's budget allows. Most of them stated that they have received health promotion materials from institutions such as: the Ministry of Health, the National Institute of Public Health, the Department for Emergency Situations, the National Coordinating Committee of the Activities on Vaccination against COVID-19 or UNICEF.

Promotional materials from the pandemic period were displayed at various points of interest for the population, such as shops or crowded spaces, and were distributed to the population through community health workers or health mediators. However, most DSP representatives did not believe that the materials received were sufficient to manage the COVID-19 pandemic.

GPs reported that they routinely use health promotion materials such as leaflets, brochures, posters, or videos. Some of these materials are made by the National Society of Family Medicine, later printed, displayed and distributed by doctors in the offices, but also on social networks (e.g., Facebook).

2.11.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

Against the background of the health crisis caused by COVID-19, all respondents (DSP representatives and family doctors) reported the adoption of new technological communication channels. For vulnerable communities, however, the DSP representatives highlighted that the information was transmitted more effectively through community nurses and health mediators.

2.11.4 Strategies: Methods used

Considering the importance of public communication, transparency of information and strengthening of trust in coordinated efforts at each level of the health system, the UNICEF Representation in Romania, in collaboration with the Department of Public Health, the Faculty of Political, Administrative, and other Sciences of Communication from Babeş Bolyai University Cluj-Napoca conducted a research study in the period December 2020 — June 2021. The aim of the research was to identify and describe the communication, consultation and feedback mechanisms between the health authorities and the population, during the COVID-19 pandemic. Mixed research methods were used: qualitative - interviews with representatives Directorates of Public Health (DSP) and group

interviews with family doctors - and quantitative – questionnaire addressed to parents or guardians of children under 18 years of age.

The results show that there is no written strategy or operational plan for ensuring communication, consultation, or feedback from the population. Most respondents to the questionnaire (76.7%) stated that they did not communicate until present with DSPs, neither before the COVID-19 pandemic, nor during it (The free and unrestricted access of any person in Romania to information of public interest, defined as such by Law 544/2001, constitutes one of the fundamental principles of relations between individuals and public authorities).

GPs mentioned the low quality of communication with DSPs both before the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as during it (especially during the state of emergency). Most of them reported poor communication with other health authorities, such as The Ministry of Health, stating that the information regarding the legislative changes, procedure or those related to measures to prevent the transmission of the SARS-CoV-2 virus were not received in a timely manner, which made it difficult to effectively inform patients.

Both family doctors and DSP representatives signalled the need to develop a standardized communication tool, through which family doctors can forward their feedback to the DSP.

2.11.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

The main barrier indicated by family doctors in communicating with patients was the abundance of false information and the lack of medical staff. The majority pointed out the misinformation of the population by the mass media.

Misinformation and disinformation are phenomena that are present when talking about the COVID-19 pandemic in Romania. Some disinformation narratives regarding the COVID-19 pandemic caught on better in Romania than in other parts, because they folded on some older wounds present in Romanian society (Report on disinformation in the digital space, by the Eurocommunicare Association and coordinated by Alina Bârgăoanu, an expert in disinformation).

The main conclusion of the report is that, from the point of view of the infodemic, the Romanian online space was perfectly connected with the global one, being attacked by the same waves of disinformation that fact-checking organizations from all over the world have documented ("manufactured virus", "the introduction of mandatory vaccination", "microchipping of the population", "the COVID masquerade", "the COVID dictatorship") as it is presented in the report entitled "Covid-19 Infodemic in Romania".

The team that produced the report analysed 82 sources that circulated false information or toxic narratives about the pandemic, as well as 150 such materials from the online environment, between March and October 2020. It also measured their popularity on Facebook, using CrowdTangle, to determine which were the most successful.

For example, the conspiracy narrative that was most successful on Romanian Facebook says that "during the Spanish Flu, only vaccinated people died." It was published by the ortodoxinfo.ro website (closed by the authorities during the state of emergency, because it propagates fake news, but which immediately moved to another server) and reached over 4 million users, of which almost 40,000 have interacted with it.

In second place in terms of popularity is the false information that COVID-19 can be cured with Propolis, an article published by the website melidava.ro and which reached more than 1.6 million Facebook users, according to the cited report.

The Romanian digital space has added its own "local touches" to the great disinformation it has faithfully imported from around the world. The "toxic" narratives about how the pandemic is actually a "generated crisis, a masquerade, a cover-up or a plot behind the logic of the global elite or corruption" have been coupled with some local breaches in the Romanian collective mentality, explains for Europe Releases university lecturer doctor Flavia Durach, from the Eurocommunication Association.

A first loophole exploited by disinformation is distrust in the medical system: "Older discussions about the state of the health system were conducted in a deeply emotional note, starting from the tragedy in the Colectiv club. Distrust of the health care system exploded during this period and led to greater persuasion of toxic narratives surrounding this distrust. They got on better with us, because they already fit in with this mistrust", says Flavia Durach.

The second is the "semi-conspiratorial philosophy of life in which the state tries to steal the freedom of the citizen" and which in Romania has been coupled with "a chronic mistrust of the authorities".

"Eastern European states, and Romania in particular, are champions of mistrust in authorities - Government, Parliament. This is another local form - that the government wants us bad", explains Flavia Durach, for Free Europe.

The third Romanian peculiarity of the "infodemic" behind the COVID-19 pandemic concerns the church. "We are witnessing the confrontation between the two irreconcilable positions - supporting the church, respectively the more decisive, more brutal secularization of the state. And then part of the narratives came along this Orthodox vein, of pride in being Orthodox and the idea that the church is under threat," says Flavia Durach.

The success themes in Romania for disinformation regarding Covid-19 in the digital environment, due to the Covid-19 pandemic were the following nine:

- "Plandemic. Masquerade"
- "a simple virus"
- "The Manufactured Virus"
- "No Muzzle"
- "Bill Gates - the figure of the "occult" and the Big Pharma industry"
- "Dictatorship and the New World Order"
- "Elite corruption and mistrust of authorities"
- "5G is making us sick with COVID-19"
- "Miracle Treatments and Remedies"

Fortunately, in Romania there are already several initiatives from civil society and academia to expose and dismantle disinformation campaigns: Breaking Fake News (show broadcast by the National Television), Factual.ro (political fact-checking site), the Anti-fake newsletter (project of the Eurocommunication Association), the Laboratory for Information Warfare Analysis and Strategic Communication (LARICS) etc.

2.12 Spain

2.12.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

The period from March 2021 to September 2022 begins with a change in the person responsible for the implementation of the communication strategy for the management of the pandemic against COVID-19 at the national level. The appointment of Carolina Darias, in January 2021, as the new Minister of Health (BOE, 2021) introduced a remarkable change in the ministerial spokesperson. This ministerial change comes just as the third wave of the SARs-CoV-2 virus is developing in Spain and the first shipments of doses of COVID-19 vaccines, developed by the companies Moderna, BioNTech-Pfizer and AstraZeneca/Oxford, are arriving in Spain (La Moncloa, 2021). Until January 2021, Darias had served as Minister of Territorial Policy and on multiple occasions accompanied former Minister of Health, Salvador Illa, to meetings of the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System (CISNS).

Contrary to the key role played by the former Minister of Health in the communication strategy on the management of the pandemic, a role that he exercised alternately with the Director of the Health Alerts and Emergencies Coordination Centre (CCAES), Fernando Simón, Minister Darias has opted for a discreet style of spokesperson, with few and occasional appearances before the media through press conferences, normally held at the Government Headquarter, the Palacio de La Moncloa. This limited media exposure has been balanced by the greater involvement of the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System and the technicians and middle managers of the Autonomous Communities in the communication related to the management of COVID-19.

Throughout the vaccination process (i.e., from January 2021 or from the third wave onwards), the presence of technical profiles accompanying health authorities or alternating with them as spokespersons is a frequent practice at the regional level (autonomous communities) and among the working groups within the Interterritorial Council of the National Public Health System. The result of these communication practices has been a decentralised and multi-layered constellation of spokespersons, usually responsible for the implementation of health measures or for monitoring their evolution.

The contents of the information have been mainly of a medical nature and secondarily of a political nature, based on scientific evidence, mainly on recommendations from the World Health Organisation and the European Medicines Agency (EMA), these being the international and European sources preferably referred to by this ministry. At the national level, the various expert committees and working groups associated with the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System (CISNS), as well as the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products, are the sources of information regularly cited by the Spanish ministerial spokesperson.

As part of the de-escalation process, the communication strategy that - since the beginning of the pandemic - had been shared alternately by the Ministry of Health and the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System (CISNS) was also decentralised to the Autonomous Communities, which had to manage - based on the so-called "new normality" - the response to the health crisis in their respective territories. On this basis, communication on the management of the pandemic, during the period from March 2021 to September 2022, was also maintained as a multi-spokesperson strategy, with a coordinated response, communicatively fragmented and decentralised through the spokespersons of the different parties involved.

During the period March 2021 to September 2022, official data have indicated that mortality has been reduced compared to the first months of the pandemic (first wave), although the number of contagions has increased significantly throughout 2021 and 2022 (third wave onwards). In March 2021, the availability of different modalities of vaccines in the country has also contributed significantly to this initial perception of relative relief. This partly explains that until May 2022 Spanish authorities offered daily information about contagions, hospitalizations, and deaths. Since that month and onwards, the strategy for managing and tackling the pandemic, from the health point of view, has adjusted the health intervention to a scenario similar to that of the flu seasonal epidemic. Consequently, from the beginning of 2021 until now, the CISNS has also adopted a new strategy of communication, focusing on the COVID-19 vaccination process.

The vaccination process in Spain was framed by the Spanish COVID-19 Vaccination Strategy (GTV, 2020). This strategy was drawn up, in September 2020, by the COVID-19 Vaccination Technical Working Group (GTV) of the Interterritorial Council of the National Health System (CISNS).

Regarding the steps identified on new communication strategies, it is possible to mention some communication practices used by the CISNS between March 2021 and September 2022 in a couple of areas or dimensions:

- Understanding how public perceive risk is important to tailor communication appropriately and align messages with public perception
- Informing and advising the public (immediate and long-term post-emergency) - from March 2022, the COVID-19 vaccination strategy coexists with the new surveillance and control strategy.

2.12.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

Press conferences have mostly been aimed at making specific announcements on future measures or adjustments of existing measures in relation to the health management of COVID-19, especially on vaccination. In addition, daily reports called "Covid-19 situation status" (in Spanish "Estado de situación del Covid-19") have also been published with daily updated data on the total number of confirmed COVID-19 cases and deaths due to this virus, reported by the Autonomous Communities to the National Epidemiological Surveillance Network (SiViEs system). Likewise, press releases have been published from the official website of the Government <https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/> and the Ministry of Health as channels to inform about the agenda of this ministry related to COVID-19. The Ministry of Health also has an official website with updates on COVID-19-related public health alerts for health professionals.

The Ministry of Health's press conferences about the vaccination process were particularly devoted to reporting on the number of doses purchased, arriving in the country, and delivered or distributed to the health systems of the autonomous communities. The ministry has also regularly informed the public about the number of people vaccinated and the development of the vaccination schedule.

The communication channels used for the vaccination campaign were mainly videos on social networks, media spots, posters, and banners. In addition to this campaign, the Ministry of Health has made available a specific website with questions and answers on the COVID-19 vaccination strategy, as well as a section called "Information for Citizens on COVID-19" on its official website. The Spanish Agency for Medicines and Health Products also has specific information on Covid-19 vaccines on its official website.

In programme terms, the vaccination strategy and its implementation have been regularly updated by the GTV. Communicatively speaking, the reports of the successive updates of the Covid-19 vaccination strategy have been the preferred channel through which the CISNS has sent its key messages. Aimed at a general audience, through these update reports, the media has been able to report in detail on the adjustments, corrections, and innovations of the vaccination campaign. Currently, eleven update reports on the vaccination strategy are available (GTV, 2020), which include future measures and modifications or adjustments to previous vaccination measures.

The content of these update reports is mainly based on scientific evidence, normally using as sources studies or research carried out by its expert committees and by research centres associated with the Ministry of Health (National Epidemiology Centre, Carlos III Health Institute, Spanish Medicines Agency), as well as research centres or international organisations such as the European Medicines Agency or the World Health Organisation. These update reports have also been one of the main inputs for the Health Minister's press conferences to report on new measures adopted or changes to existing measures of the national vaccination strategy.

In December 2021, in the context of the Christmas holidays and due to the increase in infections, some autonomous communities -such as Madrid- launched campaigns encouraging people to take antigen self-tests, which led to a shortage of these tests in pharmacies.

2.12.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

Communicatively speaking, the main target audience has been citizens in general, especially throughout the vaccination campaign, although the most targeted groups for the intervention of health measures have continued to be - since the beginning of the pandemic - the elderly (60 years of age and older), people with previous diseases, and immunocompromised people.

In May 2021, the health authorities decided to vaccinate with the Janssen vaccine to groups in situations of socio-economic vulnerability and social exclusion, especially the homeless (GTV, 2021a, p. 9). In some Spanish regions such as Madrid, a special vaccination campaign against COVID-19 was deployed to inform and immunise this population with the Janssen's single-dose vaccine (Madrid City Council, 2021).

2.12.4 Strategies: Methods used

The availability of the different vaccines, from the end of December 2020 onwards, introduced a new scenario. Then the vaccination campaign, conceived as "the symbol of hope in the face of fear", has guided the communication strategy, which has maintained the practice - introduced by the former Minister - of limiting the media exposure of high-level decision-makers, while at the same time increasing the involvement of technical staff and middle managers in communication on the management of the pandemic.

2.12.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

While the Spanish population in general has been receptive to vaccination, one of the main steps identified for the new communication strategies, established as of March 2021, has been aimed at reducing the public's perceived risk of vaccines and their potential side effects, as well as the misinformation generated by this social perception, especially after the alerts about cases of thrombosis allegedly associated with the AstraZeneca vaccine during the second quarter of 2021. In this regard, the Ministry of Health, together with the Spanish Red Cross, launched and disseminated in

the media and social networks the mass campaign #I vaccinate myself for sure (in Spanish #Yo me vacuno seguro). The key messages of the campaign were: "For me, for you and for all people #IVaccinateMyself", "Vaccination protects you, your loved ones and everyone" and "Vaccine by vaccine we will overcome the pandemic".

This campaign, aimed at all citizens, pursued two complementary objectives: on one hand, to raise awareness among the population about the advisability of vaccination and encourage positive individual behaviour (or, where appropriate, a change in behaviour) towards vaccines, by informing about the safety of vaccines and their health benefits; and, on the other hand, to stimulate vaccination among the general population, considering that in Spain vaccination is legally voluntary and not compulsory.

2.13 Sweden

2.13.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

During the period of March 2021 and September 2022 several changes occurred in the official handling of the COVID-19 pandemic in Sweden. On 1 November 2021 the director of the Public Health Agency, Johan Carlsson, resigned and was replaced by Karin Tegmark Wisell, on 29 November 2021 a new prime minister was elected, Magdalena Andersson, and on 1 March 2022 the state epidemiologist, Anders Tegnell, who had been the main spokesperson of the government's information about the COVID-19 pandemic, resigned and was replaced by epidemiologist Anders Lindblom. From that point on, Tegmark Wiksell was the most frequently appearing spokesperson of the agency.

Also, important to keep in mind, is that the Swedish Government did not carry out or administer information campaigns on vaccinations itself but delegated the task to national/regional authorities

The Swedish information and communication activities regarding the COVID-19 pandemic at the national level were regulated by Government mandates to two public agencies:

- On 19 March 2020 the Swedish Civil Contingency Agency (SCCA) was appointed to coordinate and efficiently produce information on the pandemic to the population.
- On 17 December 2020 the Public Health Agency was commissioned by the Government to carry out coordinated national information campaigns on vaccination against COVID-19 to the public together with the Swedish Civil Contingency Agency (SCCA), the Swedish Medical Products Agency (SMPA) and the National Board of Health and Welfare (NBHW).

The Public Health Agency coordinated the information assignment, and was together with SCCA, the National Board of Health and Welfare and the Medical Products Agency responsible for the activities and campaigns that were carried out based on the agencies' respective areas of responsibility.

An inter-agency operational working group with communicators from the Public Health Agency, the Medical Products Agency, SCCA and the National Board of Health and Welfare was formed to drive the operational work of the information efforts.

2.13.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

March 2021 to September 2022 has been characterised mainly by information efforts targeting vaccinations and the gradual phasing out of preventive measures as the spread of infection declined and came under control. From 1 April 2022, COVID-19 was no longer classified as a disease of public

health concerns by the Swedish government authorities. Society opened again, and on 9 April several restrictions and recommendations were withdrawn.

The focus of the national information efforts on COVID-19 vaccination was to provide easily accessible information to the general public and tailored information to specific target groups. The aim was for everyone to have sufficient knowledge to make an informed choice about vaccination.

At the beginning of the year (2021) the focus of the information campaign was to ensure that facts and information on the vaccination against COVID-19 were collected and made available before, during and after vaccination campaigns launching. The information was aimed to raise awareness and provide reassurance by addressing important questions people were asking.

The communication efforts during the autumn 2021 focused on reaching out to those who had not yet been vaccinated and were built on the issues that were important to them.

Focus of communication efforts during 2021:

- Spring 2021: Communication to increase knowledge and reassurance was complemented by communication to support and motivate vaccination.
- Summer 2021: Communication targeting younger age groups and people on holiday.
- Autumn 2021: Reach the last 20% who had not yet been vaccinated against COVID-19.

While national authorities were responsible for informing the public about the need to vaccinate, Sweden's regions were responsible for providing information on how, where and when to get vaccinated. The regions offered vaccination in different ways. The basic information was disseminated and always available via the website 1177.se – a site for information and health care advice operated by the Swedish regions.

2.13.3 Strategies: Methods used

The information efforts were based on those who were in favour of vaccination to support those who were hesitant, for example by highlighting the proportion who had already been vaccinated.

To provide knowledge and reassurance as well as support and motivation for the decision to vaccinate, interventions were based on both factual and emotional messages.

Evidence-based information was the basis for communication throughout the year and was subsequently complemented by communication aimed at providing support and motivation for vaccination.

To reach persons in need of information in other languages than Swedish the following activities were implemented:

- Posters, videos, and fact sheets with information in other languages,
- Dialogue and cooperation with organisations, leaders of different groups, such as cultural, linguistic, or religious groups, and cooperation with civil society,
- Videos and dialog with leaders and members of faith communities.

Several information campaigns were launched in each region.

2.13.4 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

The main messages were targeted at the general public and complemented by sub-messages relevant to different target groups. The information was designed for different groups in society based on

accessibility requirements and considering language, imagery, graphic design, and information channels.

The Public Health Agency was responsible for facts, evidence, and information on vaccination against COVID-19 to the public and groups where coverage of other vaccinations was lower. The National Board of Health and Welfare was responsible for coordinating information and communication on vaccines to health care professionals.

Identified target groups and efforts made to reach them: The aim was to make the information available to as many people as possible.

The Public Health Agency administered several webpages on vaccination against COVID-19 translated in twenty languages.

SCCA had a collection page for translated and accessible material.

To reach people aged 18-25 and 16-17, mainly digital channels aimed at younger target groups were used, such as Facebook, YouTube, Instagram stories, Snapchat, and Twitch.

Based on knowledge of those most affected by the pandemic and attitudes towards the COVID-19 vaccine and other vaccinations, the following groups were identified as requiring targeted and specially designed information:

- People who were not reached through broad information channels, for example for linguistic or technical reasons,
- People with lower acceptance of other vaccinations,
- People who felt more hesitant about COVID-19 vaccination,
- People who were more severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic.

As the vaccination against COVID-19 kept opening access to everyone beyond risk groups, the Västra Götaland Region VGR made extensive communication efforts to reach relevant target groups. The messages were adapted to the current target group and included, for example, advertisements in free-of-charge newspapers and the mailing of postcards to elderly residents in Västra Götaland, the publication of up-to-date information on VGR's social media and websites for younger target groups, as well as the ongoing publication of up-to-date vaccine information on the 1177.se regional page for Västra Götaland. Additionally, several major communication campaigns/activities were conducted.

2.13.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

The SCCA continuously monitored misinformation and rumour spreading in Sweden about COVID-19 and vaccinations and sent weekly reports to relevant authorities for prioritisation of information efforts. In spring 2021, the SCCA conducted a vulnerability analysis on vaccine hesitancy with the aim of identifying groups that were not reached by the authorities' information or groups that were vulnerable to disinformation about vaccination against COVID-19. The results were weighed against other studies on vaccine acceptance and used as a basis for designing and targeting information efforts.

The Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency was responsible for continuously monitoring and, where necessary, addressing misinformation, disinformation and rumour spreading about COVID-19 vaccination.

A specific Vaccine Podcast was launched. It was a result of the vaccine follow-up showing that men under 50 and age-groups under 39 had a slightly lower willingness to vaccinate. These age-groups had also indicated that they needed more information about the benefits and risks of vaccination. The podcast was chosen as an information channel based on the need to provide more in-depth facts from experts on different issues regarding the vaccination. Podcasts in general were the information channel that was increasing the most, especially in the mentioned target groups. Podcast listening was increasing during the summer and was a cost-effective and flexible format for quickly capturing and highlighting relevant issues. A broader launch activity was carried out for the Vaccine Podcast with promotion in other podcasts that were already popular with the target audiences. During the spring, summer and autumn of 2021, web ads for the podcast were featured on aftonbladet.se (biggest national online newspaper) with a particular focus on podcast episode 7, which responded to vaccine doubters with facts about vaccine safety.

2.14 Switzerland

2.14.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

There have not been major changes in communication strategies, plans and practices in Switzerland.

The two most essential documents in force, which might have been essential during the pandemic, are the Influenza Pandemic Plan Switzerland (Influenza-Pandemieplan Schweiz) and COVID-19 management: Strategic foundations of the GDK and the EDI-BAG (COVID-19-Bewältigung: Strategische Grundlagen der GDK und des EDI-BAG).

The last update of the “Influenza Pandemic Plan Switzerland” took place in 2018 and it is provided by the Federal Office of Public Health (Bundesamt für Gesundheit, BAG). It includes its own chapter about communication, outlining how communication between public authorities and the population should be organised. The plan differs between two different types of communication, as there are: coordinative communication, which serves as support for enforcement, and informative/behavioural communication, addressing different stakeholder groups. There are also different actors to which the communication plan applies. These actors have already been described in D7.1, as well as the fact that they must follow the “One-Voice-Principle”, meaning that respective responsibilities have to be clearly defined. The BAG is the major responsible body regarding the technical management of communication in all situations. However, depending on the escalation level, also other institutions could oversee specific communication tasks or decision-making processes (e.g., the General Secretariat of the Federal Department of Home Affairs, the Federal Department of the Interior; the Federal Chancellery or the Federal Council).

Communication varies depending on the pandemic phase. Therefore, the plan distinguishes between:

- Sensibilisation during normal Influenza activity, meaning that the population should be sensitised to certain behavioural measures or vaccines;
- Risk communication, in case of an early pandemic phase, where comprehensive, transparent, and continuous information should be transmitted to the population;
- Crisis communication, during a pandemic, where responsible authorities are providing up-to-date information, which addresses all stakeholder groups.

The document “COVID-19 management: Strategic foundations” was published in October 2020 and is the result of a cooperation between the Conference of the Cantonal Health Directors (Konferenz der kantonalen Gesundheitsdirektorinnen- und direktoren, GDK), the Federal Department of the Interior (Eidgenössisches Department des Inneren, EDI) and the BAG. This document also provides a short chapter about communication. However, the content is very generic the following points are outlined:

- Communication campaigns must divide the situation into three stages (of epidemic development) and adapt the respective information to the demands of the population;
- Corresponding campaign concepts and products are being created on the part of the Federal Government;
- Existing coordination between the Confederation and the cantons with regard referring to communication must be continued and intensified in accordance with responsibilities and confidentiality;
- The cantons are important ambassadors for credible communication, so communication of the cantons to the population should be strengthened.

The Swiss National COVID-19 Science Task Force was dissolved on the 31st of March 2022. Due to the end of an “acute crisis situation” the actions of the task force were not seen as a necessity anymore. Moreover, there have been violations against certain agreements with the health authorities, as members of the task force were not allowed to communicate directly with the media or on social networks unless they were doing so exclusively on their own behalf. That referred especially to the announcement of new measures, which have only been made after they have been announced by the authorities. Some members of the task force do not always take these provisions into account, referring to their public statements in the mainstream media and social networks.

However, it has been stressed several times by the task force that although its work is now over, the pandemic is not over.

2.14.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

Media organisations played a major role through fulfilling information and sensibilisation tasks throughout the pandemic. They kept the population informed with the help of regular reporting, special news regarding COVID-19 or (critical) documentations. The media landscape of Switzerland is composed of various mass media organisations which can differ from canton to canton. Therefore, it would go beyond the scope of this report to list each of them. However, we want to mention the SRF (Schweizer Rundfunk, the Swiss public broadcaster) which had a central role during the pandemic.

This is somewhat reflected by the Swiss population through an increase in demand and trust in quality journalism (first and foremost, the public broadcaster, followed by subscription newspapers such as swissinfo.ch). However, the economic crisis of news media is an ongoing issue that particularly quality journalism must face. The COVID-19 pandemic also had an impact on the topic reported by journalists, shifting the focus away from soft news (sports, human interest) towards politics (Jahrbuch Qualität der Medien Studie 2021).

In February 2022 a representative study was published on recipients’ satisfaction with the Swiss media’s COVID-19 reporting. Between 30.000 and 60.000 people were surveyed in the period of 2020 to 2022. The study outlined that in February 2022, 30 per cent of Swiss respondents in the survey believed the media provide comprehensive information in their reporting on COVID-19. In comparison, 51 per cent were of this opinion in March 2020. At the same time, more people believe that the media

exaggerate with their "continuous reporting": 45 per cent of respondents in July 2021 agreed with this statement, compared with only 22 per cent in March 2020.

2.14.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

Between March 2021 and September 2022, there have been several campaigns, mainly released under the framework of the “So schützen wir uns” campaign (“How we protect ourselves”). The main authority in charge of the coordination was the BAG. On its website, the BAG provides a structured overview of all campaigns that have been created since the emergence of the pandemic. The following campaigns were published between March 2021 and September 2022, according to the BAG providing information for “all people in Switzerland, in all language regions and from all social milieus”:

- Please Remain Careful (Kampagne “Bitte bleiben Sie vorsichtig”): This campaign was conducted between March and April 2021 when numbers were slowly increasing again. It served as a reminder for people to comply with the behavioural and hygiene rules but also expressed gratitude towards the population.
- “A Heart for All of Us” (Kampagne “Ein Herz für uns alle”): In the spring of 2021, the COVID-19 vaccine was available for the general population in most cantons. The campaign "A heart for all of us" was mainly broadcasted in May and June 2021 and explained that through cooperation (and vaccination) a life without restrictions could be realistic again. At the same time, the hashtag #ichlassemichimpfen (“I am getting vaccinated”) was established not only by individuals but also by institutions, clubs, and associations, which all presented their reasons for getting vaccinated.
- “How we protect ourselves” - Orange Phase: Testing and Vaccination: In May 2021 there has been an increase in cases. Therefore, this campaign was released to raise awareness and to encourage the population to stick to the implemented rules as well as get tested and vaccinated.
- “Regular Testing at Schools, Colleges and the Workplace”: This campaign was conducted in June 2021 and promoted regular testing in schools, universities and in the workplace.
- “COVID-Certificate”: At the end of June, a campaign was launched showing the population the benefits of the COVID certificate and explaining that it is a facilitator for many areas, such as travelling abroad, dancing at the club or attending events.
- “Canton-specific Vaccination Registration”: Since vaccination is coordinated by the cantons, the texts, and presentations of the campaign as well as its playout period, which lasted from June to September 2021, are individualised to the different cantons. It links directly to the appropriate cantonal registration.
- “Get Tested After Vacation” (Kampagne “Nach den Ferien testen lassen”): In August 2021, a campaign was launched to remind the population to get tested after returning from summer vacation so that chains of infection could be interrupted. Vaccinated and recovered persons were exempt from this.
- “Do Not Miss: Get vaccinated” (Kampagne “Nicht verpassen: impfen lassen”): This campaign was conducted during August and September 2021, due to a decreasing number of daily vaccinations. People who had not been vaccinated until that time were particularly addressed.
- “Really? Get Vaccinated!” (Kampagne “Really? Lasst euch impfen!”): The release of this campaign took place in September 2021, especially because of the emerging vaccination scepticism among young adults.

- “Better Get Vaccinated” (Kampagne “Lieber impfen lassen”): The “Better get vaccinated” campaign was launched in October 2021 and emphasised that vaccination against COVID-19 not only provides a high level of protection against severe disease progression but also is a practical alternative to testing and quarantine.
- “Protect Yourself and Others” - orange stabilisation phase: In October 2021, COVID-19 infections were rising. The federal government therefore once again communicated the orange phase to increase caution among the population. In particular, all those who have not yet been vaccinated were encouraged to do so.
- “Affected People Tell their Personal Stories” (Kampagne “Betroffene erzählen ihre persönliche Geschichte”): This campaign was broadcasted from November 2021 until January 2022 because infections number continued to rise and also to clarify the severe consequences of a COVID-19 infection.
- “Protect Yourself and Others” - orange phase: behaviour winter: There was a steady increase in cases in December 2021, since people spent more time in the interiors. Therefore, this campaign was created, encouraging people to comply with the rules, which have been in force then.
- “Booster Vaccination” (Kampagne “Auffrischungsimpfung”): At the beginning of January 2022, only a quarter of the population had a booster vaccination. Therefore, the campaign “Booster Vaccination” was launched, showing the population why a booster vaccination is useful and necessary. According to the BAG’s website, no other campaign was launched in 2022.

Videos:

- Peer-to-peer videos: “Personal Immunisation Decisions of Health and Care Professionals”: This campaign lasted from April to June 2021 and showed health care staff, who explained how they experienced the year 2020 and why they wanted to get vaccinated.
- Testimonial videos promoting COVID-19 vaccination: This video was published simultaneously to the peer-to-peer campaign. Different people from different backgrounds tell why they are going to be vaccinated. However, it must be mentioned that there is no variation in cultural background, but in age and profession.
- Videos of Midwives Promoting the COVID-19 Vaccine: A number of myths and misinformation circulated around the COVID-19 vaccination, including rumours about the vaccines’ effects on fertility. In this video, which was broadcasted from August to September 2021, midwives explain that vaccination does not cause infertility and the reasons why they promote vaccination.

Others:

- “More than half a reason to celebrate” campaign (Aktion “Mehr als ein halber Grund zum Feiern”): By the mid of July 2021, 63 per cent of adults in Switzerland have received at least one coronavirus vaccination. The responsible authorities wanted to thank all those who have been vaccinated and the many people who have been involved and call on them to keep it up.
- National Vaccination Week: In the autumn of 2021, the number of cases increased again but the number of vaccination appointments at the same time decreased. For this reason, the federal government and the cantons were organising a national vaccination week from the 8th to the 14th of November 2021, with various counselling and vaccination offers, events, and free information.

2.14.4 Strategies: Methods used

The ETH Zürich (Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology) developed the so-called “SwissCOVID app” for contact tracing and the identification of an infection risk. The app informs its users if they were in contact with an infected person and is, as such, an effective tool for communicating risks. Due to the end of the above-mentioned “acute crisis situation” and the connected requirement of isolation, the app has been suspended, at least temporarily, at the point in time this report is submitted (October 2022). This was announced according to a decision of the Federal Council, which is in line with legal requirements. These state that the system can be turned off when it is no longer needed to manage the pandemic. In this regard, the Federal Council also points out that the monitoring of the situation will still take place and that the app will be re-set if the pandemic situation requires it. Therefore, the informatics infrastructures will continue to be maintained in the background.

Due to the Federal Council’s effort to collect and bundle ideas of the civil society, the COVID-19 Verbindungsstelle Zivilgesellschaft (COVID-19 Civil Society Liaison Office) was launched to provide an access point for civil society initiatives or organisations working to address the Corona crisis and having a specific request to the federal administration. It was built up by the organisation Staatslabor (state laboratory). As a communication channel between civil society and the Federal Council, the idea was to foster exchange with civil society initiatives. In addition to selecting and funding projects (e.g., an online neighbourhood support platform, hackaton challenges), a roundtable was organised to foster dialogue between the Federal Council and CSOs. It involved 20 representatives from established organisations such as Pro Senectute and the Swiss Red Cross, as well as new initiatives like “Hilf Jetzt” or “Corona Legal” (EID 2020). However, the website is not available anymore and we do not know when it was discontinued.

The “Ja-Kampagne der Zivilgesellschaft” (yes-campaign of civil society), which, in opposition to the anti-measure’s activists, is in favour of the national Covid law. The impetus for the involvement came from an advertising agency in Bern that Peter Metzinger, the campaign director, works with to produce explanatory videos. The agency contacted him in mid-August 2021 asking to publish an explanatory video on COVID-19 and to launch an online campaign. On Twitter, Metzinger kept recruited about a dozen “highly committed” people who work with him on a voluntary basis for the decentral organised committee. Despite this team of supporters, it is only Metzinger in the campaign. This is due to the harsh climate that prevails around this issue as there were already some examples that showed that there are some anti-measure activists who have discarded all decency (e.g., threatening politicians).

2.14.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

On the 4th of February 2021, the COVID-19 Science Task Force published a policy brief on how to cope with Corona denial and how to respond to misinformation and the spread of COVID-19 conspiracy theories. According to the task force, there should not only be a focus on people who disseminate misinformation but also on the certain percentage of the population which finds itself in a challenging situation regarding the formation of opinion during challenging times and wants to gain back a piece of control over an overall uncertain situation (Swiss National COVID-19 Science Task Force 2021, 7). Conspiracy theories provide simple explanations and are specifically designed to respond to the needs of the population, especially to those persons who struggle with discordant information (ibid.). Therefore, the COVID-19 Science Task Force developed the following recommendations for handling conspiracy theories and misinformation:

- **Responding to misinformation:** Since the outbreak of the pandemic, the WHO has extensively tried to mitigate the spread of misinformation which circulated around COVID-19. In September 2020, the WHO and some UN agencies published a joint statement, encouraging member states to work against the dissemination of conspiracy theories, as the decrease in belief in such theories, goes in line with the decrease in misunderstandings and misperceptions. UNESCO and the European Commission (EC) have provided material supporting the critical and fact-checking abilities of the general public. The task force suggests that authorities at the state as well as at the cantonal level should disseminate these materials and strategies, in a way that individuals can integrate them into their daily lives.
- **Encouraging dialogue across society:** According to the task force, the integration of institutions and experts into the public discourse mitigates the presence and the domination of conspiracy theories (Swiss National COVID-19 Science Task Force 2021, 8). Parallel to that, authorities in charge should admit mistakes and wrong decisions since this is perceived as positive on part of the population. Moreover, the adoption of an ‘error culture’ generates a certain degree of transparency between political leaders and/or public health leaders and the population. Beyond that, the task force suggests that there should be an implementation of “deliberative and interactive communication formats”, where members of the civil society are able to come up with pandemic-related concerns and have the opportunity to enter a conversation with authorities and specialists (ibid.).
- **Supporting the adoption of protective behaviours:** During a pandemic, people will always be exposed to a certain amount of contradictory information. This could possibly impact their behaviour towards certain measures, restrictions, and statements on the part of authorities. Therefore, it is essential that the responsible authorities provide a clear and consistent attitude on the measures imposed by them, such as the wearing of masks and physical distancing. These methods are also helpful for the justification of COVID-19-related measures and help to address those percentages of the population who are not sure about whom to believe.
- **Avoiding polarisation:** According to the task force, another important instrument against the spread of misinformation is the non-marginalisation of holders of conspiracy theories since they already heavily mistrust political authorities and institutions. That just supports the progress of social division and subsequently polarisation among different groups.

We do not know whether these recommendations were implemented.

2.15 Wales

2.15.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

The Welsh Government continues to communicate its measures and plan in updated versions of the ‘Coronavirus Control Plan’. Between March 2021 and September 2022, three updated versions have been published:

- **March 2021:** “Coronavirus control plan: revised alert levels in Wales”, which “describes changes to alert levels taking account of vaccination and the dominant Kent strain”.
- **July 2021:** “Coronavirus control plan: alert level 0 (zero)”, which “describes the measures to control coronavirus at alert level 0.”

- October 2021: “Coronavirus control plan: autumn and winter 2021 update”, which “focuses on the options available to us over the autumn and winter period.”

All three plans have brief sections on communication, and the changes in the period can be summarised with the quotation from “Coronavirus control plan: autumn and winter 2021 update”: “Communications have focused on collective responsibility and the need for everyone to maintain the key behaviours to prevent the spread of the virus. This approach will continue” (p. 31).

The Technical Advisory Group that provides the most important pandemic advice to the Welsh Government launched a new report in March 2022 “Living safely with COVID19 in Wales: risk communication and behavioural science perspectives”.

The emphasis in the March 2021 to September 2022 period has shifted to everyone and all business and organisations needing to continue actively taking up anti-COVID measures. Most emphasis is placed on individual behaviours being most crucial in keeping transmission levels, infections, hospitalisations, and death at a low level. This message is based on the ‘Covid Code’ in the Technical Advisory Group’s August 2021 paper Sustaining COVID-safe behaviours in Wales. It is carried over in the Technical Advisory Group’s March 2022 report “Living safely with COVID19 in Wales: risk communication and behavioural science perspectives”.

Changes in the cabinet with reshuffles following general elections on 13 May 2021 and changes at the lower political scale through local elections on 5 May 2022 have minimally impacted the pandemic governance and communications. In both elections, Labour, the left-leaning party that had been in charge during the earlier stages of the pandemic remained in charge and grew in the local elections. The nationalist-independence sentiment of Plaid Cymru reflected growth and the right-wing Conservative party decreased in Wales on national and local levels.

Given that at the national level Labour remained in charge after the May 2021 elections, no new ideological changes were made in communication content and strategies. Newly responsible for the COVID-19 responses as Minister of Health and Social Services at the Welsh Government is Eluned Morgan MS whilst the previous Health and Social Care minister – Vaughn Gething – was put in charge as Minister for the Economy. Spokespeople and organisations that had played a role in the pandemic response remained in the same capacity. The Chief Nursing Officer changed from Jean White to Sue Tranka; other most senior figure stayed largely the same, but at lower levels of seniority many changes occurred, which will have had minimal impact on the management of the pandemic in Wales.

Sources for developing the communication strategies, plans, practices. (None of the following is a new source since March 2021):

- International: World Health Organisation (WHO)
- UK: Scientific Advisory Group for Emergencies (SAGE)
- UK: One of the subgroups of SAGE is the pre-pandemic “Pandemic Influenza Group on Modelling, Operational sub-group” (SPI-M-O)
- UK: One of the subgroups of SAGE is the pre-pandemic “Scientific Pandemic Insights Group on Behaviours” (SPI-B)
- UK: Office of National Statistics (ONS)
- Wales: Joint Committee on Vaccination and Immunisation (JCVI)
- Wales: Technical Advisory Group.

- Wales: the COVID-19 Moral and Ethical Advisory Group Wales (CMEAG) that offers ethical advice and support to policy makers in relation to issues caused or affected by COVID-19.
- Wales: StatsWales

A large group of people were involved in the healthcare organisations' pandemic response formulations and many of the senior figures have been occupied by difficult people. There are too many changes in people occupying job roles to name here. It is only a small minority that has remained in the same job roles as when the pandemic started in Wales.

Public Health Wales has remained responsible for the operationalisation of the Welsh Government guidelines, but the communication seems to have improved between the organisations (this is based on WP5 interviews though). In Wales the Health Boards are not health authorities and cannot impose laws, but targets are set jointly by the Welsh Government and NHS Wales.

The Public Health Wales website seemed to have largely retained its intensity of publishing resources on the pandemic, even though the website content is not possible to trace in terms of dates added or updated.

2.15.2 Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

The Public Health Wales website 'Knowledge Base' was updated until January 2022; it entails studies and recommendations from a wide variety of source organisations, such as WHO research and statements, universities, research institutes, governmental agencies, and private organisations. It does continue to publish updates on quantitative pandemic data and interpretations; in particular in weekly reports: the "COVID-19 weekly surveillance and epidemiological summary". This data and its interpretations serve as future evidence for policymaking for Public Health Wales and the Welsh Government.

The monthly 'COVID-19 current awareness bulletins' from the Public Health Wales Knowledge Base ran until December 2021 and were then integrated into the more broadly defined awareness bulletins that cover other diseases and public health news in Wales. As such, COVID-19 became normalised as yet another disease in the present range in Wales.

In March 2021, the Welsh Government released a new video with the main point being Covid-19 hasn't gone away and listing five reminders of individual behavioural measures people should stick to, to keep safe (meeting outside, wearing a mask, washing your hands, staying at home when unwell, and get fully vaccinated).

Public warning and assurance happened with regards to safety concerns with AstraZeneca COVID-19 vaccine in April 2021. Public Health Wales put out a statement to assure people in Wales that the benefits outweigh any concerns of this vaccine.

In December 2021, coinciding with the first Omicron wave and in the run up to Christmas, the Welsh Government released its latest campaign: "Disrupt the transmission". According to the website, it focused on the importance of face masks, vaccinations, testing and self-isolation. New in this campaign was the importance of ventilation and the use of lateral flow tests before socialising. The campaign materials were also shared with other organisations to distribute on their own social media channels. It was visible as TV adverts, digital posters at shopping centres and bus stops, as well as audible on the radio and Spotify, and it was broadcasted via social media (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Snap Chat, Twitter, and YouTube). According to the Welsh government website, the campaign reached more than

91% of adults in Wales. Also a leaflet was sent to 1.4 million homes and it has been made available in 35 languages, Easy Read, Braille, large print and BSL. In October 2022 the campaign video can no longer be found on YouTube and other websites, nor does feature on the ‘Keep Wales Safe’ website nor on the governmental websites other than the press release on 6 December 2021 . It can still be found on the Facebook of the Swansea Bay University Health Board.

In July 2022, The Welsh Government collaborated with Public Health Wales and the Directors of Public Protection Wales (DPPW) and launched the ‘Communicable Disease Outbreak Plan for Wales (The ‘Wales Outbreak Plan). Communication is an important aspect of the plan. Led by the Outbreak Control Team (OCT) communication strategies strongly resemble those developed and followed during the COVID-19 pandemic. Most importantly (p. 21):

- “Agree who needs to know about this outbreak
- Provide multi-agency updates (SitReps) following OCT meetings – the frequency and timing will depend on the nature of discussions and the frequency of meetings.
- Consider the most appropriate means of communication with identified individuals/bodies, which may include internal & external colleagues, stakeholders, patients/cases and carers, and the public, including the need for an incident room and/or helplines. With professional communications advice, consider the range of communications channels available, including print media, broadcast, and social media).
- Draw up a list of organisations that press statements should be circulated to when released.
- Ensure appropriate information and advice is given to the public, if required
- Ensure accuracy, consistency, and timeliness.
- Use the media constructively.
- Consider the issues around information governance and data protection.”

It also includes specific template-like guidelines for social media posts (p. 22):

“The purpose of such social media posts is to provide reassurance that the organisation has awareness of the issue (and is collaborating with other relevant organisations if this is in progress). It is not to provide any specific details on the incident. That duty lies with the OCT. Therefore, any holding posts released in these circumstances:

- Must not include any details about geography not already circulating in the public domain
- Must not name any alleged source premises (except an educational premises if named already)
- Must not be in response to any deaths without being agreed by the relevant people in their organisation (potential core members as specified in this plan).”

The pandemic communication strategy has changed markedly in terms of tone and focus. The earlier pandemic communication plans were aimed at ensuring the public that the pandemic would end and that the virus would vanish with the government’s policies and practices. Particularly noteworthy was the main plan launched by the Welsh Government in April 2020, ambitiously named “Leading Wales out of the coronavirus pandemic: A framework for recovery”. In March 2022, the Welsh government launched its most recent plan ‘Together for a safer future: Wales’ long-term Covid-19 transition from pandemic to endemic’. In it, the focus is no longer the disappearance of the virus and the return to pre-pandemic normality:

“The recovery plan for Wales will need to address how we can return to work, to education, and meet our families and friends without endangering life or health.”

In that plan, the virus is depicted as entity that is an immediate threat to life and health, from which the logic of separating people from the virus naturally follows. Indeed, in the Foreword of the plan, First Minister Mark Drakeford puts it as follows: “the virus remains a very serious threat to us all and we cannot be complacent in any way”. What complacency means in this quotation is not specified, but the Foreword and the plan does put emphasis on individuals keeping up with sticking to the behavioural rules of self-isolation, testing, social gatherings, and keeping distance, and remaining accepting of more measures that would restrict people’s movements.

The March 2022 plan’s focus has shifted to urging moving towards a co-existence with the virus and the formulation of a new normality. In the Foreword written by First Minister Mark Drakeford (the highest public official in Wales) and Minister of Health and Social Services Eluned Morgan MS, this co-existence and search for new normality is put as follows:

“We can now begin to move beyond the initial emergency phase, which has characterised our response to the pandemic so far. We can begin to plan a future in which we live with coronavirus, just as we live with many other infectious diseases.”

The plan continues to outline how COVID-19 will need to be seen as just another infectious disease, placing it in the same group as Flu, for instance. The need to separate people and virus is thus no longer a logical commitment from the Welsh government. The Foreword also explicitly mentions that the virus is expected to be here to stay, and that life without it is no longer attainable, despite its earlier characterisation as ‘a threat to life and health’:

“But this is a virus full of nasty surprises. In preparing for a different future, we must also be ready to respond quickly to future outbreaks and new variants as we learn to live alongside coronavirus in the long term”.

As such, the communication plan from the Welsh Government normalises the pandemic and includes people in Wales having to accept the virus as part of their life. What had been deemed to make people vulnerable and severely disrupt services and institutional functioning is now no longer supposed to be so powerful. With this plan and characterisation of COVID-19, the Welsh Government absorbs the virus into the normal life processes it governs.

2.15.3 People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

The main recommendation of the latest Corona Control Plan “Living safely with COVID19 in Wales: risk communication and behavioural science perspectives” suggests that behavioural measures are significant especially “through tailoring responses to address behavioural barriers and enablers in clearly identified population groups” (p. 2). Rather than addressing everyone in Wales in the same manner, this report suggests that adapting the government’s message to address different demographics results in better compliance. The plans continue defining vulnerability in accordance with the early-stage formulation of definition that follows clinically defined likelihood to severe illness plus working in healthcare and having an increased exposure to the virus through working with COVID patients. This group remains separate from groups that are recognised as having been subjected to historical marginalisation and occupy a disadvantaged position in Welsh society. These marginalised groups are discussed as needing continued dedicated attention to improve their vaccination rate.

Many larger organisations, such as Housing Association Cymru, do not have new communications on COVID after March 2021, smaller organisations that represent clinically vulnerable groups do. For

instance, Learning Disability Wales continues to communicate guidance and pandemic-related news and updates.

2.15.4 Strategies: Methods used

The government plans and policies continue to employ inclusive language by adopting a style with ‘we’ and ‘our’ that helps blurring the boundaries between the government and the public and addresses the reader specifically by talking to the reader specifically by using ‘you’. The “COVID-19 Moral and Ethical Advisory Group Wales” (CMEAG) does not list new meeting minutes after 29 January 2021. The list of minutes and statements ends with a form with which people can request discussions from the group on particular pandemic-related topics.

Public Health Wales also launched a new campaign ‘How are you Doing’ in March 2022, complete with a video and resources to improve self-care. It emphasises the ongoing uncertainty and the difficulties that come from living in what it calls ‘uncertain times’. Addressing “the negative impact of COVID-19 on the mental, physical and social wellbeing of people in Wales” it brings the focus to the person rather than the virus or measures and extends its acknowledgement of life in pandemic times with its foci. It follows advice from “charities and human rights experts warning that emergency isolation measures to tackle COVID-19 will put disabled, vulnerable and older people at risk.”

The #TimeToBeKind campaign from the Welsh Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) Support Hub that is based on the Public Health Wales’ World Health Organization Collaborating Centre (WHO CC) communicated the ‘promotion of kindness’ during the pandemic via a short film. Based on an evaluation study with Bangor University according to Mark Bellis, the managing Director of the Centre, it “found that film can be a highly effective tool to promote behaviour change for kindness. With the COVID-19 pandemic accelerating a move online for many, the findings of the present evaluation are relevant to how public health messaging can adapt and utilise this space to target individuals and promote behaviour change now and in the future”. As such, short film would be considered a viable new means of communicating behavioural pandemic measures that fit with Alert level Covid Stable from the Welsh Government.

On 11 January 2021 the NHS Wales Respiratory Health Group released its Long COVID Recovery App for Apple and Android smartphones, and on 28 June 2021 it released its 2.0 version which has been developed with Long Covid Wales. According to the app, it provides “all the important information and advice about your COVID recovery in one easily accessible place” (COVID recovery app, 2022).

2.15.5 Misinformation targeting: Impacts

None of the Corona Control Plans mention disinformation, misinformation, or fake news. The TAG does, however, discuss it at length in its advice. For instance, in its August 2021 white paper on ‘sustaining COVID-safe behaviours in Wales’. It recognises that “there is no such thing as a neutral message”. It recommends the usage of ‘credible, trusted messengers’, places emphasis on collectiveness in the Welsh population, both in terms of efforts and concerns, and normalised ‘protective behaviour’ rather than ‘personal restriction’. What constitutes a credible, trusted messenger is not explained.

3 Global analysis of the evolution of COVID-19 communication

This section provides an overall analysis of the changes identified and described in section 2, even though the way each country communicates to their population varies according to its history, culture, policymaking, and so many other factors not accounted for in-depth in this deliverable, but that can be further contextualised with other work developed in WP4-6.

Moreover, subsections 3.1 and 3.2 provide input from each country report regarding: National and international COVID-19 communication evaluation; and main lessons and recommendations, respectively. Subsection 3.3. provides a list of indicators for evaluating risk communication in different countries during the COVID-19 pandemic based on information provided in each country's report, as well as a global analysis of effective communication factors based on literature review.

Epidemiologists warned at the start of the COVID-19 pandemic that to understand how it would evolve, policymakers would have to look beyond the purely medical parameters such as virulence or contagion rates. Psychology would play a large role in people's behaviour and would have to be factored into the public health response. Experience showed that as strategies to combat the virus started to bear fruit, people feared the virus less, and were less inclined to follow rules and official guidance, thereby helping to amplify the impact of any new waves of infection.

If the ebb and flow of fear of disease was well-studied, the same cannot be said of another major determinant of the success of pandemic management, communication. The pandemic produced what came to be known as an "infodemic". This is often used to characterise the flow of false and misleading information from social media platforms, and from some charismatic figures. However, it is clear from the analyses in the preceding section that the communication strategies of public bodies played a major role in either clarifying the situation or making it more confused. In some cases, information that was correct and potentially useful only contributed to people's sense of being overwhelmed by all the data and discussions. In other cases, the reports speak of mixed messages from different sources within government and other institutions, with Irish businesses for instance complaining about inconsistent messages and impractical plans.

Section 2 also confirms the importance of a sound theoretical framework for understanding such a rapidly evolving multi-faceted situation as the pandemic. COVINFORM chose to base its analysis on a combination of complexity and intersectionality theories.

Complexity theory allows us to draw several globally applicable lessons from the case studies on how communication evolves, and should evolve, in a pandemic. First, history matters. The pandemic occurred in each economic, social, political, and cultural context in each country. Among other things, this context determined how much people trusted the government and its messages. In Austria, for example, the communication strategy had to account for mistrust of the government and state broadcaster among vulnerable groups and seek new ways of getting the message across.

Complexity theory also emphasizes emergence. Behaviours emerge through interactions, and they cannot always be foreseen. It is impractical to try to determine the content of communication strategies in advance, but it is possible to create flexible, agile structures that can become operational quickly when the need arises. A third point to keep in mind is that in a complex system, multiple scales are operating at once, from the individual to the planetary. Communication must start with individuals, and positive messages have more chance of influencing behaviour than negative ones. In Switzerland

for example, measures that could be perceived as restrictive were presented as “protective behaviour”, appealing to a sense of personal responsibility.

Intersectionality gives us an insight into how different groups are affected by the situation, and how they adapt their behaviours to cope with it. In particular, it helps to guard against oversimplification when it comes to “vulnerable” groups and people. Behaviour and attitudes may be determined more by religion than ethnicity for example, or more by socio-economic status than religion. In Israel for instance, a range of “identities” had to be considered at the same time. Specific task forces were created to address the concerns of ultra-Orthodox Jews and Muslim Arabs (with a third task force for the rest of the population).

Within this complexity-intersectionality framework, we can draw some global conclusions concerning the main aspects of communication considered in the project and using the topics framed in section 2 (also see Table 1).

3.1 Communication structures & responsibilities

Communication structure and responsibilities in every country recognised the need for a multi-level approach. Each had a national-level committee, and various stakeholders from the medical, scientific, political and non-governmental communities. Existing political structures had a major influence on how communication was organised, as did the size of the country. In Cyprus, for example, most of the responsibility was assumed by just two ministries – Health and Interior – while in the UK the Prime Minister’s Cabinet Office coordinated efforts across the whole of central government and with the devolved governments of Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland.

Not all countries used ministries to coordinate communication. In Greece, for example, although communication plans and strategies as well as messages were drafted and issued through governmental actors (following consultation with outside experts) the actual responsibility for communication initiatives fell to the General Secretariat of Civil Protection.

Coordination posed particular challenges for countries with a strongly decentralised political tradition. Belgium dealt with the question by deciding that the National Crisis Centre would have overall responsibility for coordination and communication regarding the pandemic, but that the federated entities would be responsible for applying central directives in areas devolved to them, such as social care.

Means of communication, Main contents & Communication style

Politics also had a direct impact on communication contents and style, as can be seen in particular in countries such as Sweden and Italy that saw a change of government. In Italy, there was a notable shift in messaging style when Mario Draghi replaced Giuseppe Conte as prime minister. As mentioned above, this was summarised by one commentator as emotional and massive communication under Conte versus an informative and discreet style under his successor.

Although styles of communication inevitably varied depending on who the communicator was, the actual content and means of communication were broadly similar everywhere. Despite the attention devoted to social media and other new forms of communication, it is striking that the traditional press conference was the cornerstone of government communication, with regular participants who had been unknown before the pandemic, such as statisticians or epidemiologists, often achieving star status in the media as the crisis unfolded. This is in stark contrast to the trend that had been gathering

pace before the pandemic to discredit scientific and expert opinion in favour of the views of “real” people and “alternative facts”. This was not enough in itself to counter the masses of fake news and conspiracy theories discussed below, but it did play an important role.

Another traditional means of communication adopted by countries was the telephone. Cyprus for instance created hotlines available 24 hours a day where people could get information on symptoms or legal measures, while Austria created five hotlines providing information on a range of topics from vaccination to vaccination to working in the arts and culture.

Other means of communication that were broadly deployed include dedicated websites and social media initiatives to provide information and encouragement to act. Much of this focused on vaccination initially, even in a country like Spain where vaccine uptake was strong. The second main component was respect for non-pharmaceutical interventions such as social distancing and wearing masks.

As the pandemic subsided, the focus shifted from crisis communication based on vaccination rates, contagion, deaths and so on, to what can broadly be described as living with Covid and, in the words of the UK strategy, building back better. The daily press conferences were suspended, and efforts shifted to reminders that the virus was still present and that vigilance was still required.

People receiving information & Vulnerability considerations

Much information was of course produced for the entire population, but it was quickly recognised that targeted campaigns were needed to reach particular groups. There were roughly two categories of special cases: those not being vaccinated and the vulnerable. The first group can be defined and measured relatively easily, although the reasons for non-vaccination may be more complicated, ranging from lack of knowledge to hostility. The communication strategies considered in this report often give the impression that the same can be said of “the vulnerable”. Similar lists appear across countries, usually featuring the elderly, children, women ethnic minorities, and similar tools were developed, for example information in different languages.

However, if the concept of vulnerability is not used tactfully, it risks alienating the very people agencies are hoping to reach out to and help. It is not clear from the reports whether some authorities had considered what constitutes vulnerability other than belonging to one of the categories listed. In Germany the main criterion seems to have been not speaking German, while information campaigns tried to show a diverse set of people. Others were more precise. Wales for example set out criteria including likelihood of contracting severe illness and working in healthcare, plus being a member of a group that was historically marginalised. Spain’s definition was restricted to those aged over 60, people with previous diseases, and those immunocompromised.

Strategies: Methods used

The ultimate goal of the communication strategies in every country was obviously to get people to act on the information and arguments presented in the desired way. The scientists tended to think that simply presenting the facts in an objective and comprehensible fashion was enough. A major flaw in this approach was that most people had little scientific training, so when messages changed as new data and analyses became available, some accused the experts of lying.

The methods used evolved to include not just websites, social media, and apps, but more personal approaches and “emotional” messaging as the Swedish report says. This usually meant involving

community leaders, particularly from ethnic minorities, and creating information channels thought to correspond best to the habits and expectations of target groups. Italy for example created a communication campaign specifically around vaccination for 5 to 11-year-olds. Emotional messaging is typified in the #TimeToBeKind campaign in Wales that used a short film, judged to be a viable means of communicating behavioural pandemic measures.

There were also attempts to present information in an immediately understandable way, through “traffic light” systems or Belgium’s coronavirus barometer.

Misinformation targeting: Impacts

Misinformation is a global ecosystem, with the same stories quickly spreading from one country to another. Common themes include conspiracy theories that the pandemic was being manipulated by an international elite to further its own goals or claims that the vaccines were killing people or causing serious health problems. As the Romanian study notes, there were also numerous local variants in addition to these common themes. These additions were usually rooted in long-standing issues in the country concerned, such as mistrust of the authorities in former communist countries.

Countries initially tackled misinformation by reacting as quickly as possible to provide objective information, but often, by the time the response was ready the damage had already been done. This prompted a move to a more proactive strategy, with attempts to anticipate attacks at an early stage and provide information through trusted channels. There were successful programmes involving a range of public and private partners along with community groups. In Ireland, for example, Facebook launched a campaign that included institutional partners such as the WHO to inform people how to identify fake news about vaccines. Other countries, including England, provided guidelines on how to verify information before sharing it, for example how to identify the source.

A common feature of efforts to counter misinformation was the call to use trusted messengers, in particular to reach vulnerable groups less likely to use or have access to reliable channels of information. However, in some cases, as the Wales study highlights, this kind of call remained abstract, with no practical guidance on how to identify and recruit suitable partners.

It should be noted that there is little evidence in the country reports about how effective these campaigns were, although Sweden does describe an increase in the numbers of people listening to a podcast targeted at men who were hesitant about vaccines. It could be argued that vaccine uptake, respect of guidelines, etc. could be used as a proxy, but the link may be tenuous given the number of factors that influence behaviour.

3.2 National and International COVID-19 Communication Evaluation

This subsection presents a synthesis based on a global analysis of the review of research and professional analysis to national communication on Covid-19 crisis and successful communication approaches provided by each country report.

The country reports provide comprehensive overviews of communication actions and actors, from which several common points can be identified. Although governments usually devote considerable resources to communication, practices from “normal” times could not simply be transferred to deal with the pandemic.

First, because communication campaigns are usually about subjects the campaigner has chosen and has had time to prepare, not a sudden shock like COVID-19. Few of the essential elements can be prepared long before being used.

Second, the silo approach common to national administrations is a handicap in dealing with the communication (and other) aspects of a crisis like the pandemic, where a health emergency quickly caused a series of cascading failures across numerous systems, we take for granted, including education, transport, commerce and leisure. A traditional communication campaign is usually limited to one subject – road safety, paying tax or whatever – and is entirely conceived and controlled by a single ministry or department. In the pandemic, the need was for what the Belgians called a holistic approach to federate the full spectrum of knowledge, experience and competencies required.

What can be transferred is the skill set needed to communicate, and most countries underline the need to involve communication specialists right from the start, and not after messaging has been defined. Italy is among many countries to emphasize the need to involve communication professionals to help strike a balance between the need for the messages to be simple and the need to supply sufficient information to allow a proper understanding of the issue at hand.

Communicators also had to tackle problems that were not anticipated, or that were amplified by the crisis. Austria for instance dedicated resources to dealing with social tensions the pandemic exacerbated, while several countries found themselves facing a long-term mental health crisis, especially among young people. Spain for example recorded higher suicide rates among following the crisis. This means that communication should not stop once the immediate emergency is over. Health services are likely to feel the aftershocks of COVID-19 for many years to come, and authorities should be prepared to explain the reasoning behind difficult and potentially unpopular decisions they must make.

Another common feature was the massive use of digital tools to inform the population and provide data to the authorities. Many countries developed contact tracing apps, but others went further. Greece moved particularly quickly in this respect, releasing its Covid Checker app in March 2020.

A common conclusion is that subjective factors are primordial in determining the success or failure of communication strategies. Switzerland is only one example of a country that decided not to impose certain measures, but instead to appeal to sentiments such as “national values” to convince people to act for the common good. A linked conclusion is that while some values, beliefs or attitudes are widespread in any country, successful campaigns did not stay at this “macro” level, and instead tried to see how the behaviour and reactions of subcategories of the population were influenced by their social networks, history, culture, education, socio-economic status and so on. Israel for example used an Arab woman wearing a traditional headscarf to get across the message that it was permissible to get vaccinated during Ramadan.

Overall, countries showed themselves to be flexible and willing to adapt communication strategies as the situation evolved. It will however remain too soon to draw definitive conclusions about the impact of their efforts until evaluations using clearly defined, objective criteria are made public.

3.3 Main Lessons and Recommendations

This subsection presents a synthesis based on a global analysis of the main learnings, best practices, and guidelines provided by each country report.

Covid dominated the media for nearly two years, but at the end of the period covered in this report, the emergency is generally considered to be over. Media attention is now focused on the war in Ukraine and the cost-of-living crisis. It remains however important to note the lessons learned from the pandemic because it is inevitable that new crises will emerge in the future and much valuable experience has been gained in how to respond.

The main lessons regarding communication from the above sections can be summarised as 5-Ts that interact with each other. To be successful, a communication strategy must be Trustworthy, Timely, Targeted, Transparent, and Tactful.

Trustworthy. Long-term studies such as the Edelman Trust Barometer have tracked the decline in trust in various institutions, with politicians and the media faring particularly badly. It is well-known that trust takes far longer to build than to destroy, but the country reports do provide several insights into how this can be done. Foremost among these is to remember that effective communication is a two-way process, so authorities must learn to listen to people's concerns, doubts, and suggestions. Identifying the right messenger is also central to building trust. All the countries surveyed soon involved respected figures from the communities they were seeking to communicate with, as well as public figures thought to be able to influence target groups.

Timely. Germany argues that the principles of risk communication are to an extent transferrable to future cases. Timeliness is one of the principles mentioned. Particularly in the early days of an emergency, people need to be informed quickly of the state of knowledge about what is happening and the reasons for any actions proposed. They are receiving information from multiple streams all the time, some of them formal, most of them not, so a difficult balance must be struck between timeliness and certainty. In Austria, the government came in for harsh criticism for announcing the end of the pandemic too early and too often.

Targeted. Targeting does not simply refer to identifying the potential audience. It concerns content too. As the Swedish report underlines, communicating must address matters of relevance to the audience. Targeting also means focusing on an identifiable, achievable objective.

Transparent. Transparent means the message should be clear for the intended audience. Transparent also means being clear about the source and reliability of the elements of a message. If data are limited, say so, and explain why you are using them. The same goes for models. An effort must be made to explain what a model can and cannot do, and, if the case arises, why its previous results turned out to be wrong. Transparency should extend beyond data, modelling, and analysis to include recognising uncertainty and limits in what can be done. In Wales, for example, the authorities explained what they could control and what factors were beyond their control, such as vaccine delivery scheduling.

Tactful. Communicating around a health crisis requires an understanding of what motivates people to change their behaviour. In general, this will be positive messaging. The Swiss government for example stresses the importance of avoiding messages based on guilt and fear, since these tend to entrench the behaviours or attitudes one is seeking to change. It may seem unnecessary to state this, but messages should avoid insulting people. The Greek government had to withdraw a message about social distancing after it was condemned for being sexist.

3.4 Relevant Indicators

This subsection presents the main relevant indicators to evaluate/monitor COVID-19 communication effectiveness, based also on main lessons and best practices provided by each country report, as well as a global analysis of effective communication factors based on literature review.

Several indicators are used to evaluate the effectiveness of risk communication in different countries during the COVID-19 pandemic. The following indicators are the main examples extracted from the analysis of country reports:

- Coordination and consistency
- Parsimony
- Factuality and timeliness
- Transparency regarding uncertainty
- Transparency regarding policymaking
- Relevance
- Representation
- Participation
- Word frequency
- Readability and comprehension
- Evidence-based information
- Accessible information formats
- Diversity of communication channels
- Fact-checking options
- Target communication topic/content
- Considerations of vulnerability
- Vaccination willingness
- Adaptation to recommendations and restrictions
- Trust levels in public authorities and news media
- Media usage
- Population's level of information
- Correct classification and interpretation of information
- Public compliance
- Alienation prevention
- Protective measures (distancing, face masks, avoiding public transport, staying at home, cancelling in-person meetings, home office)
- Solidarity within society
- Public satisfaction
- Values, perceptions, and situations of the public.

Effective communication is critical during times of crisis or risk, as it helps to manage fear and uncertainty and provides individuals with the information, they need to make informed decisions. Table 2 presents the 10 main key principles in risk and crisis communication merging the information provided by partners and literature review (e.g., WHO, CDC).

Table 2. Main 10 key principles for effective risk and crisis communication.

Key principle	Description
1. Be timely and accurate	<p>Timely and accurate information is key in a crisis. As soon as information is available, it must be communicated promptly, and updates must be given regularly as new information becomes available.</p> <p>The first principle of effective risk and crisis communication is to provide information as soon as possible and update it regularly as new information becomes available. This helps build trust with the public and ensures that people have access to accurate and up-to-date information that can help them make informed decisions. WHO suggests that communication must be "timely, transparent, accurate, and accessible."</p>
2. Be transparent	<p>Honesty and transparency are critical in building trust and credibility. Information must be presented openly and truthfully, and it should be stated clearly what is known and what is not known.</p> <p>Being honest and open about what is known and what is not known is an important principle of effective crisis communication. This helps to dispel rumours and misinformation and build trust with the public. Health and Human Services Victoria emphasises the importance of being "honest and transparent about what is known and not known."</p>
3. Be clear	<p>Simple and straightforward language should be used in all communication, and technical jargon must be avoided to ensure that messages are easy to understand.</p> <p>The use of simple and straightforward language, avoiding technical jargon, and making sure messages are easy to understand is another key principle of effective risk and crisis communication. NACCHO suggests using "clear, concise, and culturally and linguistically appropriate messages." The CDC adds that it is important to "avoid technical jargon."</p>
4. Be consistent	<p>It is important to ensure that all information is consistent and does not contradict previous messages. This helps to build trust and credibility.</p> <p>Ensuring that all information provided is consistent and does not contradict previous messages is an important principle of effective risk and crisis communication. This helps build trust with the public and ensures that people are receiving accurate and consistent information. Health and Human Services Victoria stresses the importance of being "consistent in our messaging and actions."</p>
5. Be accessible	<p>Information must be made available to all groups, including those with disabilities and limited proficiency of the language spoken in the person's country of residence.</p> <p>Making information available to all groups, including those with disabilities and limited English proficiency, is a key principle of effective risk and crisis communication. NACCHO suggests using "different forms of media (e.g., audio, visual, large print, easy-to-read, etc.) to ensure accessibility for diverse populations."</p>
6. Engage stakeholders	<p>Two-way communication with stakeholders, including media, community organisations, and other relevant groups, is important in addressing public concerns and dispelling rumours and misinformation.</p> <p>Encouraging two-way communication with stakeholders, including media, community organisations, and other relevant groups, is an important principle of effective risk and crisis communication. This helps to build trust with the public and ensure that people have access to accurate information. WHO suggests that communication must be "two-way, participatory, and empowering."</p>
7. Anticipate and address public concerns	<p>Public concerns must be addressed proactively, and accurate information must be provided to dispel rumours and misinformation.</p> <p>Addressing public concerns proactively and providing accurate information to dispel rumours and misinformation is a key principle of effective risk and crisis communication.</p>

	WHO recommends "anticipating and addressing public concerns and counteracting rumours."
8. Consider cultural differences	Communication must consider cultural differences and communication preferences when developing messages. Considering cultural differences and communication preferences when developing messages is an important principle of effective risk and crisis communication. NACCHO suggests using "culturally and linguistically appropriate messages."
9. Use appropriate channels	The most appropriate channels for communicating with different audiences, including social media, news media, and direct outreach, must be chosen. Choosing the most appropriate channels for communicating with different audiences, including social media, news media, and direct outreach, is a key principle of effective risk and crisis communication. Health and Human Services Victoria emphasises the importance of using "a range of communication channels to reach different audiences."
10. Evaluate and learn	The communication process must be continuously evaluated, and strategies must be adjusted as needed to improve the overall risk and crisis communication approach. Continuously evaluating and learning from the communication process and adjusting strategies as needed is an important principle of effective risk and crisis communication. WHO suggests that communication must be "adaptive and evidence-based."

The Importance of Timeliness in Crisis Communication:

Timeliness is a crucial aspect of crisis communication, as it helps to reduce anxiety and uncertainty, and it also increases the credibility of the information being communicated (Canton et al., 2012). A study by Coombs and Holladay (2010) found that timeliness is a major factor in determining the effectiveness of crisis communication, as it can help to prevent the spread of rumours and misinformation. Moreover, timely communication can also help to manage public expectations and minimise the potential for panic (Canton et al., 2012).

Providing timely information is also important in risk and crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic. This involves regularly updating the public with relevant information, including the latest data and developments, and being transparent about decision-making processes. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention and Public Health England provide guidance on this principle in their publications "Considerations for Schools: COVID-19" (2020) and "COVID-19: communicating with the public" (2020), respectively.

The Role of Source Credibility in Crisis Communication:

Source credibility is another important aspect of crisis communication, as it can influence the perceived effectiveness of the message and the level of trust that individuals have in the information being communicated (Brossard & Shaar, 2006). A study by McCombs and Shaw (1972) found that source credibility is a major determinant of the impact of mass media messages, as individuals are more likely to believe and act on information if they perceive the source to be trustworthy and credible. Additionally, source credibility can also affect the perceived severity and risk of a crisis, as individuals are more likely to view the situation as more dangerous if they believe the source to be credible (Brossard & Shaar, 2006).

Building trust and credibility is another key principle in risk and crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic. This involves establishing and maintaining open communication channels with the public, being transparent about information and data, and responding to public inquiries and concerns

in a timely manner. The Health and Human Services Victoria and the National Association of County and City Health Officials provide guidance on this principle in their publications "COVID-19 Communication Principles" (2020) and "COVID-19 Risk Communication and Community Engagement" (2020), respectively.

Use of Empathy and Emotional Appeal in Crisis Communication:

The use of empathy and emotional appeal can also be effective in crisis communication, as it can help to build trust and establish a connection with the audience (Wicks et al., 2009). A study by Nguyen and Le Roux (2014) found that emotional appeals, such as fear appeals, can be effective in motivating individuals to act during a crisis. Additionally, the use of empathy in crisis communication can help to mitigate negative emotions and provide individuals with a sense of security (Wicks et al., 2009).

In a similar vein, emphasising personal responsibility is another key principle in risk and crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic. This involves educating the public about the actions they can take to reduce their risk of infection and minimise the spread of the virus. The World Health Organization and National Association of County and City Health Officials provide guidance on this principle in their publications "Communicating in a Crisis: WHO guidance on risk communication" (2020) and "COVID-19 Risk Communication and Community Engagement" (2020), respectively.

Clear and Concise Communication:

Clear and concise communication is critical during times of crisis, as it helps to minimise confusion and reduce anxiety (Canton et al., 2012). A study by Lammers et al. (2011) found that clear and concise communication is more effective in reducing anxiety and promoting positive outcomes than more complex or vague communication. Additionally, clear, and concise communication can also help to prevent misunderstandings and ensure that individuals have the information they need to make informed decisions (Canton et al., 2012).

Likewise, risk and crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic requires a clear, concise, and consistent messaging strategy. This includes the use of clear language and avoiding technical jargon, ensuring that messages are consistent across different platforms and delivered by authorised sources. The World Health Organization provides guidance on this principle in their publication "Communicating in a Crisis: WHO guidance on risk communication" (2020).

Addressing rumours and misinformation is also important in risk and crisis communication during the COVID-19 pandemic. This involves monitoring and addressing false information and rumours, providing accurate information to counteract false information, and establishing and maintaining open communication channels with the public. The World Health Organization and Public Health England provide guidance on this principle in their publications "Communicating in a Crisis: WHO guidance on risk communication" (2020) and "COVID-19: communicating with the public" (2020), respectively.

In sum, the indicators vary from country to country, but some common themes can be noted. These include: consistency, factuality and timeliness, transparency with regard to uncertainty and policy-making, relevance, representation, participation, information based on evidence, accessible information formats, diversity of communication channels, and fact-checking tools. Other indicators include vaccination willingness, trust in public authorities and news media, media use by sub-groups in society, population's level of information, public compliance, and public satisfaction with the communication strategy. The indicators also include measures of the effectiveness of communication campaigns and information dissemination, such as the population's reaction, trust levels, and

adherence to protective measures. These factors are deemed relevant to the effectiveness of risk communication and are used to determine how well COVID-19 information is being communicated and received by different populations.

Effective risk or crisis communication is critical for managing fear and uncertainty and providing individuals with the information they need to make informed decisions. Timeliness, source credibility, empathy and emotional appeal, and clear and concise communication are all important factors that contribute to the effectiveness of crisis communication. By understanding these key elements, organisations can develop more effective risk or crisis communication strategies that help to mitigate negative outcomes and promote positive outcomes during times of crisis.

4 Conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic has created a complex communication environment, requiring effective and timely information dissemination to the general public. The various countries in the study have responded to this challenge differently, reflecting their own communication infrastructure, social norms, and political landscape.

Overall, the main sources of information were national and federal governments, which relied on a variety of channels, such as websites, dashboards, hotlines, social media, and press conferences. In several countries, non-government organisations, such as the Austrian Red Cross, also played a role in crisis communication and public health campaigns. Despite the presence of these communication channels, the focus of information has shifted from the general information about COVID-19 to the COVID-19 vaccine, although there is no formal communication strategy in place for the vaccine.

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the need for targeted and inclusive communication strategies, particularly for vulnerable populations. This was emphasised in some countries, where the transition of pandemic coordination and communication to regional authorities and the inclusion of vulnerable populations were noted. The absence of comprehensive evaluations in several countries raises the need for a specific communication component to be included in future early preparedness plans for health crises.

The communication strategies in various countries were also influenced by their political landscape and social norms. In some countries, the communication was driven by political pressure and marked by a more public and systematic evaluation process, while in others, the measures were not mandatory and focused on personal responsibility and national values. This led to differing levels of trust in the government and their communication strategies.

The use of clear and simple language and popular, reliable figures as testimonials for the vaccination campaign has been successful in some countries in reaching a wider segment of the population and achieving good results in terms of vaccination attendance. The use of social media in communicating about outbreaks and diversification of formats for conveying messages have also been noted in some countries.

The COVID-19 pandemic has also highlighted the importance of effective and targeted communication strategies in managing a health crisis. The various countries in the study have approached this challenge differently, but there is a need for a comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of these strategies and the inclusion of a specific communication component in future health crisis preparedness plans.

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